

ENTRUST

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D4.3 Runtime Assurance & Certification Framework – Final Release

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Abstract	<p>This deliverable presents the final release of the ENTRUST Runtime Assurance and Certification Framework, detailing the complete design, implementation, and validation of the security stack for secure lifecycle management of Connected Medical Devices (CMDs). Building upon the foundations laid in D4.2, this work finalizes the ENTRUST Trusted Computing Base (TCB), delivering an integrated and benchmarked solution that supports heterogeneous CMDs, from high-end TEE-based platforms to resource-constrained PUF-based devices. Key contributions include the finalized implementation of Configuration Integrity Verification (CIV), a dual-credential trust model featuring manufacturer-issued Verifiable Credentials (VCs) and dynamic, domain-issued Conformity Certificates (CCs) with privacy-preserving disclosure, and the completed Agile Swarm Attestation protocol for scalable, low-end device security. A primary achievement of this deliverable is the comprehensive security analysis of the core cryptographic schemes, including Attribute-Based Signcryption (ABSC) and</p>		

	<p>privacy-preserving Attribute-Based Credentials (p-ABCs), with formal proofs for unforgeability, confidentiality (IND-CPA), and attribute privacy. The framework’s practical viability is demonstrated through extensive benchmarking results. This work solidifies the ENTRUST architecture into an adaptive, cryptographically sound, and efficient solution for runtime trust assessment in safety-critical medical ecosystems.</p>
Keywords	<p>Attestation, Verifiable Credentials, Root of Trust, OP-TEE, PUF, Connected Medical Devices, p-ABC, DAA, Swarm Attestation, CIV</p>

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Nature of the deliverable:	O*	
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public, fully open	X
SEN	Sensitive, confidential to ENTRUST project and Commission Services	

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

DMP: Data Management Plan

Glossary of terms and abbreviations used	
Term	Description
AAA	Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting
ABAC	Attribute-based Access Control
ABE	Attribute-based Encryption
ABS	Attribute-based Signatures
ACL	Access Control List
AE	Authenticated Encryption
AK	Attestation Key
ATL	Actual Level of Trust
CA	Certification Authority
CC	Conformity Certificate
CFA	Control-Flow Attestation
CIV	Configuration Integrity Verification
CMD	Connected Medical Device
DAA	Direct Anonymous Attestation
DID	Domain Identifier
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
DM	Domain Manager
EAP	Enhanced Authentication Protocol
ECU	Electronic Control Units
EK	Endorsement Key
FV	Formal Verification
FW	Firmware
HSM	Hardware Security Module
HW	Hardware
IDM	Identity Management
IDS	Intrusion Detection System
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IoT	Internet of Things
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
KMS	Key Management System
MUD	Manufacturer Usage Descriptions

NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
PSK	Pre-Shared Key
PUF	Physically Unclonable Function
p-ABC	Privacy-preserving Attribute-Based Credential
RA	Risk Assessment
RATS	Remote ATtestation procedureS
RoT	Root of Trust
SM	Security Monitor
SoS	System of Systems
SW	Software
TA	Trusted Application
TCB	Trusted Computing Base
TCG	Trusted Computing Group
TEE	Trusted Execution Environment
TPM	Trusted Platform Module
VC	Verifiable Credentials
VP	Verifiable Presentation
ZTO	Zero-touch onboarding

Executive Summary

Deliverable D4.3 – *Runtime Assurance and Certification Framework (Final Release)* – constitutes the final technical outcome of Work Package 4 within the ENTRUST project. It provides the complete design, implementation, and validation of a comprehensive security stack for Connected Medical Devices (CMDs), aligned with zero-trust principles and regulatory requirements for safety-critical environments such as healthcare. The proposed security stack enables runtime assurance through a Trusted Computing Base (TCB) that supports heterogeneous CMD platforms, including both high-end devices equipped with Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs) and constrained devices that rely on lightweight cryptographic roots-of-trust based on Physical Unclonable Functions (SRAM-PUFs). It finalizes the implementation of key mechanisms, including:

- **Configuration Integrity Verification (CIV)** to detect unauthorized configuration changes and preserve device integrity;
- **Conformity Certificates (CCs)** to dynamically encode trust assessments and support selective disclosure of certified properties;
- **Swarm Attestation Protocols** based on one-time signature aggregation to assess the collective trustworthiness of device clusters;
- **Attribute-Based Signcryption (ABSC)** for secure and privacy-preserving communication of credentialed attributes;
- **Privacy-respecting credential disclosure mechanisms**, leveraging blinding techniques and Zero-Knowledge Proofs (ZKPs) to ensure unlinkability and minimal disclosure.

A key contribution of this deliverable lies in the realization of a dual-credential model, comprising manufacturer-issued Verifiable Credentials and domain-issued CCs, enabling layered trust evaluation and dynamic trust reassessment. The final framework also supports secure firmware update validation, runtime credential reissuance, and scalable attestation across constrained deployments. The cryptographic protocols introduced are verified against a variety of security properties, including confidentiality of IND-CPA, attribute anonymity, key binding, and unforgeability. In addition, the deliverable reports benchmarking results for all critical operations, demonstrating the practicality and efficiency of the framework across representative hardware platforms.

As part of ENTRUST's broader vision, D4.3 also outlines the integration of experimental optical PUFs as alternative hardware-based roots of trust. Although not yet integrated into the main runtime assurance stack, preliminary robustness and unclonability assessments suggest promising future directions for extending hardware diversity in trust anchors. In conclusion, this deliverable consolidates ENTRUST's contributions to trusted and privacy-preserving CMD lifecycle management. The finalized framework enables an adaptive, cryptographically sound, and scalable runtime trust evaluation, laying the foundation for future adoption in regulated medical infrastructures.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Scope and Purpose

ENTRUST's overarching vision is to facilitate the secure lifecycle management of Connected Medical Devices (CMDs), considering the stringent security and safety properties essential in medical service-graph-chains. To achieve this, ENTRUST leverages Trusted Computing and advanced cryptographic primitives, aiming to transform CMDs into security-hardened tokens for which trust can be bootstrapped from secure boot processes through to runtime trust assessment. This deliverable, D4.3, represents the final release of the ENTRUST Runtime Assurance and Certification Framework. It builds upon the architectural concepts and technical implementations presented in Deliverable D4.2, providing the complete and integrated instantiation of the ENTRUST Trusted Computing Base (TCB). This release finalizes the development of key security and trust mechanisms to support the lifecycle management of CMDs according to zero-trust principles.

The core purpose of this deliverable is to consolidate the ENTRUST trust stack, capturing the finalized implementation, integration, and evaluation of core components such as Attribute-Based Signcryption (ABSC), Conformity Certificates (CCs), agile swarm attestation for resource-constrained devices, and advanced privacy-preserving attestation techniques. Additionally, this deliverable presents the supporting security proofs, benchmarking outcomes, and interfaces that allow runtime trust assessments across heterogeneous CMD environments.

The core functionalities refined and finalized within this deliverable, as part of the secure lifecycle management of CMDs, encompass:

- **Runtime Trust Assessment:** The core of the ENTRUST framework lies in enabling CMDs to dynamically establish and maintain trust relationships between nodes in medical service-graph-chains. This is achieved through novel attestation protocols that integrate contextual and evidence-based security assertions. D4.3 introduces final optimizations and benchmarking of mechanisms for Continuous Integrity Verification (CIV), Direct Anonymous Attestation (DAA), and dynamic Attribute-Based Credentials (ABCs), all serving as the bedrock of runtime assurance.
- **Secure and Auditable Software/Firmware Updates:** Maintaining system trust in the face of emerging threats and detected misconfigurations requires secure update mechanisms. The ENTRUST framework supports cryptographically protected and trust-aware update distribution paths. These are backed by runtime assessment results, ensuring that updates are triggered and validated based on real-time device trustworthiness and conformity status. D4.3 presents some of the foundational building blocks for this process.

- **Issuance and Renewal of Conformity Certificates (CCs):** Building upon the intermediate definitions from D4.2, D4.3 delivers the final design and integration of Conformity Certificates as runtime verifiable artefacts that encapsulate a device's security posture. CCs are generated in a privacy-preserving manner and support selective disclosure through zero-knowledge crypto protocols. Their issuance is supported by the Trust Assessment Framework (TAF) and dynamically reflects both manufacturer-assured and domain-specific attestations.
- **Swarm Attestation and Lightweight Trust Mechanisms for Low-End Devices:** Recognising the diversity of CMD capabilities, ENTRUST has extended its attestation framework to support resource-constrained and highly distributed hospital environments, where large numbers of low-end medical devices must be attested efficiently and securely. This deliverable finalises the swarm attestation architecture, leveraging one-time signature schemes (WOTS/WOTS+), Merkle-tree-based aggregation, and dynamic challenge-response protocols.

Essentially, D4.3 represents the culmination of ENTRUST's efforts towards constructing a **fully interoperable security stack**. It provides the definitive and thoroughly benchmarked components, and, crucially, a comprehensive security analysis with **formal proofs** for the cryptographic protocols designed to support the envisioned functionalities.

1.2 Relation to Other WPs and Deliverables

This deliverable, D4.3, serves as the final technical specification for the ENTRUST Runtime Assurance and Certification Framework, consolidating and extending the work presented in D4.1 (which laid out the functional requirements and initial architecture) and D4.2 (which provided the first release of the framework and its components). As the third and final deliverable of Work Package 4 (WP4), D4.3 provides the definitive trusted computing and cryptographic primitives, along with their comprehensive security analyses and performance benchmarks.

The finalized framework and its components detailed herein are critical inputs for several other Work Packages:

- **WP2:** The architectural and security requirements defined in D2.1 and D2.2 provide the reference model within which the runtime assurance mechanisms are instantiated. In D4.3, these requirements are enforced through privacy-preserving cryptographic protocols that enable dynamic trust assessment.
- **WP3:** The TCB design that is completed here acts as a runtime enabler for WP3 outcomes, supporting secure software/firmware updates, providing integrity verification mechanisms, and closing the loop between design-time threat modelling and runtime remediation via attestations and conformity assessment.
- **WP5:** The finalised implementation of Conformity Certificates, Verifiable Credentials (VCs), and Verifiable Presentations (VPs) directly supports WP5's decentralised certification and auditing workflows. The runtime outputs of the TCB feed into the broader trust management plane, enabling domain-level and cross-domain trust establishment.
- **WP6:** The complete TCB stack reported in this deliverable is integrated into the system demonstrators and pilot environments described in WP6. D4.3 provides key artefacts for the system-level validation activities carried out in D6.1 and D6.2, where real-world use cases are used to assess the performance, scalability, and interoperability of the ENTRUST framework.

This deliverable also finalizes the ENTRUST interoperable security stack, designed to run across diverse medical devices by instantiating tailored TCBs for high-end (ARM-based TEEs) and low-end (SRAM PUF-based) CMDs. The extensive security proofs provided for the novel cryptographic schemes ensure a high degree of confidence in their robustness and suitability for the sensitive medical domain. The work on Agile Swarm Attestation further extends these capabilities to manage groups of devices efficiently and securely.

Figure 1.1: Relation of D4.3 with other WPs and Deliverables.

1.3 Deliverable Structure

The deliverable is organized as follows:

- **Chapter 1** introduces the scope and purpose of the document, highlighting its role as the final specification of the ENTRUST Runtime Assurance and Certification Framework and its relationship with other project deliverables.
- **Chapter 2** presents updates and refinements to the ENTRUST Trusted Execution Architecture for Secure CMD Lifecycle Management.
- **Chapter 3** details the final version of the ENTRUST Trusted Computing Base (TCB), providing in-depth summaries, technical interface descriptions, and benchmarking results for Configuration Integrity Verification (CIV), Conformity Certificates (CCs), and Direct Anonymous Attestation (DAA).
- **Chapter 4** provides a comprehensive security analysis of the core ENTRUST cryptographic protocols and algorithms, including Attribute-Based Signatures (ABS), Attribute-Based Signcryption (ABSC), domain enrolment procedures, and p-ABCs for CC management. This chapter includes formal proofs for key security properties such as unforgeability, IND-CPA, attribute privacy, and key binding.

- **Chapter 5** elaborates on the ENTRUST Agile Swarm Attestation mechanisms, including an overview of WOTS+ (WOTS Plus) one-time signatures and detailing the setup, attestation, report, and verification phases for low-end device swarms, including considerations for dynamic attributes.
- **Chapter 6** documents the research work performed towards the exploration of alternative Roots-of-Trust leveraging photonic technology (i.e. Speckle imaging-based optical PUFs)
- **Chapter 7** concludes the deliverable, summarizing the key achievements, the finalized state of the framework, and its contributions to the ENTRUST project's objectives.

Chapter 2

ENTRUST Trusted Execution Architecture for Secure CMD Lifecycle Management

2.1 High-level Summary of ENTRUST Zero-Touch Onboarding

This section acts as a reminder from D4.2 [20] and outlines the process that a CMD follows to become part of a domain's infrastructure. Initially, the device must authenticate itself with the Privacy Certification Authority (Privacy CA) to obtain verifiable information regarding its security features (e.g., secure boot, cryptographic capabilities, manufacturer identity etc). Upon successful authentication, based on the trust established between the Privacy CA and the device manufacturer, the Privacy CA issues a Verifiable Credential (VC) tied to the device. It also provides a set of attribute keys that allow proof of compliance with attribute-based policies. Device authentication is a prerequisite for receiving the VC and, if applicable, the attribute keys. This process relies on the pre-existing trust between the Privacy CA and the device's manufacturer.

During the enrollment of a CMD in the targeted healthcare domain, the Domain Manager (DM) evaluates the device's security posture by verifying the information provided in the VC against its domain-specific security and privacy policies. High-end CMDs can leverage their attribute keys to demonstrate policy compliance in a privacy-preserving manner. Here, ENTRUST supports two variants of privacy-preserving Zero-Touch Onboarding (ZTO) mechanisms for high-end devices:

- **Selective Disclosure Variant:** This variant leverages Verifiable Presentations (VPs), constructed from the VC acquired from the Privacy CA. In this scenario, the high-end device selectively discloses only those attributes required by the Domain Manager for onboarding. The VP includes a cryptographic proof generated using the device's attribute keys, ensuring minimal attribute exposure while still enabling strong authenticity verification.
- **Zero-Knowledge Proof Variant:** In the second variant, the device generates a zero-knowledge proof encompassing all the attributes included in its Verifiable Credential without employing selective disclosure. This zero-knowledge proof cryptographically demonstrates possession of the necessary attributes to the Domain Manager without explicitly revealing them, thereby maintaining core privacy guarantees.

Low-end CMDs, which lack advanced cryptographic capabilities, directly present their VC without modification. The DM verifies this VC with the assistance of the device's manufacturer. Upon successful validation and if the device meets the domain's requirements, the DM establishes shared cryptographic keys for secure communication.

Once authenticated by the DM, devices request a Conformity Certificate (CC) from the Trust Assessment Framework (TAF). Unlike the VC, which contains manufacturer-attested attributes, the CC includes security assessments made by the DM. For high-end CMDs, this incorporates both static and runtime assessments (e.g., configuration settings, control flow integrity). For low-end CMDs, the CC is restricted to static properties due to their lack of runtime monitoring capabilities.

Given that runtime trust conditions can vary, CMDs necessitate mechanisms for CC renewal. Renewal can occur either synchronously (via the DM issuing a one-time CC upon receiving a trust assessment request) or asynchronously, where the device proactively requests a CC periodically or upon detecting runtime changes. Asynchronous renewal necessitates certificate revocation mechanisms. ENTRUST will evaluate both approaches concerning security, performance, and scalability.

It is essential to differentiate between the two credential types a device maintains: the Verifiable Credential (VC) and the Conformity Certificate (CC). The VC includes manufacturer-certified static attributes and primarily supports domain enrollment, notably for low-end devices or external, highly privileged auditors. Conversely, the CC reflects the Domain Manager's trust assessments derived from static or, in high-end cases, dynamic runtime properties. CCs serve internal and cross-domain trust establishment purposes, incorporating privacy-preserving features like selective attribute disclosure and unlinkable presentations for cross-domain scenarios. These differences lead to distinct cryptographic implementations: standard digital signatures (e.g., edDSA) for VCs, and privacy-preserving attribute-based credentials (p-ABCs) enabling zero-knowledge proofs for CCs in high-end devices.

While the overall onboarding process remains consistent across device types, specific mechanisms are tailored based on cryptographic capabilities. Crucially, ENTRUST relies on essential trust relationships: the Privacy CA trusts the manufacturer, and the Domain Manager trusts the Privacy CA.

2.2 ENTRUST Trust Extensions - Summary of Updates

This section summarizes the final set of technical updates introduced in the ENTRUST framework. These updates enhance the flexibility, privacy, and evidence richness of the Trusted Computing Base (TCB), finalize cryptographic protocols, and complete the integration of attestation, certification, and onboarding mechanisms for both high- and low-end CMDs.

The runtime assurance framework introduced in Deliverable D4.1 [23] and extended in D4.2 [20] has been substantially finalized in the context of the current deliverable. In particular, Deliverable D4.3 consolidates the trust establishment mechanisms for CMDs across heterogeneous platforms, refining both the architectural integration and implementation of key components within the ENTRUST's TCB. Table 2.1 summarizes the specific updates and finalizations introduced in D4.3, with a focus on the trust anchors, credential types, and attestation capabilities tailored to each CMD class. These updates reflect the framework's ability to support secure runtime trust assessment under possible resource constraints, while maintaining interoperability and compliance with ENTRUST's overarching zero-trust principles.

Table 2.1: Technical Updates in the ENTRUST Trust Stack (Final D4.3 Release)

Component	Final Updates and Integrated State
Swarm Attestation	<p>The Swarm Attestation protocol has been significantly enhanced to support dynamic updates in the swarm’s topology, including the addition or revocation of devices and changes to the set of attributes used for trust assessment. This enhancement enables ENTRUST to perform swarm attestation based on different sets of device attributes and improves privacy through the use of non-linkable one-time signatures. The protocol is now fully integrated as a trusted subsystem of the TCB, allowing efficient, collective evidence collection from fleets of low-end CMDs. (The full protocol and security analysis are detailed in Chapter 5.)</p>
Conformity Certificate Signing	<p>The process for CC management—both for low-end and high-end CMDs—was finalized by integrating the TAF to work in tandem with the Certification Authority for issuing abstract trust properties to be included in the CC. This culminated in the finalization of the encoding schema used for the CCs, which was further secured using the signing mechanism introduced in D4.2, leveraging the AA bound to its current state. All of the aforementioned developments also contributed to the harmonization of the ENTRUST cryptography layer with the necessary primitives (p-ABCs) for managing CCs on high-end CMDs, as well as PUF-assisted authentication and CC management for low-end CMDs. The final design, along with a detailed evaluation for low-end CMDs, is provided in Chapter 3.2. This includes finalized integration for both high-end and low-end devices, enhanced support for revocation, and the incorporation of privacy-preserving attribute-based credentials (p-ABCs). (The final design is presented in Chapter 3, with security proofs in Chapter 4.)</p>

Continued on next page

Component	Final Updates and Integrated State
Expanded Evidence Types	<p>The set of trust sources has been expanded beyond static device properties to include runtime behavior. The framework now captures Control-Flow Integrity (CFI) violations by leveraging the standardized Integrity Measurement Architecture (IMA) of UNIX-based operating systems as an initial step, pending full integration of ENTRUST's eBPF-based tracer, which is capable of capturing system call execution as additional evidence. This functionality will be further extended to monitor access control violations, correct key usage, and rollback safety mechanisms for high-end devices. These features will be linked through system call trace analysis, providing a more robust and comprehensive measure of device trustworthiness. (This capability is part of the finalized TCB framework described in Chapter 3.)</p>
Enhanced TCB Interfaces	<p>New modular interfaces were developed for the Trusted Computing Base (TCB), reflecting the new federated modality of the Trust Assessment Framework (TAF) as described in D3.3. These interfaces enable the export of continuous polling or event-driven, property-specific evidence to the TAF, supporting more responsive and fine-grained runtime trust evaluations. This allows the TAF to actively poll the TCB, or for the TCB to proactively report changes in trust level. (These interfaces are detailed within the final TCB architecture in Chapter 3.)</p>
ABSC Finalisation	<p>The Attribute-Based Signcryption (ABSC) protocol has been fully implemented, integrated into the runtime framework, and comprehensively benchmarked. The final implementation provides core security guarantees, including sender anonymity, strong attribute binding, and IND-CPA security. ** (The complete protocol specification and formal security proofs are presented in Chapter 4.)**</p>
Finalization of ZTO with High Security and Privacy Guarantees	<p>To enhance device privacy—particularly within the heterogeneous CMD environment—the framework now supports two distinct, privacy-preserving onboarding flows for high-end devices: a full zero-knowledge proof or selective disclosure using Verifiable Presentations (VPs). (These architectural modes are introduced in Chapter 2, with their cryptographic mechanisms analyzed in Chapter 4.)</p>

For high-end CMDs, the Configuration Integrity Verification (CIV) component has been finalized, the Conformity Certificate (CC) now supports runtime re-issuance, and credential encoding has been enhanced with privacy-preserving and pseudonymization features. For low-end CMDs, the swarm attestation mechanism has been finalized, including both Merkle tree aggregation and one-time signature schemes. Fur-

thermore, the PUF-based key binding process has been completed. These updates reflect the consolidation of ENTRUST's runtime trust assessment framework across heterogeneous device profiles.

Chapter 3

Final Version of ENTRUST Trusted Computing Base

The **Trusted Computing Base (TCB)** in ENTRUST comprises a set of core components that enable runtime assurance, policy enforcement, and verifiable trust establishment across the lifecycle of CMDs. This chapter presents the final implementation, integration, and benchmarking of the key trust enablers of the ENTRUST TCB, specifically: **Configuration Integrity Verification (CIV)**, **Conformity Certificates (CCs)**, and **Direct Anonymous Attestation (DAA)**.

Each of these components plays a distinct role in supporting device onboarding, runtime trust maintenance, and evidence-based certification. Table 3.1 provides a concise summary of the purpose, operational context, and benchmarking rationale for each building block. The table is intended to contextualize the detailed analysis that follows in this chapter.

It is important to note that while Direct Anonymous Attestation (DAA) is not actively used in the ENTRUST operational workflows, it is introduced here for completeness. DAA offers strong privacy guarantees and is presented as a potential extension to the existing attestation mechanisms for scenarios where attribute anonymity is a critical requirement. This marks the first formal documentation of DAA within ENTRUST.

The following sections present each building block in greater detail, covering final implementation status, interfaces, and the results of targeted experimental evaluations that validate their readiness for real-world use.

3.1 Configuration Integrity Verification (CIV)

3.1.1 Summary of CIV Attestation

Configuration Integrity Verification (CIV) in the ENTRUST framework is specifically designed to ensure that CMDs consistently maintain their security configurations according to domain-defined secure baselines. CIV attestation involves verifying both static and dynamic device properties, thereby enabling the timely detection of any unauthorized modifications or misconfigurations during runtime. For a full definition and analysis of CIV, we refer the reader to D4.2 [20].

In particular, CIV attestation leverages device attributes representing hardware-based security features, firmware versions, and device-specific cryptographic identifiers. These attributes, initially certified by the Privacy Certification Authority (Privacy CA) during the onboarding phase, provide a foundational trust anchor for subsequent verification processes. By binding attribute keys to the device's hardware-based Root ID key, CIV ensures strong device identification and binding integrity.

Table 3.1: Summary of ENTRUST TCB Components and Benchmarking Motivation

Component	When Used in ENTRUST	Motivation for Benchmarking
Configuration Integrity Verification (CIV)	At runtime to monitor and validate a device’s configuration state against expected secure system properties.	To assess runtime performance overhead, detection latency, and scalability across CMD platforms, validating the feasibility of real-time deployment in operational environments.
Conformity Certificates (CCs)	Issued during onboarding and periodically at runtime to represent the verified trust status of the device. Includes both static and dynamic evidence for high-end devices, and static only for low-end devices.	To evaluate issuance and presentation cost, size of disclosed credentials (with p-ABCs), and responsiveness of the renewal process in dynamic scenarios. Critical for trust propagation across domains.
Direct Anonymous Attestation (DAA)	Not deployed in the current ENTRUST stack, but introduced as a privacy-preserving attestation mechanism enabling unlinkable device authentication.	To understand trade-offs in performance, scalability, and integration complexity if DAA were to be adopted in privacy-sensitive domains. Benchmarking supports potential future use cases.

During the runtime phase, devices actively use these attribute keys to demonstrate compliance with domain-specific security and privacy policies. CIV dynamically validates device states by comparing runtime-collected data (such as system call sequences and software configuration states) against predefined policy baselines. Deviations trigger alerts or corrective actions within the domain’s Trust Assessment Framework (TAF).

The final implementation of CIV in D4.3 extends the capability of the ENTRUST TCB by integrating a standardized and modular interface for exporting device configuration and runtime data to the TAF. This allows fine-grained monitoring and rapid verification cycles, essential for high-assurance CMD environments. The enhancements introduced ensure that CIV can provide robust, real-time configuration integrity assurances while maintaining compatibility across both CMD classes. Apart from the following section that presents the performance measurements of CIV on a low-end CMD, a full benchmark of the procedure can be found in D6.1 [24].

3.1.2 PUF-based Attestation on a Low-End CMD

In this phase of the project, we reached a significant milestone by successfully integrating a PUF module with a real-world, low-end wearable device. This represents **one of the first known cases**—if not the first—where **a PUF has been directly connected to such a constrained, commercially available wearable platform**. The interface between the two components was established through UART communication using dedicated GPIO pins, as illustrated in figure 3.1.

This work builds upon the initial benchmarking activities presented in D6.1 [24], where testing was conducted using a Nordic DK development board in a hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) configuration. In contrast, the current setup advances the evaluation framework by moving from a development board to an actual wearable device, thereby validating the ENTRUST solution in a realistic and resource-constrained

embedded environment.

Figure 3.1: PUF integrated with Wearable CMD. In the left side of the figure, the ENTRUST’s SRAM-based PUF instance, whereas in the right, the core of Sentio’s wearable device along with its interfacing components.

Beyond the hardware integration, we also introduced an important software-level enhancement. In earlier stages, artificial delays were inserted in the communication logic between the wearable and the PUF to avoid race conditions. While this approach ensured correctness, it also required the system to remain idle for unnecessarily long periods, extending the time required for each challenge-response cycle.

To address this, we refactored the communication stack by replacing the delay-based synchronization mechanism with an event-driven architecture based on callbacks. In the previous implementation, the wearable device would send a challenge to the PUF and then wait for a fixed amount of time before attempting to read the response, regardless of whether the PUF had completed its computation. In the updated design, a callback function is registered and automatically invoked as soon as the PUF indicates that the response is ready. This allows the system to proceed immediately—eliminating unnecessary waiting and significantly improving communication efficiency.

This enhancement not only improves responsiveness but also allowed us to completely remove the artificial delays described in D6.1 [24], thus reducing overhead and enabling tighter integration with real-time application constraints. The result is a more robust, efficient, and scalable implementation, bringing us one step closer to the practical deployment of PUF-based security mechanisms in commercially viable wearable platforms.

The diagram below visually illustrates the flow of these phases, highlighting key timestamps and metrics used to evaluate the time taken for critical steps such as locating the firmware image and calculating the hash. By examining the benchmarking data, we can assess the efficiency of the secure authentication process, ensuring that it meets performance requirements even in resource-constrained environments like low-end devices. This diagram serves as a comprehensive representation of how the high-level operational phases interact and are measured, offering a clear understanding of their respective performance metrics.

To evaluate the performance implications of these security mechanisms, we measured the time consumed by several key steps in the operational flow, including data retrieval from storage, computation, and preparation of the system for communication. This detailed breakdown allowed us to determine

Figure 3.2: Overview of the Low-End CMD's TCB evaluation process

whether low-end devices could execute these tasks efficiently, without incurring unacceptable delays or performance degradation.

In the following, we provide an analysis of each benchmark performed as part of the evaluation process.

Benchmark 1: Bluetooth handshake. The Bluetooth handshake process plays a pivotal role in establishing initial communication between devices. During this phase, the time required for pairing and the exchange of authentication information was found to vary significantly depending on factors such as signal strength and device proximity. A weaker signal or greater distance between devices resulted in increased latency, potentially delaying system readiness. Therefore, maintaining a robust connection is crucial for ensuring efficient communication within this benchmark. Here, the distance between the high-end and the low-end CMDs was kept at minimum, since both devices was placed side-by-side.

Benchmark 2: Calculate the Firmware Hash. The firmware hash calculation, performed by the Tracer, is essential for ensuring the integrity of the firmware by generating a secure hash. This operation is predominantly influenced by the computational power of the device and is less affected by latency. However, its efficiency is crucial to the overall system performance, particularly when verifying firmware integrity during the initial boot process or at runtime.

Benchmark 3: UART Communication - Sending Challenge and FW Hash to PUF. This benchmark evaluates the UART-based transmission of the challenge and firmware hash from the low-end wearable device to the Arduino, which forwards the data to the PUF module. Previously, this process relied on a fixed 3-second delay to avoid synchronization issues such as race conditions or data loss caused by the low-end wearable device sending data too quickly. In the updated implementation, this delay has been removed and replaced with callback-driven flow control. This event-driven approach allows the Arduino to process incoming data more efficiently, ensuring synchronization without arbitrary wait times. As a result, the system achieves more stable communication and improved performance.

Benchmark 4: PUF Challenge and Helper data retrieval. This benchmarking evaluates the latency-dependent operation of accessing data stored on an SD card in order to obtain the the critical for the PUF output reconstruction, generated during the manufacturing of the specific instance. The process involves multiple stages, including opening the file, reading the necessary data, and closing the file. These operations introduce cumulative delays that are influenced not only by the file size but also by the overhead associated with managing external storage access.

The analysis yielded the following findings:

- A 11.3kB challenge file required approximately 1597ms to open, read, and close.

- A smaller 1.2kB helper data file completed the same sequence in 513ms.

This substantial variation highlights the significant impact of file size on operation times. However, the observed delays also underscore the influence of non-size-related factors, such as the time required to open and close files. Frequent access to external SD cards further compounds these delays, emphasizing that external storage inherently introduces latency overhead.

The reliance on external SD cards for latency-sensitive operations necessitates careful consideration of their impact on overall system performance. In scenarios where these delays become unacceptable, transitioning to internal (e.g. flash memory) or more accessible storage options (e.g. NVMEs) is crucial for ensuring system efficiency.

Benchmark 5: PUF Key Derivation Function(KDF). The PUF KDF generates cryptographic keys based on unique device-specific characteristics. This process is computationally demanding and largely dependent on the device's processing capacity. Although it does not directly involve latency-related factors such as external communication or storage, its execution time must be carefully evaluated to ensure compatibility with low-end hardware. As mentioned previously, the final key generated through the KDF (attestation key) is a combination of the PUF output and the FW hash extracted from the Tracer.

Benchmark 6: UART Communication -Attestation Key Forwarding. Attestation key forwarding is a critical step in securely transmitting the derived key to its intended recipient. The system now uses callbacks to manage the key forwarding process, removing the need for the previous 3-second delay. This reduces the total processing time to approximately 0.890 seconds. By adopting an event-driven approach, the system ensures that key transmission occurs in a precise and orderly manner, resulting in a faster and more reliable key exchange.

Benchmark 7: Signing Nonce. Nonce signing is essential for preserving message integrity before transmitting data to a high-end device for verification. By utilizing an HMAC-SHA-256 cryptographic function, the system generates a cryptographic signature that authenticates the nonce while ensuring that secret keys remain protected. This method fortifies communication security, preventing unauthorized modifications and replay attacks. The signed nonce is then forwarded to the high-end device, where verification takes place, reinforcing trust and system reliability.

Benchmark 8: PUF related operations. The complete operation of the PUF encompasses the processes evaluated in Benchmark 4 and Benchmark 5, in addition to the UART communication required to transmit the derived key back to the low-end wearable device. This benchmark measures the cumulative performance of the PUF's secure functionality, which involves the following key steps:

- **Challenge and Helper Data retrieval:** As outlined in Benchmark 4, this step is highly latency-dependent due to its reliance on external SD card access.
- **Key Derivation Function (KDF):** As evaluated in Benchmark 5, this step ensures the secure generation of cryptographic keys based on unique PUF characteristics.
- **UART Communication of Derived Key:** The derived key is transmitted back to the wearable device UART communication.

This benchmark highlights the interconnected nature of the PUF operations, which combine data extraction, cryptographic processing, and communication. While both SD card access and UART communication introduce latency, the overall performance of these steps is critical for ensuring the efficiency and reliability of the PUF's secure functionality in resource-constrained environments.

Benchmark 9: Harmonic interaction of the PUF with low-end wearable device. The evaluation focused on the comprehensive implementation of the PUF operation within the wearable device, encompassing all stages starting after the FW hash and UID acquisition to the secure transmission of the attestation key, considering also the measures to mitigate racing conditions due to UART interface.

This evaluation underscores the intricate interplay necessary for achieving seamless PUF integration. Despite its complexity, the synchronization delay proved essential for ensuring stable communication and preventing functional errors, thus safeguarding the integrity of the entire process.

By integrating these elements within the wearable device, the evaluation demonstrated the feasibility of secure PUF-based operations in resource-constrained environments. It highlighted the critical importance of addressing latency, computational demands, and synchronization protocols to facilitate a reliable and efficient implementation.

Benchmark 10: End-to-end trustworthiness evidence extraction. This benchmark encompassed the entire process of extracting trustworthiness evidence, incorporating operations such as Bluetooth communication, UART communication, and data extraction from the SD card. As a comprehensive evaluation, it combined several latency-dependent factors, including:

- **Bluetooth Latency:** Influenced by signal strength and distance.
- **Data Extraction from SD Card:** Dependent on file size and storage efficiency.

This end-to-end evaluation underscored the interdependency of the various subsystems and their collective impact on overall performance. Optimizing these elements is essential for achieving both efficient and reliable operation.

The results of this updated benchmarking are summarized in the following table.

Operation	Min(s)	Max(s)	Mean(s)	Mean(s)
Benchmark 1	1.081	1.872	1.278	1.374
Benchmark 2	0.489	0.504	0.502	0.471
Benchmark 3	0.012	0.012	0.012	3.112
Benchmark 4	2.101	2.119	2.110	2.110
Benchmark 5	0.033	0.055	0.035	0.035
Benchmark 6	0.890	0.898	1	3.001
Benchmark 7	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
Benchmark 8	3.024	3.072	3.145	5.145
Benchmark 9	3.046	3.094	3.158	8.258
Benchmark 10	7.562	8.844	7.954	11.539

Table 3.2: Extended benchmarking results of the Wearable CMD's TCB. The column in red indicates the previous benchmarking results presented in [24].

The updated measurements reflect a notable improvement due to software optimizations. As seen, by utilizing the event-driven architecture based on callbacks, the complete trustworthiness evidence extraction process lasts less than 8 seconds, whereas more than eleven seconds were needed when the delay-based synchronization mechanism was employed. Such results indicate that an approximate 30% reduction in total execution time was achieved.

The major contribution to this performance is the adoption of callbacks mechanisms, which allow immediate execution of logic upon event completion, as opposed to relying on previous delays. This modification

led to a measurable improvement in communications operations. This updated benchmark validates the successful integration and execution of the complete ENTRUST attestation workflow, including an SRAM-based PUF instance, on the wearable CMD. This marks a significant milestone, demonstrating that even in the constrained context of a commercial wearable, it is feasible to incorporate hardware-rooted trust anchors without incurring prohibitive overhead.

Beyond the successful implementation, one of the most notable insights emerging from our comprehensive experimentation is the pronounced influence of the software stack over the underlying hardware architecture in the performance of trust-related operations. Across a diverse set of deployment scenarios, we observed that the bulk of the processing overhead—particularly during trust assessment and CC management—is introduced at the software level.

Crucially, this overhead is not only measurable but also largely reducible through careful software optimization, underscoring the critical importance of efficient code design and system-level integration. Furthermore, transitioning the same software stack across diverse hardware platforms, including real-world heterogeneous edge devices, produced minimal variation in performance outcomes. This observation strongly affirms that hardware architecture plays a secondary role compared to software efficiency in determining overall system behavior.

In conclusion, these findings reinforce the value and resilience of the ENTRUST solution, which remains robust in the face of hardware heterogeneity and demonstrates consistent performance across fragmented device ecosystems.

3.2 Conformity Certificates (CCs)

Conformity Certificates (CC) were fully described in detail in Deliverable D4.2 [20]. In this section, we provide an overview of their functionality and interfaces, remarking the changes incurred.

3.2.1 Summary of CCs Functionality

Conformity Certificates provide functionality for certifying high-level *trust appraisals* resulting from the attestation process, such as integrity or resilience. As detailed in Figure 3.3, the creation of the CC will be carried out by the TAF when an attestation process leads to a change in the trust level of a CMD or medical domain. CCs will be held by the device, and later presented to any third party acting as a verifier or auditor.

Figure 3.3: High-level overview of Conformity Certificates functionality

Conformity Certificates will be represented as Verifiable Credentials (VC). This format enables interoperability, flexible application of different cryptographic mechanisms for protection of the CC, and is in line with current trends in self-sovereign communities. Figure 3.4 shows an example of a CC for a high-end device formatted as a VC. This CC was issued for a device that proved fulfilment of the integrity, resilience, robustness and safety trust appraisals, while it failed to prove availability. Additionally, the CC is linked to the public key (i.e., the public part of the attestation key) of the device, and a revocation handle, that can be used for fine-grained revocation of CCs using a deny-list approach backed by the trustworthy data sharing mechanisms provided by the ENTRUST blockchain.

```

{
  "credential": {
    "@context": [
      "https://www.w3.org/2018/credentials/v1",
      "https://www.w3.org/2018/credentials/examples/v1",
      "https://ssiproject.inf.um.es/security/psms/v1",
      "https://ssiproject.inf.um.es/poc/context/v1"
    ],
    "credentialSubject": {
      "availability": "no",
      "integrity": "yes",
      "publickey": "z2e1jasudaiwlshpaidwnapsh2182ja18ajdap101ja",
      "resilience": "yes",
      "rh": "907b3587-b2b7-4a4f-a0e8-61f90d6ea866",
      "robustness": "yes",
      "safety": "yes"
    },
    "expirationDate": "2025-05-23T10:30:37.111386683Z",
    "id": "did:fabric:g2up9qvrVe7QNl6oNl25-o-fnLTDmu3eNWu8NdJGKdU6052080",
    "issuanceDate": "2025-05-22T06:43:57.111386683Z",
    "issuer": "did:fabric:g2up9qvrVe7QNl6oNl25-o-fnLTDmu3eNWu8NdJGKdU",
    "proof": {
      "created": "2025-05-22T06:43:57.136201658Z",
      "proofPurpose": "assertionMethod",
      "proofValue": "BBFkPZfLUffvtcpWDT0jxpEN0T5szdM6u5q6wQ1s5Y4qRf_TCUWDAoZdYTH-
UQOVVRNRr0j1EtPb77R8IG7q8UbAAkhuWsgBJer_nkX3LwVgd4da9xHAsHUIWso6GBeYk3Q8gUzva9p7NByng63jHH3bl3re29ta5FF0ePJetLbXT5N
soUfubSXc7sLp9XQwDROAWSYeiXhupkQLQ8_070GsVyxwQzJeb01WweYoTT2s2I8YtwnE2u4Z4ViCwZkb3wQY900u2ifrf03wxP7sGeK5iEWL-
Pccxz5ckQTFfFHTbnEoV5tx5qigk0qcFpciEURyutmvElbe8WPWnK-
bApP3ErISD78zzZA753lbyG_NvIUZBBLnwIJHgs0ZSczJzwPzmhj6xXFSzWYJ09DAzsi2QV50x218fL8V8cAgSp2m4n9KXsVp8SsqoPgDzhb0-
wVqmARpVP8uTyYiqAg_1_B-Fb-
gnjvmM_yj6zq68w6F5J8p9RQwgJotZEKtYltHAYP2QxALQF4F9IxCyZUCdzEhJkMLgYxM9NdZ0qe1GsoL9cFLTLII2BH0K7gmxFMrB4",
      "type": "PsmsBlsSignature2022",
      "verificationMethod": "did:fabric:g2up9qvrVe7QNl6oNl25-o-fnLTDmu3eNWu8NdJGKdU#xc-
nTsNiCziw_uzITeA9L0Tu0xmTXg0FaFzAmFhdB4"
    },
    "type": [
      "VerifiableCredential",
      "ConformityCertificate"
    ]
  }
}

```

Figure 3.4: Example of Conformity Certificate formatted as a Verifiable Credential

This example showcases one of the possible scenarios for CCs, where the CC is issued to a high-end device using the "PsmsBls" scheme, so that the device can later generate zero-knowledge proofs to present only a subset of the attributes contained in the CC. For low-end devices, they will not be capable of selectively disclosing information about their attributes. Instead, they will present the original VC without further attribute privacy, which is bound to the outcomes of the device's PUF-based TCB to prove their ownership.

3.2.2 Technical Interfaces of CCs and connection with attestation and trust assessment

Figure 3.5 shows the overall cryptographic protocol for CCs in high-end devices. This has been updated from D4.2 [20] to bind the CC to the device's Attestation Key.

From a technical point of view, the implementation of these flows is carried out by components on the

Figure 3.5: High-end device: Creation of Conformity Certificate as VC, and usage of Conformity Certificate during interaction with third party.

server side, integrated with the trust assessment framework, and in the device side as part of the high-end TCB. Figure 3.6 showcases a schematic view of how these components were implemented and interact. The development of the infrastructure side consists on a full-fledged wallet that can manage DIDs and Verifiable Credentials, displaying the integration and interoperability with such technologies. This functionality will be used by the TAF for providing the CCs to devices after a change in the trust appraisals. The DLT infrastructure will be used to publish events and manage the revocation of specific CCs through their revocation handle.

On the device side, the key component is a Trusted Application that will be included in the TCB and executed within the TEE to manage the CCs. This application will interface with the normal world through a Client Application following the Global Platform APIs. These capabilities will be orchestrated through the Orchestration component developed in ENTRUST, currently based on a Python REST server. Some more technical details on the implementation level are provided in D6.1 [24].

Figure 3.6: Component interactions for Conformity Certificate issuance and usage

3.2.3 Conformity Certificates for Low-End Devices

As described in D4.2 [20], the low-end device lacks the computational resources required to support advanced cryptographic protocols allowing selective disclosure. As a result, it presents the entire Verifiable Credential (VC), without the capability to selectively reveal individual attributes. Although the system still maintains a degree of trust properties by design, this is different from true selective disclosure and should be clearly differentiated. The VC is safeguarded using One-Time Signatures (OTS), created under unique keys bound to the output of the PUF-based identity composition engine. This mechanism ensures both proof of ownership, since generating the correct keys requires access to the corresponding PUF, and assurance of integrity, as the device must accurately reflect its intended and trusted operational state in order to produce a valid, verifiable signature.

During the enrollment phase, the low-end device is issued a CC by the TAF, which attests to the device’s compliance with the trust requirements of the target domain. The CC includes a set of trust properties, such as availability, integrity, resilience, robustness, safety, and the DID. Along with these trustworthiness claims, the CC structure includes metadata fields such as the issuance timestamp and expiration date. These elements collectively establish the identity of the device and provide a temporal context for validation. Some fields within the CC—specifically proofValue, type, and proofPurpose—are intentionally left empty at issuance. These are populated dynamically at runtime, upon request from an external

verifier, typically via a high-end parent device. The type field identifies the cryptographic algorithm used (e.g., ECDSA), and proofPurpose denotes the function of the proof—primarily to assert the freshness and current validity of the certificate.

Once the device constructs and signs the CC, the TAF performs a verification step. The proofValue signature is derived from a cryptographic key that is bound to the device’s PUF output. Successful verification of the signature by the TAF confirms the integrity of the signature and ensures that the PUF-derived key material has not been leaked, cloned, or externally reconstructed.

Upon successful verification, the TAF sends an acknowledgment (ACK) message to the device. This ACK serves as an official confirmation that the certificate is valid, the low-end device is uncompromised, and the CC can be securely stored and reused during runtime to assert the device’s trustworthiness to external parties.

Upon receiving such a request, the low-end device generates a new one-time signature over the existing Conformity Certificate. This process does not involve updating the trust properties of the CC, but instead binds the existing claims to the current state of the device, allowing the verifier to detect inconsistencies through signature validation. The cryptographic signature is generated using a key derived through a Key Derivation Function (KDF). This KDF takes as input the output of the device’s PUF—evaluated on the received challenge—along with the output of a tracer that reflects the current state of the device. As a result, both the hardware identity and software state are cryptographically bound to the derived key, which is then used to sign the stored credential structure, producing a fresh proofValue.

As shown in the corresponding figure 3.7, this updated Conformity Certificate now includes all fields, trust properties, metadata, and the populated proof section.

```

{
  "credential": {
    "credentialSubject": {
      "availability": "no",
      "integrity": "yes",
      "resilience": "yes",
      "robustness": "yes",
      "safety": "yes",
      "DID": "A61E65991DBD2DCD"
    },
    "expirationDate": "2025-05-23T10:30:37",
    "issuanceDate": "2025-05-22T06:43:57",
    "proof": {
      "proofPurpose": "assertionMethod",
      "type": "ECDSA",
      "proofValue": "a62ab78727db5c4bc5d41b3bf1c5dc343d78201ee63d914dc25ac57e3deb199b",
      "challengePUF": "73fc714c4727ee9395f324cd2e7f331f121f17432e0250c32c3e31e208ac66a8"
    },
    "type": {
      "ConformityCertificate"
    }
  }
}

```

Figure 3.7: Example of Conformity Certificate in Low-End Device

This mechanism enables lightweight, runtime validation of trust without requiring frequent reassessment. The freshly generated proofValue acts as a dynamic assertion of integrity: even if all the trust properties listed in the CC remain unchanged, a mismatch in the signature reveals that the device’s state has drifted from what was initially certified. In such cases, the verifier can flag the inconsistency and trigger appropriate auditing or revocation procedures via the TAF. This approach is especially valuable in low-resource environments, where continuous trust assessment is impractical, yet runtime consistency must still be assured.

3.2.4 Benchmarking

3.2.4.1 Benchmarking of CC Operations on Low-End Devices

To evaluate the performance of CC operations on constrained devices, we performed a benchmarking based on the setup defined in D6.1 [24]. The experiments were executed on a Nordic nRF52840 development kit, a representative low-end IoT platform with limited computational and memory capabilities, configured to work with a PUF-based.

During the enrolment phase, the low-end device receives a complete JSON credential structure, derives a signing key using a PUF response and the current state of the device, signs the credential, and sends it back for verification. After receiving an acknowledgment, the device stores the signed credential locally. This process includes parsing the credential, executing the Key Derivation Function, performing the signature operation, and saving the result. The total execution time for this phase was measured at **3.716 seconds**.

As explained previously as well as in D4.2 [20], the creation of the signature is based on a challenge, which is why we include the *"ChallengePUF"* in the CC. During the runtime phase, we consider two models: static and dynamic challenges. In the static model, a single challenge is generated during enrollment and reused in all future runtime operations. To ensure freshness, a nonce is added to each request. However, this approach requires the device to produce two signatures, one over the cc and another over the nonce. It also assumes that no external verifier is involved in the runtime process.

In contrast, the dynamic model involves an external verifier, typically acting as a verification authority, requesting a fresh cc through the high-end device. The verifier obtains a new challenge, via the manufacturer, and forwards it to the low-end device. The device then uses this challenge to re-derive the signing key and produce a fresh signature over the stored credential.

We implemented the dynamic challenge model because it reflects a more realistic and secure deployment scenario, where credentials are verified by an external authority on demand. This model supports verifier-driven attestation in line with standard certification workflows. Under this setup, the runtime operation, where the device re-derives the key using the fresh challenge and signs the stored cc, was slightly faster than enrolment, with a total execution time of **3.695 seconds**, due to the absence of full JSON parsing.

This specific benchmarking, as also indicated by the selected proof type, currently relies on a traditional ECDSA scheme for one-time signatures. In the next version, we plan to adopt a dedicated one-time signature scheme, specifically using WOTS (Winternitz One-Time Signature). A detailed description of this implementation can be found in chapter 5, and a performance comparison between ECDSA and WOTS will be presented in D6.2.

3.3 Direct Anonymous Attestation (DAA)

In medical environments, particularly those structured around dynamic and regulated service graph chains, there is a growing need for authentication mechanisms that preserve privacy. Traditional platform attestation schemes rely on signing mechanisms that inevitably bind trust-related data to a persistent device identity. While such signatures enable verifiability, they also compromise unlinkability, making it possible to associate various pieces of trust evidence (and, by extension, application-level activity) to a specific device. This can be problematic in privacy-sensitive medical settings, where the identity of the device must remain abstracted, yet its trustworthiness must still be demonstrable.

Direct Anonymous Attestation (DAA) addresses this challenge by enabling a device to produce signatures that are verifiable but unlinkable. Under DAA, a CMD can authenticate itself as a legitimate group member and sign trust-related evidence using a group public key. The resulting signature ensures verifiers of its validity, without revealing which specific device produced it. Only authorized openers (if required

under regulatory or emergency access policies) may de-anonymize the signer, and only under specific controlled conditions.

This privacy-preserving property makes DAA an attractive extension for ENTRUST, particularly in cases where trustworthiness must be conveyed to external domains or auditors without exposing sensitive hardware or software characteristics. By decoupling trust assertions from persistent identifiers, DAA supports the construction of abstract, yet verifiable, attestation reports, thus enabling secure cross-domain trust without compromising patient or infrastructure privacy.

In this deliverable, DAA is introduced for completeness. It is not currently deployed in ENTRUST's operational workflows, but we evaluate it as a potential privacy-enhancing building block for future system extensions. Its relevance is increasing as regulatory and ethical demands on medical data confidentiality grow, and as trust requirements extend to decentralized, multi-tenant CMD infrastructures.

DAA is a standardized attestation mechanism, grounded in anonymous signature schemes, where only authorized entities can link a signature to its origin. In our analysis, we consider state-of-the-art DAA protocols, including revocation-enabled and threshold-issuance variants. These schemes aim to remove single points of trust and are particularly relevant to future deployments involving distributed or multi-stakeholder trust governance.

In the sections that follow, we investigate the feasibility of running DAA schemes on high-end CMD platforms. We evaluated both performance characteristics and integration requirements to determine whether DAA can be realistically adopted in ENTRUST-style environments. This assessment is guided by existing literature [17, 11, 31, 6] and our own proof-of-concept implementations.

3.3.1 Summary of DAA

In general, a DAA scheme consists of an issuer (Privacy CA), a set of signers, and a set of Verifiers. The issuer creates a DAA membership credential for each signer. A DAA credential corresponds to a signature of the signer's identity produced by the DAA issuer. A DAA signer consists of the (Host, TC) pair (TC stands for Trusted Component, in our implementation a TMP was used, but DAA can be agnostic to the underlying TC). Their membership in the DAA community and trustworthy state is proved by providing the Verifier with a DAA signature of the TC representation of the Host state. The DAA signature includes a zero-knowledge proof-of-knowledge, which is a cryptographic construct used to convince the Verifier that the signer possesses a valid membership credential, but without the Verifier learning anything else about the identity of the signer. The DAA is a protocol that enables a TC and a Host device not only to authenticate themselves to a verifying edge device and to prove that the Host is in a trustworthy state, but also to do so in a privacy-preserving manner. More concretely, the DAA provides the TC with the ability to sign its register values anonymously, while still convincing the Verifier that it possesses valid DAA credentials.

DAA supports user-controlled linkability: from a Verifier's point of view, two DAA signatures created by the same signer may or may not be linked. The linkability of DAA signatures is controlled by an input parameter called the *basename*. If a signer uses the same *basename* in two signatures, they are linked; otherwise, they are not.

3.3.2 Experimental Approach

To evaluate the feasibility of Direct Anonymous Attestation (DAA) in medical service-graph-chains, we conducted a series of experiments using a Trusted Platform Module (TPM) as the Root of Trust (RoT). This setup reflects the current state of DAA implementations, which are optimized for TPM-based execution [51]. Our objective was to assess DAA's performance under realistic constraints and to provide a

Figure 3.8: Overview of the DAA Signature

comparative point of reference against other trust establishment mechanisms, particularly those developed within ENTRUST.

Although DAA is not adopted in the ENTRUST architecture, it represents a well-established privacy-preserving attestation model that enables unlinkable trust evidence. Evaluating it under typical hardware conditions helps clarify its potential applicability — and limitations — in environments like those targeted by ENTRUST, where responsiveness and resource efficiency are critical.

The TPM was selected as the RoT due to its widespread standardization and native support for DAA operations. However, it is also known to impose constraints in terms of cryptographic throughput and I/O performance. This provides a conservative benchmark environment, particularly when compared to Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs) such as OP-TEE, which are used in ENTRUST’s trust extensions and offer significantly lower-latency cryptographic operations.

Importantly, ENTRUST’s attestation architecture is RoT-agnostic — protocols are designed to work independently of the underlying hardware trust anchor. However, the choice of RoT has a direct impact on operational performance. As part of this evaluation, we compare the performance of DAA signature generation on TPM hardware with the expected signing times achieved using OP-TEE in our extensions. This comparison is relevant not only for assessing the raw performance of DAA but also for understanding the broader trade-offs between privacy features and runtime efficiency.

The following section presents benchmark results from our TPM-based experiments, covering signature generation latency and credential handling. These results help contextualize the role of DAA within a spectrum of attestation technologies and provide insights into its performance envelope when compared to other trust mechanisms explored in ENTRUST.

Table 3.3: DAA SIGN Operation Timing (HW-TPM)

Activity	Mean (ms)	± (95% CI)
Total Application Stack	609.05	0.57/0.55
TPM2_StartAuthSession	23.93	2.67
TPM2_PolicyCommandCode	14.99	0.03
TPM2_PolicyOR	21.64	0.09
TPM2_LoadExternal	71.34	0.24/0.44
TPM2_VerifySignature	55.97	2.64
TPM2_PolicyAuthorize	34.36	7.74
TPM2_Commit	95.11	0.03/0.05
TPM2_Hash	34.04	0.04/0.009
TPM2_StartAuthSession	23.19	2.67
TPM2_PolicyNV	20.99	0.03
TPM2_PolicyOR	40.62	0.09
TPM2_VerifySignature	53.92	2.64
TPM2_PolicyAuthorize	34.36	7.41
TPM2_Sign	39.77	0.04/0.01
TPM2_FlushContext	13.27	0.02/0.01

3.3.3 Benchmarking

In the table below, we present the DAA SIGN Operation Timing in a TPM.

The DAA SIGN operation performed by edge devices (Table 3.3) takes ≈ 700 ms. Observe that the actual signing operation (performed with the TPM2_Sign command) is quite fast, lasting 84.03ms. However, recall that the DAA key is protected by key usage policies, so it can only be used if the device is in a correct state. This is instantiated by the TPM2_NV_Read and TPM2_PolicyNV commands, which verify that a pseudonym has both been correctly activated and has not been revoked before being used for signing, consuming approximately 120ms. Also, note that the duration of 97.69ms for the TPM_Commit command refers to the case where linkability is not needed. Therefore, a basename is not used. In case linkability capabilities are needed, a basename needs to be used, which increases the execution time of this command to 224.0ms, thus introducing a trade-off in terms of efficiency versus linkability. The DAA VERIFY is split into two operations: the verification of the (randomised) DAA credential takes up ≈ 155 ms (irrespective of whether the bsn changes for every signature or not), and the verification of the ECDSA signature takes up ≈ 20 ms. In case a basename bsn is used (columns bsn $\neq \perp$), the signature verification time is slightly increased by 5ms compared to the case where a basename is not used (columns bsn $= \perp$). In any case, this is quite an efficient operation, and since it takes place on the host device, the use of more powerful processors can also reduce the execution time.

Chapter 4

Security Analysis of ENTRUST Crypto Protocols and Algorithms

This chapter provides a comprehensive security analysis of the core cryptographic protocols and algorithms that constitute the foundation of the ENTRUST framework. The purpose of this analysis is to formally validate the robustness, integrity, and privacy-preserving nature of the mechanisms designed to enable secure runtime assurance and certification. Building upon the protocol descriptions presented in Deliverable D4.2, this chapter furnishes the rigorous mathematical arguments and game-based proofs that substantiate their security guarantees.

Specifically, the analysis covers the core cryptographic schemes, including Attribute-Based Signatures (ABS) and Attribute-Based Signcryption (ABSC), alongside the procedures for domain enrolment and Conformity Certificate (CC) management. Formal proofs are detailed for critical security properties such as unforgeability, indistinguishability against chosen plaintext attacks (IND-CPA), attribute privacy, and key binding. Ultimately, this chapter serves to solidify the cryptographic foundation of the ENTRUST architecture, providing the necessary assurance that its components are secure, privacy-preserving, and fit for purpose in high-stakes medical service-graph-chains.

4.1 A brief description of the ABS/ ABSC protocols presented in ENTRUST D4.2 [20]

To enable the creation and sharing of trustworthiness evidence in a verifiable manner, ENTRUST has developed a set of secure and efficient cryptographic protocols that support the generation of Verifiable Credentials (VCs), where a set of certified attributes is issued by an authority. Based on the issued (VCs), a device can then create Verifiable Presentations (VPs) to demonstrate that a certain security policy, denoted as P , is satisfied. These presentations take the form of Attribute-Based Signatures (ABS) if the verifier and the prover device belong to the same domain, or Attribute-based SignCryption (ABSC) if they belong to different domains. To prove enrollment in a specific ENTRUST domain, each domain is treated as a standalone attribute, where each high-end device receives its corresponding key, called the Domain Key and denoted by DK_E . In case high-end CMD possesses such a key, ABS is utilized to satisfy the security policy P , while ABSC is employed otherwise. When facilitating CMD communication within the same medical domain, where the anonymity of attributes is not a requirement, the ABS without anonymity is used. On the other hand, in cases where different medical domains (e.g., different hospitals) require a CMD or the entire domain to prove its trust level without disclosing its specific trust properties (which may potentially lead to implementation disclosure attacks), the ABSC with anonymity needs to be employed. Every time a VP is created by the device, ENTRUST's Trust Assessment Framework (TAF)

[22] generates a temporal Conformity Certificate, denoting a successful VP for a specific set of attributes. Table 4.1 presents the main security and privacy requirements of our ABSC scheme.

ABS/ABSC Security Requirement	Description
ABSC.SC.1 - Unforgeability	It is computationally infeasible to produce an ABSC on a message M that is accepted by the verification algorithm without knowledge of the attribute keys and the root identity key needed to create the ABS signature.
ABSC.SC.2 - Anonymity	Our ABSC with anonymity protocol supports complete privacy against external Verifiers that might be honest but curious to de-anonymise all devices' identities even if they are in a correct state.
ABSC.SC.3 - User Revocation	Our ABSC protocol supports revocation of the Devices relying on the trustworthiness of the Devices and the accuracy of the updated Key Revocation List KRL .
ABSC.SC.4 - Attribute Disclosure	A verifier that verifies an ABSC doesn't learn anything regarding the device's attributes other than that the device adheres to a certain predefined policy.
ABSC.SC.5 Correctness	It ensures that honestly generated ABSCs are always valid and the decryption extracts the exact message that was encrypted.
ABSC.SC.6 - Indistinguishability against Chosen Plaintext Attack	TA A property that a ciphertext does not reveal any information about the encrypted message, which we call "Indistinguishability against Chosen Plaintext Attack (IND-CPA)" security.
ABSC.SC.7 - Key Binding	An ABSC protocol holds the key binding property if every valid ABSC is generated using a set of attribute keys that are bound to the device's secret identity root key; this property prevents attacks on the sharing of attribute keys.

Table 4.1: High-level Security Analysis of the ABSC Scheme

In the following sections, we recall the protocols presented in [20] to provide the full security proofs.

4.1.1 ABS with Attribute Anonymity and Root Key Binding for the Run-Time Phase

The ABS Setup algorithm takes a security parameter λ and, as input, then generates the CA public key $mpk := X = e(g_1, g_2)^\alpha$ and the corresponding secret key $msk := \alpha$. The Privacy CA publishes the system's public parameters G along with its public key mpk . The Key Generation algorithm $KeyGen(msk, (\mathbf{M}, \pi))$ takes as inputs the CA secret key, the access matrix \mathbf{M} and a function π that maps each row in \mathbf{M} to its corresponding attribute, this algorithm returns the user attribute keys sk_1 and $sk_{2,i}$ bounded to the user's root key ($SK = x, PK = g^x$). This is done by letting the user creates $\sigma_i = H_1(i || h_m || \pi(i))^x$, where $h_m = H_0(\mathbf{M})$, for each row $i \in I$, where I represents the indices of the rows in \mathbf{M} that corresponds to the user attribute set S . The details of these algorithms are presented in Algorithm 1. The Privacy CA runs this algorithm.

Algorithm 1 ABS Setup and KeyGen

- 1: Take the security parameter λ as input
- 2: Pick $\alpha \leftarrow_{\$} \mathbb{Z}_p$, $H_0 : \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_p$ and $H_1 : \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow G_1$
- 3: Define $G := (p, G_1, G_2, G_T, e, g_1, g_2)$
- 4: $\text{mpk} := (G, H_0, H_1, X = e(g_1, g_2)^\alpha)$
- 5: $\text{msk} := \alpha$
- 6: $\text{KeyGen}(\text{msk}, (\mathbf{M}, \pi), I) \rightarrow \text{sk}$
- 7: Selects the attributes assigned to the user and sends every attribute $\pi(i) \in S$
- 8: $\sigma_i = H_1(i || h_m || \pi(i))^x$, where $h_m = H_0(\mathbf{M})$
- 9: The CA verifies each σ_i under PK
- 10: Pick $r \leftarrow_{\$} \mathbb{Z}_p$, $V^r \leftarrow_{\$} \mathbb{Z}_p^{n_2-1}$
- 11: $\text{sk}_1 := g_2^r$
- 12: $\text{sk}_{2,i} := g_1^{\mathbf{M}_{i,1}(\alpha || V^r)^T} \cdot \sigma_i^r$ for each row $i \in I$
- 13: Output $\text{sk}_{\text{PK}} := (\text{sk}_1, (\text{sk}_{2,i})_{i \in I})$
- 14: Keep $(\text{sk}_{\text{PK}} : (\text{sk}_1, k_2), h_m, \text{PK})$ in its records

The algorithm $\text{Sign}(\text{sk}, S \subseteq U, (\mathbf{M}, \pi), \text{msg})$ takes an attribute set S with the corresponding attribute keys, a message msg to be signed, and a policy matrix \mathbf{M} , then generates an ABS signature σ . The ABS signature includes proof of knowledge of the corresponding attribute keys without revealing which attributes are used. This proof is achieved by Schnorr's signature of knowledge as described in Algorithm 2. This algorithm is run by the signer.

Algorithm 2 ABS Sign: $\text{Sign}(\text{sk}, S \subseteq U, (\mathbf{M}, \pi), \text{msg}) \rightarrow \sigma$

- 1: Pick $s, t, r_\alpha, (r_i)_{i \in [n_1]} \leftarrow_{\$} \mathbb{Z}_p$
- 2: $h_m = H_0(\mathbf{M})$
- 3: $\sigma_1 := \text{sk}_1^{s \cdot t}$, Q_1
- 4: $\sigma_2 := \prod_{i \in I} (\text{sk}_{2,i})^{y_i^s}$, Q_2
- 5: $\sigma_3 := \prod_{i \in I} H_1(i || h_m || \pi(i))^{y_i^s} = \prod_{i \in [n_1]} H_1(i || h_m || \pi(i))^{y_i^s}$, and Q_3
- 6: $\sigma_4 := g_2^t$
- 7: $Y = X^{s \cdot t}$
- 8: $Z = X^{r_\alpha}$
- 9: $W = \prod_{i \in [n_1]} H_1(i || h_m || \pi(i))^{r_i}$
- 10: $c = H_0(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3, \sigma_4, Y, Z, W, \text{msg})$
- 11: $s_\alpha = r_\alpha - s \cdot t \cdot c$, and
- 12: $\forall i \in [n_1] s_i = r_i - \gamma_i \cdot s \cdot c$.
- 13: Output $\sigma := (\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3, \sigma_4, c, s_\alpha, (s_i)_{i \in [n_1]})$

To verify an ABS signature, the algorithm $\text{Verify}(\text{mpk}, (\mathbf{M}, \pi), \sigma, \text{msg})$ takes an ABS signature, the general access policy \mathbf{M} and a message msg and outputs 0 or 1. It verifies the the pairing to prove that the attribute keys are issued by the Privacy CA under mpk , it also verifies Schnorr signatures as described in Algorithm 3. This algorithm is run by the Verifier.

Algorithm 3 ABS Verify: Verify(mpk, (\mathbf{M}, π) , σ , msg) \rightarrow 0/1

- 1: $h_m = H_0(\mathbf{M})$
- 2: $Y = e(\sigma_2, \sigma_4) / e(\sigma_3, \sigma_1)$
- 3: $Z' = X^{s\alpha} \cdot Y^c$ and $W' = \prod_{i \in [n_1]} H(i || h_m || \pi(i))^{s_i} \cdot \sigma_3^c$
- 4: $c' = H_0(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3, \sigma_4, Y', Z', W', \text{msg})$
- 5: If $c' \neq c$, output 0; otherwise, output 1

Signer	Verifier
$(rsk, rp_k), (sk_1, sk_{2,i})$ Pick $s, t, r_\alpha, (r_i)_{i \in [n_1]} \leftarrow_{\$} Z_p$ Compute $h_m = H_0(\mathbf{M})$ $\sigma_1 := \prod_{i \in I} sk_{1,i}^{r_i}$ $\sigma_2 := \prod_{i \in I} (sk_{2,i})^{r_i^s}$, $\sigma_3 := \prod_{i \in I} H_1(i h_m \pi(i))^{r_i^s}$ $\sigma_4 := g_2^t$. Compute $Y = X^{s \cdot t}$ $Z = X^{r_\alpha}$ $W = \prod_{i \in [n_1]} H_1(i h_m \pi(i))^{r_i}$, $c = H_0(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3, \sigma_4, Y, Z, W, \text{msg})$ $s_\alpha = r_\alpha - s \cdot t \cdot c$ $\forall i \in [n_1] s_i = r_i - \gamma_i \cdot s \cdot c$. $\sigma := (\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3, \sigma_4, c, s_\alpha, (s_i)_{i \in [n_1]})$	rp_k, \mathbf{M} $\xrightarrow{\sigma}$ Checks the following Compute $h_m = H_0(\mathbf{M})$. Compute $Y' = e(\sigma_2, \sigma_4) / e(\sigma_3, \sigma_1)$ Compute $Z' = X^{s_\alpha} \cdot Y'^c$ $W' = \prod_{i \in [n_1]} H(i h_m \pi(i))^{s_i} \cdot \sigma_3^c$ $c' = H_0(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3, \sigma_4, Y', Z', W', \text{msg})$ If $c' \neq c$, output 0 otherwise, output 1

Figure 4.1: ABS with attribute anonymity

4.1.2 ABSC with Sender's Attribute Anonymity and Key Binding During Run-Time Phase

We now present the attribute-based signcryption scheme used during the run-time phase to establish a trust relationship between two devices belonging to different medical domains. This scheme supports the signer's attribute anonymity, preventing a verifier from learning the attribute set used to create the ABS. Our ABSC scheme is an extension of the ABS scheme presented in Section 4.1.1. In this scheme, the signer encrypts the signed message (Attestation data) under a certain policy through an Attribute-based Encryption (ABE) scheme. The decryptor should satisfy the decryption policy to allow a successful decryption of the cipher text.

- $\text{Setup}(1^\lambda) \rightarrow (\text{mpk}, \text{msk})$. It takes the security parameter λ as input. The CA picks $\alpha \leftarrow_{\$} \mathbb{Z}_p$, $H_0: \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_p$ and $H_1: \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow G_1$. The CA publishes $G := (p, G_1, G_2, G_T, e, g_1, g_2)$ and its public key $\text{mpk} := (G, H_0, H_1, X = e(g_1, g_2)^\alpha)$. The CA secret key is $\text{msk} := \alpha$ as in Algorithm 1.
- $\text{sKeyGen}(\text{msk}, (\mathbf{M}, \pi), I) \rightarrow \text{sk}$. The ABSC key generation algorithm (similar to Algorithm 1) outputs a set of attribute keys for someone who plays the role of a sender. The Privacy CA sends a set of attributes S to be certified for the user. Then the user with a root key ($\text{SK} = x, \text{PK} = g_2^x$), replies with $\sigma_i = H_1(i || h_m || \pi(i))^x$, where $h_m = H_0(\mathbf{M})$ for all $i \in I$, where I represents the set of indices of the attribute in S . The Privacy CA verifies each σ_i under PK . Then proceeds as follows: The CA picks $r \leftarrow_{\$} \mathbb{Z}_p$, $V \leftarrow_{\$} \mathbb{Z}_p^{n-1}$ and computes $h_m = H_0(\mathbf{M})$ and the attribute keys $\text{sk}_1 := g_2^r$; $\forall_{i \in I} \text{sk}_{2,i} := g_1^{\mathbf{M}(\alpha || V)^T} \cdot \sigma_i^r$. Finally, the CA outputs $\text{sk} := (\text{sk}_1, (\text{sk}_{2,i})_{i \in I})$.
- $\text{KeyGen}(\text{msk}, (\mathbf{M}', \pi')) \rightarrow \text{sk}'$. This ABSC key generation algorithm outputs a set of attribute keys for someone who plays the receiver role. The Privacy CA sends a set of attributes S' to be certified for the user. Then the user with a root key ($\text{SK}' = x', \text{PK}' = g_2^{x'}$), replies with $\sigma'_i = H_1(i || h'_m || \pi'(i))^x$, where $h'_m = H_0(\mathbf{M}')$ for all $i \in I'$, where I' represents the set of indices of the attribute in S' . The Privacy CA verifies each σ'_i under PK' . The CA picks $r \leftarrow_{\$} \mathbb{Z}_p$, $V' \leftarrow_{\$} \mathbb{Z}_p^{n-1}$. Compute $h'_m = H_0(\mathbf{M}')$ and the attribute keys $\text{sk}'_1 := g_2^r$, $\forall_{i \in I'} \text{sk}'_{2,i} := g_1^{\mathbf{M}'(\alpha || V')^T} \cdot \sigma'_i{}^r$. The CA outputs $\text{sk}' := (\text{sk}'_1, \text{sk}'_{2,i}) \forall i \in I'$.
- **ABSC Signcrypt:** This algorithm is run by the encryptor/signer. We follow the construction of the ABS scheme presented in Section 4.1.1 and add the encryption part of the message that is signed (this is step 8 in Algorithm 4). The steps of this phase are presented in Algorithm 4. Note that the signature and the encryption parts are glued together using the same parameter t to prove that the signer is the encryptor to avoid man-in-the-middle attacks.

Algorithm 4 ABSC Signcrypt: $\text{SignEnc}(\text{sk}, (S, S') \subseteq U, (\mathbf{M}, \pi), (\mathbf{M}', \pi'), \text{msg}) \rightarrow \sigma$

- 1: Pick $s, t, r_\alpha, (r_i)_{i \in [n_1]} \leftarrow_{\$} \mathbb{Z}_p$.
 - 2: Compute $h_m = H_0(\mathbf{M})$ and $h'_m = H_0(\mathbf{M}')$,
 - 3: $\sigma_1 := \text{sk}_1^{xt}$,
 - 4: $\sigma_2 := \prod_{i \in I} (\text{sk}_{2,i})^{y_i^s}$,
 - 5: $\sigma_3 := \prod_{i \in I} H_1(i || h_m || \pi(i))^{y_i^s} = \prod_{i \in [n_1]} H_1(i || h_m || \pi(i))^{y_i^s}$ since we choose $\forall i \in [n_1] \setminus I \gamma_i = 0$,
 - 6: $\sigma_4 := g_2^t$
 - 7: $\forall_{i \in I'} \sigma_{5,i} = H_1(i || h'_m || \pi'(i))^t$
 - 8: $\sigma_6 = X^t \cdot \text{msg}$
 - 9: $Y = X^{s \cdot t}$
 - 10: $Z = X^{r_\alpha}$
 - 11: $W = \prod_{i \in [n_1]} H_1(i || h_m || \pi(i))^{r_i}$
 - 12: $c = H_0(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3, \sigma_4, (\sigma_{5,i})_{i \in I'}, \sigma_6, Y, Z, W)$
 - 13: $s_\alpha = r_\alpha - s \cdot t \cdot c$,
 - 14: $\forall_{i \in I}, S_i = r_i - \gamma_i \cdot s \cdot c, \forall_{i \in [n_1] \setminus I} S_i = r_i$
 - 15: $\sigma := (\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3, \sigma_4, (\sigma_{5,i})_{i \in I'}, \sigma_6, c, s_\alpha, (S_i)_{i \in [n_1]})$
-

- **ABSC VerifyDec:** This algorithm is run by the decryptor/verifier. It takes a signcrypt and returns a verification result of 0 or 1. This algorithm also supports decryption and returns a message msg (Step 5 in Algorithm 5).

Algorithm 5 ABSC VerifyDec: $\text{VerifyDec}(\text{mpk}, S', (\mathbf{M}, \pi), (\mathbf{M}', \pi'), \sigma) \rightarrow 0/1$

- 1: Parse σ to $(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3, \sigma_4, (\sigma_{5,i})_{i \in I'}, \sigma_6, c, S_\alpha, (S_i)_{i \in [n_1]})$.
- 2: Compute $h_m = H_0(\mathbf{M})$ and $h'_m = H_0(\mathbf{M}')$.
- 3: Compute $Y' = e(\sigma_2, \sigma_4)/e(\sigma_3, \sigma_1)$.
- 4: Compute $Z' = X^{S_\alpha} \cdot Y^c$ and $W' = \prod_{i \in [n_1]} H_1(i || h_m || \pi(i))^{S_i} \cdot \sigma_3^c$.
- 5: Compute $c' = H_0(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3, \sigma_4, (\sigma_{5,i})_{i \in I'}, \sigma_6, Y', Z', W')$.
- 6: If $c' = c$, output 0; otherwise,

$$7: \text{Compute } \text{msg} = \frac{\prod_{i \in I'} \sigma_{5,i}^{v'_i} \cdot x'_i}{e \prod_{i \in I'} \text{sk}_{2,i}^{v'_i} \cdot \sigma_4^{x'_i}}.$$

This section provides a qualitative security analysis of the CIV, ABS, and ABSC schemes. It offers an initial high-level overview of the security proof for these schemes.

4.2 Security Analysis of Attribute-Based Signcryption

In this section, we will model the security properties provided in Table 4.1 and provide a concrete security proof for each property based on the Game-based model. A game-based proof, as defined in [36], starts with the initial game, which comes from the definition of each security property to be proved. This can be seen as a challenge involving the attacker and oracles. Attacker and oracles are efficient probabilistic algorithms, while oracles model services provided by the environment. For the ABS protocol, the goal of the adversary can be either one of the following:

- 1) To forge a signature with a predicate that his attributes do not satisfy. For instance, consider the use-case example presented in D4.2 [20] where the signer attribute set is

$$S = \{\text{Authenticated Tracer, Certified Trusted Computing base, Verifiable Policy Enforcer}\}$$

We mathematically proved that S doesn't satisfy the policy in D4.2 [20]. Therefore, the signer cannot generate a valid ABS that satisfies the policy matrix \mathbf{M} . This is achieved in our ABS scheme because the keys that correspond to the attributes in S are not enough to verify the correctness of the pairing $Y = e(\sigma_2, \sigma_4)/e(\sigma_3, \sigma_1)$. Recall that the attribute keys have the following construction: $\text{sk}_{2,i} := g_1^{M_i(\alpha || V^T)^T} \cdot \sigma^r$ for each row $i \in I$. Also, Algorithm 2 shows that $\sigma_2 := \prod_{i \in I} (\text{sk}_{2,i})^{Y_i^S}$ is a part of the ABS signature. If the attribute keys $\text{sk}_{2,i}$ corresponding to the attributes in S are not enough to satisfy \mathbf{M} as in our case, then the simplification of the $\prod_{i \in I} g_1^{M_i(\alpha || V^T)^T Y_i^S}$ is not possible because the equation $\sum_i Y_i^S M_i = (1, 0, \dots, 0)$ cannot be valid. Hence, the ABS signature will not be successfully verified. A corrupt signer might get the attribute key corresponding to the Secure Boot from another signer so to have enough keys to build an ABS valid signature, but this would not work in our scheme since the attribute keys are bound to the root-key of the device and generated from different seeds r for different users. This prevents any collusion between signers or impersonating attacks. Similar unforgeability arguments follow for our ABSC schemes.

- 2) To distinguish which attributes were used to generate a signature or any other identifying information associated with the particular signer amongst the users satisfying the predicate. This might lead to the device fingerprinting, which in turn can disclose information to the adversary of the internal device's characteristics (e.g., Operating System version, whitelist of binaries loaded as part of the operational stack) that can further lead to implementation disclosure attacks. The security requirements can be

summarized as unforgeability and attribute-signer privacy. For the ABSC, in addition to the above two targets, the ciphertext does not reveal any information about the encrypted message, which we call “Indistinguishability against Chosen Plaintext Attack (IND-CPA)” security. We formally define the security properties that are achieved in our ABSC and then provide full game-based proofs of these properties:

Property 1 (SC.1: Unforgeability). We consider that the ABS scheme is existentially unforgeable against chosen predicate and message attacks. Its formal definition is based on the following game involving a challenger B and an adversary A :

- Setup Phase: B runs Setup. B retains Privacy CA secret and public keys generated from Setup, sends the public key to A ;
- Query Phase: A can perform a polynomially bounded number of queries on (msg, S) to private key extraction oracle and signing oracle, respectively. These queries will be answered by B with a secret key.
- Forgery: Finally, A outputs an ABS signature σ^* on messages msg^* using an attribute set ω^* that satisfies a policy S^* .

We say that the adversary wins the game if σ^* is a valid signature on message msg^* for a policy S^* , such that (msg^*, S^*) has not been queried to the signing oracle and no attribute set ω such that there exists $\omega \subset \omega^*$ satisfying S^* has been submitted to the key generation oracle. The advantage of A is defined as the probability that it wins the game and should be negligible.

Property 2 (SC.6 IND-CPA) The security model for our ABSC scheme used during run-time addresses the property that a ciphertext does not reveal any information about the encrypted message, which we call “Indistinguishability against Chosen Plaintext Attack (IND-CPA)” security. We model the adaptive IND-CPA security in a game running between an adversary A and a challenger B as follows:

- Setup Phase: B runs Setup to obtain the Privacy CA public and secret keys. It sends the CA’s public key to the adversary and keeps the secret part.
- Phase 1. A issues queries to a key generation oracle for a Key generation oracle that issues a set of attribute keys for an attribute set S under a certain access matrix \mathbf{M} and sends the keys to A .
- Challenge. A outputs a challenging attribute set S^* with the restriction that S^* cannot satisfy any S that has been queried in Phase 1 and two equal-length messages msg_0^* and msg_1^* . Then B selects a random bit $b \in \{0, 1\}$, runs the encryption algorithm to get the ciphertext CT_b^* on a message msg_b^* under S^* and returns the challenge CT_b^* to A .
- Guess. A outputs $b' \in \{0, 1\}$ and wins the game if $b = b'$.

An ABSC scheme is adaptively IND-CPA secure if the advantage function defined by the probability $|b' = b| - 1/2$ is negligible. This property follows from the security of FABEO scheme.

Property 3 (SC.2-SC.4 Attribute Privacy in ABS). Given two valid attribute-based signatures σ_1 and σ_2 generated from two different attribute sets A_1 and A_2 (associated with two attribute key sets SK_1 and SK_2 generated and certified by a trusted authority) and satisfying the same policy P . Choose a random signature σ_i from $\{\sigma_1, \sigma_2\}$, the probability that an adversary knows which set of attributes in $\{A_1, A_2\}$ used to generate σ_i is $1/2$.

The privacy is achieved in our schemes by the construction of σ_3 and the Shonrr signatures as follows:

$$\sigma_3 := \prod_{i \in I} H_1(i || h_m || \pi(i))^{\gamma_i^s} = \prod_{i \in [n_1]} H_1(i || h_m || \pi(i))^{\gamma_i^s}$$
 since we choose $\forall i \in [n_1] / I \gamma_i = 0$. Note that a Shonrr signature is created on all the attributes in the matrix policy \mathbf{M} that represents the policy for the

Universe attribute set U , this not only helps in verifying the construction of σ_3 and hence σ but also hides the attributes used by the signer to satisfy P into a larger set U .

Property 4 (SC.7: The Key binding): This property requires the Privacy CA to be honest. An ABS protocol holds the key binding property if every valid ABS generated using a set of attribute keys sk_{PK} and the device's secret identity key x , which corresponds to the device public key PK , then $(sk_{PK} : (sk_1, sk_2), h_m, PK)$ is found in the CA's record, i.e., the attribute keys in sk_{PK} and PK should belong to the same device.

The key binding experiment $\text{Exp}_{\text{ABSC}}^{\text{keybind}}$ allows the adversary A to corrupt some attribute keys. In this game, the adversary is given access to a corrupt device's attribute keys sk_{PK}^* (resp. sk_{PK}^*) and generates an ABSC on behalf of the device using the attribute keys that can represent signing keys (resp. decryption keys) in sk_{PK}^* (resp. sk_{PK}^*) without the knowledge of the secret identity key x^* (resp. x^*) that corresponds to PK (resp. PK'). At the end of the execution. The outcome of the experiment is determined as follows. If the key (α, X) or $(x, PK)/(x', PK')$ has been corrupted, the experiment returns 0. Otherwise, if σ^* is valid, the experiment returns 1, else it returns 0.

We define the advantage of the adversary A in the key binding game as: $\text{Adv}_{\text{ABSC}}^{\text{keybind}}(v) = \Pr[\text{Exp}_{\text{ABSC}}^{\text{keybind}}(v) = 1]$ and say that the ABSC (ABS) protocol holds key binding if $\text{Adv}_{\text{ABSC}}^{\text{keybind}}(v)$ is a negligible function of v for all polynomial-time adversaries A .

4.3 Proof of the Unforgeability of the ABS/ ABSC

4.3.1 Hardness assumptions

Bilinear Diffie-Hellman Inversion (BDHI) assumption. We use a simplified version of the BDHI problem introduced in [14] with a Type-III setting.

We define $\text{par} := (p, G_1, G_2, G_T, e, g_1, g_2) \leftarrow \text{GroupGen}(1^\lambda)$, $\alpha, \beta \xleftarrow{\$} \mathbb{Z}_p$, $D = (g_1^\alpha, g_2^\alpha, g_1^\beta, g_2^\beta)$. The target is to compute $T = e(g_1, g_2)^{\alpha\beta}$. We denote the advantage of an algorithm A in solving the computational

BDHI problem by

$$\text{Adv}_A^{\text{BDHI}}(\lambda) := \Pr[A(\text{par}, D, T) = 1]$$

Which should be negligible in λ . We say that an algorithm $A(t, \epsilon)$ solves the BDHI problem in G_T if A runs in time at most t , $\text{Adv}_A^{\text{BDHI}}$ is at least ϵ .

Theorem 1. *Our ABS scheme satisfies unforgeability in the random oracle model under the BDHI assumption.*

Proof 1. *Suppose a PPT adversary A can break our ABS scheme in the selective unforgeability game. There exists an algorithm B that solves the BDHI problem. The simulator B is given a BDHI tuple $(g_1^\alpha, g_2^\alpha, g_1^\beta, g_2^\beta)$. B 's objective is to compute $e(g_1, g_2)^{\alpha\beta}$, it works by interacting with A as in the following game settings:*

Setup. *Let $l^* + 1$ denote the number of challenged attributes in S^* , including the identity attribute on which the adversary aims to create a forged ABS. Let $g_1 = \hat{g}_1^\alpha$ and $g_2 = \hat{g}_2$. B sets the master public key $X \leftarrow e(g_1, g_2)^\alpha = e(\hat{g}_1^\alpha, \hat{g}_2)^\alpha = e(\hat{g}_1, \hat{g}_2)^\alpha$. The master secret key is implicitly set as α , and g_1^α is implicitly set as $\hat{g}_1^{\alpha^2}$.*

B samples a uniformly random vector $V^ \in \mathbb{Z}_p^{n^*-1}$. If the attribute corresponding to the row M_i^* belongs to the challenge set S^*/id , the simulator calculates $\xi_i = M_i^* \cdot (1|V^*) \in \mathbb{Z}_p$. Note that if the attributes corresponding to the rows M_i^* satisfy the policy \mathbf{M} , then $\sum \xi_i = 1$. Assume that the attributes in S^*/id satisfies*

M. The adversary aims to forge an ABS signature on S^* without having the attribute key corresponding to the identity (not necessarily identity can be any attribute that the adversary doesn't have its key).

Let f_i be random secret integers randomly sampled by the simulator for each challenged attribute u_i and let $f = \sum_{i \in [1, l^*]} f_i$. The simulator samples a random integer d .

B sets the random oracle $H_1 : \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow G_1$ that takes an attribute as input and sets the output as follows:

- If the attribute corresponding to the row M^*_i belongs to the challenge set S^*/id , B sets:

$$H_1 : \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow g_1^{f_i - \xi_i d \alpha}$$

- If the attribute is the identity attribute, then B sets:

$$H_1 : \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \hat{g}_1^{d \alpha}$$

When A issues a query for generating a secret key on a set of attributes $S \subseteq S^*/id$. B runs the random oracle H_1 to obtain the corresponding $h_i \in G_1$ for each attribute u_i where the random oracle is defined as before. B defines $h_m = H_0(\mathbf{M})$ for all $i \in I$, where I represents the set of indices of the attributes in S , we denote I by $[1, l]$ for some integer $l < l^*$. Let r be a random integer in Z_p sampled by the simulator. The attribute keys are set as follows:

$$sk_1 := g_2^r$$

$$sk_{2,i} := \hat{g}_1^{\alpha^2/l^*} g_1^{(-d\alpha/l^*)r} g_1^{r f_i}$$

Then B implicitly sets $r = \alpha/d \forall i \in I$, then the simulator keys will be:

$$sk_1 := g_2^r = \hat{g}_2^{\frac{\alpha}{d}}$$

$$sk_{2,i} := \hat{g}_1^{\alpha^2/l^*} g_1^{(-d\alpha/l^*)\frac{\alpha}{d}} g_1^{f_i \frac{\alpha}{d}} = g_1^{\frac{f_i \alpha}{d}}$$

Signing oracle. When A issues a query for a signature with an access policy $P = (\mathbf{M} \in Z_p^{n_1 \times n_2}, \pi, \{\pi(i)\}_{i \in [n_1]})$ and a specific attribute **subset** of $S = \{u_i\}_{i \in [1, k]}$ on message msg . B runs the random oracle to obtain the corresponding h_i for each attribute $\pi(i)$. B proceeds as follows:

- Pick $s, t, r_\alpha, (r_i)_{i \in [n_1]} \leftarrow_{\$} Z_p$

$$\sigma_1 := sk_1 = g_2^{\frac{\alpha}{d} t}$$

$$\sigma_2 := \prod_{i \in [1, k]} (sk_{2,i})^{\gamma_i s} = \hat{g}_1^{\sum_{i \in [1, k]} f_i (\alpha/d) \gamma_i s}$$

$$\sigma_3 := \prod_{i \in [n_1]} H_1(i || h_m || \pi(i))^{\gamma_i s} = \prod_{i \in [1, k]} g_1^{\sum_{i \in [1, k]} (f_i - \xi_i d \alpha) \gamma_i s}$$

If the attributes corresponding to $[1, k]$ rows satisfies the policy \mathbf{M} , then $\sigma_3 = \hat{g}_1^{\sum_{i \in [1, k]} s f_i - s d \alpha}$. Note that $\gamma_i = 0$ if $i \notin [1, k]$, otherwise $\gamma_i = 1$.

$$\sigma_4 := g_2^t = g^{\alpha t}$$

$$Y = X^{s \cdot t}$$

- $Z = X^{r_\alpha}$,
- $W = \prod_{i \in [n_1]} H_1(i || h_m || \pi(i))^{r_i}$,
- $c = H_0(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3, \sigma_4, Y, Z, W, msg)$,
- $s_\alpha = r_\alpha - s \cdot t \cdot c$, and
- $\forall i \in [n_1] s_i = r_i - \gamma_i \cdot s \cdot c$.
- Output $\sigma := (\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3, \sigma_4, C, S_\alpha, (S_i)_{i \in [n_1]})$

The signature verification passes if S satisfies **M**. It is easy to see that:

$$e(g_1, g_2)^{\alpha s t} = e(g_1^{\alpha}, g_2^s)^{t} = Y' = e(\sigma_2, \sigma_4) / e(\sigma_3, \sigma_1)$$

$$= \frac{e(g_1^{\sum_{i \in [1, k]} f_i s_i}, g_2^t)}{e(g_1^{\sum_{i \in [1, k]} s_i - s d \alpha}, g_2^{\alpha t})}$$

This indicates that B can simulate a valid signature σ for A 's query without knowing the answer to the BDHI problem.

Forgery. When A outputs a valid forgery $\sigma^* = (\sigma_1^*, \sigma_2^*, \sigma_3^*, \sigma_4^*, s_\alpha^*, \{s_i^*\}_{i \in [n_1]}, c^*)$ on a message msg^* that satisfies the verification process, there exists $r^*, s^*, t^* \in \mathbb{Z}_p$ such that:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_1^* &= g_1^{\alpha} r^{*t^*} \\ \sigma_2^* &= \prod_{i \in [1, l^*]} (g_1^{s_i^* \alpha^2 / l^*} g_1^{-r^* s^* d \alpha / l^*} g_1^{r^* s^* f_i}) \cdot g_1^{r^* s^* \alpha d} \\ &= g_1^{\alpha^2 s^*} \cdot g_1^{\sum_{i \in [1, l^*]} f_i r^* s^*} \\ \sigma_3^* &= \prod_{i \in [n_1^*]} H_1(i || h_m || \pi(i))^{\gamma_i s^*} \\ &= \prod_{i \in [1, l^*]} (g_1^{s_i^* f_i - s^* \xi_i \alpha d}) g_1^{s^* \alpha d} \\ &= g_1^{\sum_{i \in [1, l^*]} s_i^* f_i} \end{aligned}$$

Note that $\gamma_i^* = 0$ if $i \notin S^*$ and 1 otherwise.

$$\sigma_4^* = g_1^{\alpha} t^{*2}$$

It proceeds by creating Schnorr signatures, as in the ABS protocol. It sets $s_\alpha^* = r^* - s^* \cdot t^* \cdot c^*$, $\forall i \in I^* : s_i^* = r^* - \gamma_i^* \cdot s^* \cdot c^*$, $\forall i \notin I^* : s_i^* = r^*$ and outputs σ^* .

The signature verification passes if S^* satisfies **M**. It is easy to see that:

$$e(g_1, g_2)^{\alpha s^* t^*} = e(g_1^{\alpha}, g_2^s)^{t^*} = Y'^* = e(\sigma_2^*, \sigma_4^*) / e(\sigma_3^*, \sigma_1^*)$$

=

$$\frac{e(\hat{g}_1^{\alpha^2 s^*}, \hat{g}_1^{\sum_{i \in [1, I^*]} f_i r^* s^*})}{e(\hat{g}_1^{\sum_{i \in [1, I^*]} s^* f_i}, \hat{g}_2^{r^* t^*})}$$

Then B uses the forking lemma [?] to extract the value $s^* t^*$ hidden in s^* , and the value $\{\gamma_i^* s\}_{i \in I}$ hidden in s^* : After a polynomial reply of A, B obtains two valid signatures (s^*, c^*) and (s^*, c^*) , where $c_1^* = c_2^*$. According to the scheme, $s^* = r^* - s^* t^* \cdot c^*$, $s^* = r^* - s^* t^* \cdot c^*$, then we can get $s^* - s^* = s^* t^* \cdot (c_2^* - c_1^*)$. Therefore, $s^* t^* = \frac{s_1^* - s_2^*}{c_2^* - c_1^*}$. Similarly, we can obtain $s^* - s^* = \gamma_i^* s^* \cdot (c_2^* - c_1^*)$, so $\gamma_i^* s^* = \frac{s_1^* - s_2^*}{c_2^* - c_1^*}$. By leveraging the knowledge of $s^* t^*$, $\{\gamma_i^* s^*\}_{i \in I}$ and $\{\gamma_i^*\}_{i \in I}$, B can first calculate the value of s^* and t^* separately, and then compute $g_2^{r^*} = \sigma_1^{t^*}$. Finally, B can extract the answer to the BDHI problem from the forgery by the following:

$$T = \frac{e(\sigma_2^{s^*}, \hat{g}_2^\beta)}{e(\hat{g}_1^\beta, \hat{g}_2^{r^*})^{\sum_{i \in [1, I^*]} f_i}}$$

4.4 Proof of Indistinguishability against Chosen Plaintext Attack (IND-CPA)

Theorem 2. Our A-KP-ABE scheme used in the ABSC is adaptively IND-CPA secure under the generic group model by modeling the hash function H_1 as a random oracle.

Proof 2. In the IND-CPA game, the only ciphertext component that is related to the two challenged messages is $\sigma_6 = e(g_1, g_2)^{\alpha t} \cdot \text{msg}$. Therefore, the adversary A attempts to win the game by distinguishing $\sigma_6 = e(g_1, g_2)^{\alpha t} \cdot \text{msg}_0^*$ from $\sigma_6 = e(g_1, g_2)^{\alpha t} \cdot \text{msg}_1^*$.

For $\tau \leftarrow \mathbb{Z}_p$, the probability of distinguishing $e(g_1, g_2)^{\alpha t} \cdot \text{msg}_0^*$ from $e(g_1, g_2)^\tau$ is equal to that of distinguishing $e(g_1, g_2)^\tau$ from $e(g_1, g_2)^{\alpha t} \cdot \text{msg}_1^*$. Therefore, if A has advantage ϵ in winning the IND-CPA game, then it has advantage $\epsilon/2$ in distinguishing $e(g_1, g_2)^{\alpha t}$ from $e(g_1, g_2)^\tau$. Thus, we consider the game where A can distinguish $e(g_1, g_2)^{\alpha t}$ from $e(g_1, g_2)^\tau$. The modified game is simulated as follows:

Setup. The challenger B chooses $\alpha \leftarrow \mathbb{Z}_p$ and sends the public key $pk; (g_1, g_2, X = e(g_1, g_2)^\alpha)$ to A.

Phase 1. In phase 1, A can make oracle queries to the random oracle and a key generation oracle as follows:

Random Oracle: When A makes a query, B outputs

$$H_1 : \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow g_1^d$$

Key generation oracle: When A makes a key query for an access policy, B picks $r \leftarrow \mathbb{Z}_p$ and a vector $V^r \leftarrow \mathbb{Z}^{n^2-1}$. Let $m_i = \mathbf{M}(\alpha || V^r)$. Note that the m_i is random since it depends on the random distribution of α and V^r . Then B generates the secret key as the following: $sk_1 = g_2^r, \forall i \in I^* sk_{2,i} := g_2^{m_i + d_i r}$ and sends them to A.

Challenge: A outputs an attribute set S^* and two messages $\text{msg}_1^*, \text{msg}_2^*$ that it intends to attack. B checks if S^* satisfies any access policy queried in Phase 1. If yes, B aborts. Otherwise, B chooses $t, \tau \leftarrow \mathbb{Z}_p$. B chooses $\mu \leftarrow \{0, 1\}$. If $\mu = 0$, it generates the challenge ciphertext as follows: If $\mu = 0$, then $\sigma_6 : e(g_1, g_2)^{\alpha t}, \sigma_4 : g_2^t, \forall i \in I^* \sigma_{5,i} = g_2^{d_i}$. Otherwise, $\sigma_6 : e(g_1, g_2)^\tau, \sigma_4 : g_2^t, \forall i \in I^* \sigma_{5,i} = g_1^{d_i t}$. B sends the ciphertext to A.

Phase 2. It is the same as in Phase 1, with the restriction the input access policy \mathbf{M} is not satisfied by the challenge attribute set S^* .

If A can construct $e(g_1, g_2)^{\delta\alpha}$ for some $\delta \in \mathbb{Z}_p$ that can be combined from the oracle outputs already queried, then A can use it to distinguish $e(g_1, g_2)^{\alpha}$ from $e(g_1, g_2)^{\tau}$. A can construct $e(g_1, g_2)^{\delta\alpha}$ with negligible probability since A needs to cancel the term m_i to get g^α . However, it is impossible to reconstruct α since any input access policy \mathbf{M} cannot be satisfied by the attribute sets S^* . Therefore, A cannot gain a non-negligible advantage in the IND-CPA game.

4.5 Proof of attribute privacy

(This is only needed in the run-time phase and is not required for the enrolment proofs)

Definition 1. Decisional External Diffie-Hellman (XDH) assumption.

Define $\text{par} := (p, G_1, G_2, G, T, e, g, g_1, g_2) \leftarrow \text{GroupGen}(1^\lambda)$, $a, b, R \xleftarrow{\$} \mathbb{Z}_p$, $D = (g_1^a, g_1^b)$. $T_0 = g_1^{ab}$, $T_1 = g_1^R$. The advantage of an algorithm A in deciding the XDH problem

$$\text{Adv}_A^{\text{XDH}}(\lambda) := \Pr [A(\text{par}, D, T_0) = 1] - \Pr [A(\text{par}, D, T_1) = 1]$$

is negligible in λ . The probability is over the random choice of the parameters and the coin tosses of A . We say that an algorithm $A(t, \epsilon)$ decides XDH problem in G_1 if A runs in time at most t , $\text{Adv}_A^{\text{XDH}}$ is at least ϵ .

The (t, ϵ) XDH assumption holds in G_1 if no t -time algorithm has an advantage at least ϵ in solving the XDH problem.

Theorem 3. Our ABS scheme has adaptive attribute privacy in the random oracle model under the Decisional XDH problem.

Proof 3.

4.6 Proof of the Attribute-Identity Key Binding

Theorem 4. Our ABS/ ABSC schemes have the key binding property if BLS signature scheme is EU-CMA (Existential Unforgeability under a Chosen Message Attack) secure and the DH problem is hard.

Proof 4. Suppose that an adversary gets access to an attribute key set $\text{sk}^* : (\text{sk}_1^*, \text{sk}_2^*)$ and wants to create a signature without the knowledge of the secret identity key x^* that corresponds to PK^* under which the attribute keys were issued by the Privacy CA.

Case 1: The adversary proceeds as follows: Picks $s^*, t^*, r^*, (r_i^*)_{i \in [n]} \leftarrow_{\$} \mathbb{Z}_p$. A then computes $h_m = H_0(\mathbf{M})$ and $h'_m = H_0(\mathbf{M})$, however we assumed that the adversary has no information about x^*, r^* , then the adversary chooses a random f for x^* and proceeds by setting $\sigma_1 := \text{sk}_1^{ft^*}$.

Case 2: The adversary proceeds as follows: Picks $s^*, t^*, r^*, (r_i^*)_{i \in [n]} \leftarrow_{\$} \mathbb{Z}_p$. A then computes $h_m = H_0(\mathbf{M})$ and $h'_m = H_0(\mathbf{M})$, $\sigma_1^* := \text{sk}_1^{r^*t^*} = \text{PK}^{r^*t^*}$, however we assumed that the adversary has no information about x^*, r^* , then the adversary chooses a random f for r^* and proceeds by setting $\sigma_1^* := \text{PK}^{ft^*}$.

The adversary then proceeds in both cases as normal ABS: $\sigma_2^* := \prod_{i \in I} (\text{sk}_{2,i}^*)^{v_i s^*}$,

$$\sigma^* := \prod_{i \in I} H(i || h || \pi(i))^{v_i s^*} = \prod_{i \in [n]} H(i || h || \pi(i))^{v_i s^*}$$

since we choose $\forall i \in [n_1] \setminus I \gamma_i = 0$, $\sigma_4^* := g_2^{t^*} \prod_{i \in I'} \sigma_{5,i}^* = H_1(i || h_m || \pi(i))^{t^*}$ and $\sigma_6^* = X^{t^*} \cdot msg$.

A calculates $Y^* = X^{s^* t^*}$, $Z^* = X^{r^* \alpha}$, $W^* = \prod_{i \in [n_1]} H_1(i || h_m || \pi(i))^{r^*}$ and the challenge $c^* = H_0(\sigma_1^*, \sigma_2^*, \sigma_3^*, \sigma_4^*, (\sigma_{5,i}^*)_{i \in I'}, \sigma_6^*, Y^*, Z^*, W^*)$. It then creates proof of knowledge of the parameters $s^* \alpha = r^* \alpha - s^* \cdot t^* \cdot c^*$. Finally, $\sigma^* := (\sigma_1^*, \sigma_2^*, \sigma_3^*, \sigma_4^*, (\sigma_{5,i}^*)_{i \in I'}, \sigma_6^*, c^*, s^*, (s^*)_{i \in [n_1]})$. We want to argue that σ^* is accepted if σ_1^* is well constructed, and this cannot be completed without the knowledge of x^* or r^* . The adversary proceeds without the knowledge of r^* or x^* as follows:

Assuming that the adversary gets the required attribute keys, the signature is only verified if $Y' = e(\sigma_2^*, \sigma_4^*) / e(\sigma_3^*, \sigma_1^*)$ and $Z' = X^{s^* \alpha} \cdot Y^{*c^*}$ and

$$W' = \prod_{i \in [n_1]} H_1(i || h_m || \pi(i))^{s^*} \cdot \sigma_6^{*c^*}$$

$c' = c^* = H_0(\sigma_1^*, \sigma_2^*, \sigma_3^*, \sigma_4^*, (\sigma_{5,i}^*)_{i \in I'}, \sigma_6^*, Y', Z', W')$. This means that $Y^* = Y'$ equals

$$Y' = \frac{e(\prod_{i \in I'} (g_1^{v_i s^*} M_{\alpha || V^*})^{r^*} \cdot H_1(i || h_m || \pi(i))^{x^* r^* \gamma_i s^*}, g_2^{t^*})}{e(\prod_{i \in [n_1]} H_1(i || h_m || \pi(i))^{\gamma_i s^*}, sk_1^{t^*})}$$

or

$$Y' = \frac{e(\prod_{i \in I'} (g_1^{v_i s^*} M_{\alpha || V^*})^{r^*} \cdot H_1(i || h_m || \pi(i))^{x^* r^* \gamma_i s^*}, g_2^{t^*})}{e(\prod_{i \in [n_1]} H_1(i || h_m || \pi(i))^{\gamma_i s^*}, PK^{t^*})}$$

In both cases, this is only true if $f = r^*$, which contradicts our assumption that the Privacy CA is not corrupt, or $f = x^*$, which contradicts that the device identity key is unknown to the adversary. The adversary is not able to find $g_2^{x^* r^*}$ (due to the hardness of the DH) even with the knowledge of $g_2^{x^*}$ and $g_2^{r^*}$. Hence, the adversary succeeds in this game by randomly guessing x^* (due to the unforgeability of the BLS signature $H_1(i || h_m || \pi(i))^{x^*}$) or r^* (due to hardness of the DL) with a probability of $1/q + 1/q = 2/q$, which is low for a large enough q . \square

4.7 Overview of the Domain Enrolment

The Domain Manager (DM), upon receiving an enrolment request from the high-end device, authenticates the device based on its Root Key RK. The DM then generates a Domain ID for the device to be enrolled and sends this ID together with a domain key generation request to the Privacy CA. The Privacy CA is the entity responsible for issuing the attribute keys, the device domain key which can be considered as an attribute key for the device should be bound to the other device's attribute keys. The only entity that can do this binding is the Privacy CA since it can retrieve the seed used to generate the attribute key and create the domain key from the same seed. Note that all the attribute keys are bound to the device's Root Key to prevent sharing these keys among unauthorized devices. Upon successful issuance of the domain key from the Privacy CA, this key will be encrypted and sent to the DM. The DM then certifies this key and initiates an Attribute-based Signcryption, i.e. the DM first encrypts the domain key under a certain policy that allows the device to decrypt the message and retrieves the domain key only if it holds certain sets of attributes. The DM then creates an Attribute-based Signature on the generated cipher text (the encrypted domain key) under some of his attributes that satisfy a certain policy by DM. Finally, the DM sends the signcryption to the device. The device then verifies the DM signature and decrypts the cipher text as in Figure 4.2.

The device generates its Attestation Key AK: $f, F = g_1^f$ and sends it together with its public part of the Root Key to the DM. The DM then creates a shared symmetric key that is derived from the device Attestation key and domain key. The device then uses this key to create a symmetric signature T and

sends it to the DM. The DM upon successful verification of T proceeds with creating the credential for the Trusted Component Attestation Key as in Figure 4.3. The DM wraps the credential and sends it to the Trusted Component through the device. The Trusted Component unwraps the credential. This Trusted Component operation is called "activate credential." The device then verifies the credential, i.e., verifying that the signature provided on the Trusted Component public attestation key under the DM public key is valid. Finally, the device stores the credential and loads it whenever it needs to generate attestations.

Figure 4.2: Enrolment Authentication for Edge devices based on AACKA[42]

Figure 4.3: Attestation Key Credential Issuance based on the enhanced privacy-CA solution (ePCAS) in [12]

4.8 Security Analysis of the Domain Enrolment

Credential Unforgeability We consider that our scheme is existentially unforgeable against chosen message attacks. Its formal definition is based on the following game involving a challenger B and an adversary A :

- Setup Phase: B runs Setup. B retains the DM secret and public keys generated from Setup, sends the public key to A ;
- Query Phase: A can perform a polynomially bounded number of queries on some attestation keys F to the private key extraction oracle and signing oracle, respectively. These queries will be answered by B with a secret key by outputting $(F, CRED)$ to the adversary.
- Forgery: Finally, A outputs a credential $CRED^*$ on a device public attestation key F^* .

We say that the adversary wins the game if $CRED^*$ is a valid credential on F^* , such that $(F^*, CRED^*)$ has not been queried to the signing oracle. The advantage of A is defined as the probability that it wins the game and should be negligible.

Theorem 5. *Our protocol is unforgeable if the signature scheme used in SIG is EU-CMA secure.*

Proof. This is reduced to the unforgeability of the signature SIG used by the DM to generate the credential, this can be BBS, CL, etc.. □

4.9 Security Analysis for Attestation-Identity Key Binding

Definition 2. The Key binding Experiment: *This property requires the device with an identity key (x, g^x) to be honest. This property guarantees that if the device with an identity key $(SK : x, PK : g^x)$ holds a valid credential $CRED$ on an Attestation key F , then F should be bound to the device's unique identity key (SK, PK) .*

The key binding experiment $\text{Exp}_{\text{Att}}^{\text{keybind}}$ allows the adversary A to corrupt some attestation keys. In this game, the adversary is given access to corrupt devices' attestation keys f^* and generates a self-certification SCER on behalf of an honest device using the attestation key f^* without the knowledge of the secret identity key x of the honest device, that corresponds to the public part PK .

At the end of the execution, the outcome of the experiment is determined as follows: if the key (x, PK) has been corrupted, the experiment returns 0. Otherwise, the experiment returns 1.

Definition 3. Key binding: We define the advantage of the adversary A in the key binding game as: $\text{Adv}_{\text{Att}}^{\text{keybind}}(v) = \Pr[\text{Exp}_{\text{Att}}^{\text{keybind}}(v) = 1]$ and say that the protocol holds key binding if $\text{Adv}_{\text{Att}}^{\text{keybind}}(v)$ is a negligible function of v for all polynomial-time adversaries A .

Theorem 6. Our scheme has the key binding property if and the DH problem is hard and the encryption scheme ENC is IND-CPA secure.

Proof 5. Suppose an adversary gains access to a corrupt attestation key f^* and attempts to create a signature without knowledge of the secret identity key x that corresponds to PK , under which the attestation key credential will be issued by the DM.

The adversary proceeds as follows: The adversary sends PK to the DM. The DM then samples $r \leftarrow \mathbb{Z}_q$ and calculates $H = g_1^r$, $R = \text{ENC}_{PK}(H | DK_E)$ for some DK_E issued by the privacy CA and bounded to x . The DM sends R to the device.

The adversary cannot decrypt R since it doesn't know the secret x (SK). It samples a random H^* and k^* , then calculates $Z^* = H^{*f^*}$ and $T^* = \text{MAC}(H^*, k^*)$. The adversary T^* to the DM. The DM calculates $Z = F^{*r}$ and $k = \text{KDF}(Z, DK_E)$ then checks $T^* = \text{MAC}(H, k)$. The encryption scheme ENC is stated to be IND-CPA secure, which means it is secure against chosen plaintext attacks. This provides confidence that the adversary cannot gain any useful information from R .

Probability of Abortion: Since the adversary does not have access to the secret key x that corresponds to PK , then with high probability the check $T^* = \text{MAC}(H, k)$ will fail and the DM will abort. This is because the device doesn't succeed to prove a knowledge of both secret keys f and x simultaneously. The DM will abort the operation, preventing any unauthorized access or manipulation.

The described protocol emphasizes strong security measures through the use of encryption and MACs, ensuring that only devices with the correct knowledge of secret keys can successfully authenticate and communicate with the DM. This design helps safeguard against adversarial attempts to compromise the integrity of the communication.

4.10 Security Analysis of p-ABCs for CC Management

4.10.1 A brief description of the high-end CC protocols presented in ENTRUST D4.2 [20] and previous section

The CC Setup algorithm (Algorithm 6) takes the number of attributes to consider k , a security parameter λ (which is used to choose a pairing-friendly group and generators) and generates the Issuer secret key $\text{CCpabc}_{\text{priv}} = (x, \{y_i\}_k, y_{k+1})$ and the corresponding public key $\text{CCpabc}_{\text{pub}} = (X, \{Y_i\}_k, Y_{k+1})$. The Issuer publishes the system public parameters G with its public key $\text{CCpabc}_{\text{pub}}$.

Algorithm 6 CC Setup and KeyGen

- 1: Take the security parameter λ and number of attributes as input
- 2: Run PS-MS.Setup(k, Γ) to get public parameters pp , including $G := (p, G_1, G_2, G_T, e, g_1, g_2)$
- 3: Run PS-MS.KeyGen(pp) to get $CCpabc_{priv} = (x, \{y_i\}_k, y_{k+1})$ and $CCpabc_{pub} = (X, \{Y_i\}_k, Y_{k+1})$
- 4: Output $pp, CCpabc_{pub}$

The algorithm Issue($CCpabc_{priv}, \vec{a}, AK_{pub}$) (Algorithm 7) takes an attribute set \vec{a} a p-ABC signature σ for the CC. This algorithm is run by the issuer.

Algorithm 7 CC Issue: Issue($CCpabc_{priv}, \vec{a}, AK_{pub}$) $\rightarrow \sigma$

- 1: Parse $\vec{t} = (t_i)_{i=1}^k$ with $t_i = a_i$ for $i = \{1 \dots k - 1\}$ and $t_k = AK_{pub}$
- 2: Run PS - MS.Sign($CCpabc_{priv}, \vec{t}$), that is:
- 3: $(t', h) = H(\sum_{i=1}^k t_i)$
- 4: $w = x + \sum_{i=1}^k y_i t_i + y_{k+1} t'_k$
- 5: Output $\sigma = (t', h, h^w)$

The algorithm PresentCC($CCpabc_{pub}, \vec{a}, AK_{priv}, \phi, ctx$) (Algorithm 8) takes a CC (p-ABC) signature, the policy ϕ and a context ctx and outputs a presentation token if $\phi(\vec{a}) = \text{True}$. This algorithm is run by the Conformity Certificate holder, i.e. the device.

Algorithm 8 CC Present: PresentCC($CCpabc_{pub}, \vec{a}, \sigma, AK_{priv}, \phi, ctx$) $\rightarrow pt$

- 1: Parse $\vec{t} = (t_i)_{i=1}^k$ with $t_i = a_i$ for $i = \{1 \dots k - 1\}$ and $t_k = AK_{pub}$
- 2: Perform PS - MS.PresentZk($CCpabc_{pub}, \sigma, t, \phi, ctx$) to obtain a derived ZK proof $\pi = (\sigma', \sigma', \pi')$
- 3: Sign with attestation key $\sigma_{AK} = \text{SIGN}(\pi, AK_{priv})$
- 4: Output $pt = (\sigma_{AK}, \pi)$

The algorithm VerifyCCtok($CCpabc_{pub}, pt, \vec{a}_{revealed}, AK_{pub}, \phi, ctx$) (Algorithm 9) takes a presentation token for a CC pt , the policy ϕ (and the revealed attributes including the public attestation key) and a context ctx and outputs 1/0 depending on the validity. This algorithm is run by the Verifier.

Algorithm 9 CC Verify: VerifyCCtok($CCpabc_{pub}, pt, \vec{a}_{revealed}, AK_{pub}, \phi, ctx$) $\rightarrow pt$

- 1: Run $r_1 = \text{VERIFY}(\sigma_{AK}, \pi, AK_{pub})$.
- 2: Parse $\vec{t}_{revealed} = (t_i)_{i \in \text{revealed}}$ with $t_i = a_i$ for $i \in \text{revealed}$ and $t_k = AK_{pub}$
- 3: Run $r_2 = \text{PS - MS.VerifyZk}(CCpabc_{pub}, \pi, \vec{t}_{revealed}, \phi, ctx)$
- 4: Output 1 if $r_1 = r_2 = 1$ and 0 otherwise

4.10.2 Security Properties of the High-End CC Scheme

For the Conformity Certificate protocol, particularly in the case of high-end devices, the goal of the adversary can be either one of the following:

- 1) To forge the presentation of a conformity certificate with attributes that he does not satisfy. For example, if an auditor requires the validation of a conformity certificate demonstrating that the device complies with the *integrity* and *resilience* trust evaluations. In our protocol, forging a signature for the CC would require corruption of the issuer's private key because of the unforgeability of the p-ABC scheme, while

forging a zero-knowledge token that "reveals" the wrong set of attributes is again ruled out by the p-ABC's unforgeability property [25]. Additionally, the protocol mandates that CC is bound to the device's public part of the attestation key as one of the attributes that must be revealed, and a presentation requires a fresh signature using this attestation key, ruling out the use of CC's unintended for the device.

2) Similarly to the ABS scheme, an adversary may try to distinguish which attributes are contained in the CC used to generate a presentation token, or any other identifying information associated with the particular element beyond the presentation policy. In our protocol, the protection of undisclosed attributes is derived from the unlinkability property of the p-ABC scheme [25]. Note that unlinkability is not needed (or achieved) by our CC protocol, only the privacy property known as selective disclosure.

The security requirements can be summarized as unforgeability and CC-holder's attribute privacy. We formally define the security properties that are achieved in our ABSC and then provide game-based proofs of these properties.

Property 1 (Unforgeability). We consider that the CC scheme is existentially unforgeable against chosen message attacks. The formal definition is based on the game between a challenger B and an adversary A :

- Setup phase: B runs CC Setup and KeyGen, and gives the $CCpabc_{pub}$ key to A
- Query phase: A can perform a polynomially bounded number of queries on a issuing, presentation and issuance reveal oracles, defined as follows:
 - ✓ $O_{issue}(j, \vec{a}^j, AK_{pub}^j)$: Run $Issue(CCpabc_{priv}, \vec{a}^j, AK_{pub}^j) \rightarrow \sigma_j$ and add $\{j, \vec{a}^j, AK_{pub}^j\}$ to Q_{issue}
 - ✓ $O_{present}(j, \phi, AK_{priv}, ctx)$: Add $\{\phi, \vec{a}^j, AK_{pub}^j, ctx\}$ to $Q_{present}$ and return $pt \leftarrow PresentCC(CCpabc_{pub}, \vec{a}^j, \sigma_j, AK_{priv}, \phi, ctx)$
 - ✓ $O_{revealsign}(j)$: Add $\{\vec{a}^j, AK_{pub}^j\}$ to $Q_{revealsign}$ and return σ_j
- Forgery Phase: A outputs a token pt^* on attributes \vec{a}^* , AK_{pub}^* , context ctx^* so that $\phi^*(\vec{a}^*) = 1$.

The adversary then wins if the forgery is valid, that is: $VerifyCctok(CCpabc_{pub}, pt^*, \vec{a}^*, AK_{pub}^*, \phi^*, ctx^*) = 1$ and it did not get a legitimate credential fulfilling the requirements, $(\phi^*(\vec{a}^j) = 0 \vee AK_{pub}^* \neq AK_{pub}^j) \vee \{ \vec{a}^j, AK_{pub}^j \} \in Q_{revealsign}$, nor queried the presentation oracle on the input, $\{\phi, \vec{a}^j, AK_{pub}^j, ctx\} \notin Q_{present}$. The advantage of A is defined as the probability that it wins the game and should be negligible.

Property 2 (Selective disclosure), or attribute privacy. Given two sets of attributes \vec{a}_1 and \vec{a}_2 that fulfil a predicate ϕ for which two valid CCs σ_1 and σ_2 are generated (controlled by the adversary)¹, the challenger B generates a presentation token for an adversarially chosen ctx for a randomly chosen CC, pt^* and gives it back to the adversary. Then the probability that the adversary knows which set of attributes (or which CC signature) were used to generate pt^* is $1/2 + \text{negl}(\lambda)$

Property 3 (Device attestation key binding). The CC protocol fulfils this property if it is unfeasible for an adversary to forge a presentation token for a AK_{pub} for which it does not control the AK_{priv} . This is formally defined by the following game:

- Setup phase: B generates a pair $\{AK_{priv}, AK_{pub}\}$ and gives AK_{pub} to the adversary.

¹Note that we do not allow two different attestation keys that would lead to trivial distinction as they are always revealed, but we do not seek privacy for these keys)

- Query phase: A can perform a polynomially bounded number of queries on a signing oracle O_{sign} , answered by B with a secret key. Note that we give the adversary full control over the CC issuance key, other attributes in the CC, context and predicate.
- Forgery: Finally, A outputs a token pt^* for AK_{pub} and his chosen set of attributes, predicates, context, and $CCpabc_{\text{pub}}^*$.

The adversary then wins if the forgery is valid, that is: $V_{\text{erifyCCtok}}(CCpabc_{\text{pub}}^*, pt^*, \vec{a}^*, AK_{\text{pub}}, \phi^*, ctx^*) = 1$, and he did not call the signing oracle on a message whose signature is verified during $V_{\text{erifyCCtok}}$. The advantage of A is defined as the probability that it wins the game and should be negligible.

As an additional feature of the protocol, proactive **revocation** of credentials, is made possible using a deny list approach. A revocation handle is included in each CC and a public list of revoked credentials is kept updated in the ENTRUST blockchain. Note that, additionally, credentials will have an expiration time that can be adjusted to the expected periodicity of attestation processes or desired lifetimes according to the use case, so generally most CCs will be revoked by default after they expire and do not need to be kept in the revocation list. This approach allows us to achieve the desired revocation functionality, it does not compromise the privacy property as unlinkability of CCs was not considered anyway, and its security is trivially derived from the unforgeability property of the protocol (i.e., an adversary will not be able to present a CC with a different revocation handle than the one legitimately signed by the issuer).

4.10.3 Proofs

In this section, we provide proofs that the proposed high-end CC protocol achieves the security properties outlined. Note that in the proofs we will rely on the *generic* security properties of the p-ABC scheme selected in D4.2 [20], so it could be directly substituted in the protocols for any other p-ABC scheme that provides EUF-CMA for the signing process and the Zero-knowledge presentation process (e.g. BBS + [33]) without harming the functionality or security of the protocol. Similarly, for the attestation signature, we simply assume an EUF-CMA signing scheme, so we are not constrained to the specifics of the signing scheme or its key management.

Theorem 7. *The CC protocol in Section 4.10.1 fulfils the unforgeability property.*

Proof 6. *In this case, the security is reduced to the unforgeability (EUF-CMA) of the signature, and simulation-sound extractability and zero-knowledge properties of the presentation in the PS-MS scheme. The latter are used to extract a witness from the adversaries forgery, which leads to a forgery of the EUF-CMA property of the signature.*

More concretely, from the original security game we create a modified game where the O_{present} oracle, instead of running step 2 in Algorithm 8, generates a simulated proof. As PS-MS presentation is zero-knowledge, this is computationally indistinguishable to the adversary, and thus result in at most a negligible difference in his advantage.

Then, if we assume A wins the modified game, we can construct an algorithm B that breaks PS-MS EUF-CMA security for σ by interacting with the adversary A in the following way:

- Setup phase: Take $CCpabc_{\text{pub}}$ and public parameters output by challenger and send them to A
- Query phase: B responds to the oracle calls in the following way:
 - ✓ $O_{\text{issue}}(j, \vec{a}^j, AK_{\text{pub}}^j)$: Add $\{j, \vec{a}^j, AK_{\text{pub}}^j\}$ to Q_{issue}
 - ✓ $O_{\text{present}}(j, \phi, AK_{\text{priv}}, ctx)$: Add $\{\phi, \vec{a}^j, AK_{\text{pub}}^j, ctx\}$ to Q_{present} and return pt where the modified version of PresentCC with a simulated ZK proof in step 2.

- ✓ $O_{\text{revealsign}}(\vec{a}^j) : \text{Add } \{\vec{a}^j, AK_{\text{pub}}^j\} \text{ to } Q_{\text{revealsign}}, \text{ set } \vec{t} = (AK_{\text{pub}}^j, \vec{a}^j) \text{ and return the result of } O_{\text{sign}}(\vec{t}) \text{ from the EUF-CMA game. Successive calls to } j \text{ return the same } \sigma_j.$
- *If A wins through $pt^* = (\sigma_{AK}^*, \pi^*)$, try to extract a witness σ^* from π^* . If successfully extracted a witness $(\sigma, AK_{\text{pub}}, a)$, output (σ, t) with $t = (AK_{\text{pub}}, a)$ as a forgery.*

The probability that B fails to extract a witness from π^* is negligible due to the simulation-sound extractability property of the PS-MS presentation protocol. Thus, if A wins, B outputs the forgery with overwhelming probability. As the winning conditions for the security game require that A did not call $O_{\text{revealsign}}$ for $(\vec{a}^*, AK_{\text{pub}})$, B did not call during the execution O_{sign} for t^* , so it would be an actual forgery that makes B win the game.

Theorem 8. *The CC protocol in Section 4.10.1 fulfils the selective disclosure property.*

Proof 7. *This is reduced to the zero-knowledge property of the PS-MS scheme.*

Particularly, we can modify the security game so that instead of B running step 2 of the PresentCC(CCpabc_{pub}, \vec{a} , σ , AK_{priv} , ϕ , ctx) \rightarrow pt process (Algorithm 8), it simulates a proof. This will be computationally indistinguishable for the adversary due to PS – MS being zero-knowledge. The output pt^* in the modified experiment does not give A any input related to the chosen bit, so the probability of a correct guess is 1/2. As the modification is computationally indistinguishable to the adversary, the difference of advantages is at most negligible.

Theorem 9. *The CC protocol in Section 4.10.1 has the attestation key binding property.*

Proof 8. *In this case, it is trivial to see that this property for our high-end CC protocol is reduced to the existential unforgeability under chosen message attacks of the signing scheme SIGN used with the attestation key.*

Chapter 5

ENTRUST Agile Swarm Attestation

This chapter details the final version of the ENTRUST Agile Swarm Attestation protocol, a comprehensive framework for establishing the trustworthiness of large-scale groups of low-end devices. The design addresses the dual challenges of scalability and the need for granular, attribute-based verification in resource-constrained settings. The chapter is structured to guide the reader from the foundational building blocks to the complete protocol and its formal security proof.

The presentation is organized as follows:

1. **Cryptographic Foundations:** We begin by reviewing the underlying cryptographic primitives, including Winternitz One-Time Signatures (**WOTS+**) and the use of **Merkle hash trees** for aggregating multiple public keys into a single, verifiable root.
2. **Attribute-Based Attestation:** We then introduce the core innovation of the protocol: the construction of per-device **Attribute Trees**. This mechanism binds one-time keys to specific, attestable device properties, enabling dynamic and fine-grained verification.
3. **Protocol Architecture and Phases:** The complete, multi-party protocol is presented, detailing the roles of the Manufacturer, Domain Manager (DM), high-end "mother" device, and low-end "child" devices. We describe the full lifecycle of the protocol, from the initial **Setup** and **Enrollment** to the **Attestation & Report** and final **Verification** phases.
4. **Formal Security Analysis:** Finally, we formally define the security properties of the swarm attestation scheme, such as unforgeability, traceability, and attribute disclosure. We then outline a rigorous proof of security using the **Universal Composability (UC) model**, demonstrating that the protocol securely achieves its goals in a complex, adversarial environment.

5.1 Overview of One-time signatures (WOTS, WOTS+)

For one-time signatures (OTS), we use a variant of the Winternitz signature scheme [7]. In this scheme, the message to be signed is hashed to create a digest, which is encoded as a base w number. Each digit of the digest is then signed using a hash chain, as follows. A hash chain is created by randomly generating a secret key R_i of PUF using a challenge C_i . The size of R_i is 256 bits long. The public key, PK_{OTS}^i , is then created by applying the hash function, H , to the secret concatenated with the device's Expected State $b-1$ times, i.e. $PK_{OTS}^i = H^{w-1}(R_i | \text{Expected State})$. The manufacturer creates these keys and then sends them to the DM, which creates the Merkle tree as before.

When the device wants to create a signature corresponding to a challenge C_i . The device, using its PUF creates the k^{th} the digest, one time signature, $s_k = H^{N_k}(R_i | \text{current State})$, is signed by applying the hash function, H , to the private key concatenated with the device's Current State N_k times. The signature for the k^{th} digit of a digest can be verified by checking that $PK_{OTS}^i = H^{w-1-N_k}(s_k)$.

To create a hash tree, the OTS public keys are hashed once to form the tree leaves, and these hashes are then hashed together in pairs to form the next level up. Those hash values are then hashed together in pairs, the resulting hash values are hashed together, and so on, until all public keys have been used to generate a single hash value (the root of the tree), which will be used as the long-term public key.

5.2 WOTS+: One-Time Signatures

WOTS+ is an OTS scheme; while a private key can be used to sign any message, each private key **MUST** be used only once to sign a single message. In particular, if a private key is used to sign two different messages, the scheme becomes insecure.

- WOTS+ uses the following parameters: n , which denotes the message length and the length of a private key, public key, or signature element in bytes. w : the Winternitz parameter; it is a member of the set 4, 16. A higher value of w results in shorter signatures but slower overall signing operations; it has little effect on security. Choices of w are limited to the values 4 and 16 since these values yield optimal trade-offs and easy implementation. The above parameters are used to compute values l , l_1 , and l_2 , let $l = l_1 + l_2$.
- The WOTS+ algorithm uses a keyed cryptographic hash function F_k . F_k accepts and returns byte strings of length n using keys of length n .
- Using F , we define the following chaining function that takes the bitmask r and evaluates F_k a follows:

$c_k^i(x, r^{\rightarrow})$: On input of value $x \in \{0, 1\}^n$, iteration counter $i \in \mathbb{N}$, key $k \in K$ and randomization elements $r^{\rightarrow} = (r_1, \dots, r_j) \in \{0, 1\}^{n \times j}$ with $j > i$. The chaining function works the following way. In case $i = 0$, c returns x . For $i > 0$ we define c recursively as:

$$c_k^i(x, r^{\rightarrow}) : F_k(c_k^{i-1}(x, r^{\rightarrow}) \oplus r_i)$$

The secret key $sk = (sk_1, \dots, sk_l)$ consists of l random bit strings. The remaining $w - 1$ bit strings are used as the randomization elements $r = (r_1, \dots, r_{w-1})$ for c .

$$PK = pk_1, \dots, pk_l = ((r^{\rightarrow}, k), c_k^{w-1}(sk_1, r^{\rightarrow}), \dots, c_k^{w-1}(sk_l, r^{\rightarrow}))$$

5.3 A single Attestation with Dynamic Attributes

Whenever the low-end device wants to join, the DM requests the manufacturer to enrol it by sending a set of challenges ch_i and the device identity ID. Note that the manufacturer has access to the PUF's key. Suppose we define four attributes for the low-end devices known to the external verifiers. For example, the attributes a_1 , a_2 , a_3 , and a_4 can correspond to secure boot, Key restriction user policy, authenticated tracer, and certified TCB, respectively.

The manufacturer calculates one-time attribute keys using a KDF that takes the PUF response R_i corresponding to a challenge ch_i as inputs, together with the golden value of the attributes. For instance, the

Figure 5.1: Construction of the Attribute Tree TREE_i for a Challenge ch_i

secure boot attribute key corresponding to the challenge ch_i is $ak_1^i = KDF(R_i, \text{golden value of } a_1)$. To construct the Merkle attribute tree TREE_i as in the Figure 6.3, the manufacturer calculates the hash of the one-time attribute keys ak_1^i, ak_2^i, ak_3^i and ak_4^i that correspond to the leaf nodes of the tree and calculates the upper nodes to reach to the top node AK_i that is the master one-time attribute key of the challenge ch_i. We need each attribute key mapped to a specific domain, with no different attribute keys sharing the same domain. Therefore, given an attribute key-value pair, the verifier should be able to identify which attribute is being attested.

Enrollment: The manufacturer then creates the one-time public keys corresponding to challenges ch_i, namely PK_{OTS}^i as follows:

$$PK_{OTS}^i = KDF(AK_i)$$

where AK_i is the master attribute key corresponding to TREE_i, sends the challenges together with the corresponding PK_{OTS}^i and attribute trees TREE_i to the DM. The DM manager proceeds as before (see Figure 5.2), issuing the Merkle tree by hashing the PK_{OTS}^i to reach mpk. The DM then publishes mpk, ch_i and sends the Merkle tree and the attribute trees TREE_i to the Low-end device.

Attestation: Upon receiving a challenge ch_i and the attribute to be attested (say, secure boot) from an external verifier, PUF internally creates the response R_i. Using R_i, PUF computes the attribute key corresponding to the secure boot leaf node, i.e. $ak_1^i = KDF(R_i, \text{current boot value})$. Using

Figure 5.2: mpk issuance

Figure 5.3: A single device authentication with a challenge input ch_2 out of eight challenges

the attribute tree $TREE_i$, the Low-end device calculates the attribute authentication AA path, as shown in Figure 6.3 (Key restriction user policy node value and a_{34}). The Low-end device then calculates $PK_{OTS}^i = KDF(AK_i)$, and creates $auth_i$ as in Figure 5.3 and a one-time signature σ_i . Finally, the signature is $(\sigma_i, ak_i^1, auth_i, AA)$ to the verifier.

Verification: The verifier checks that ak_i^1 belongs to the secure boot domain and verifies the one-time signature σ_i under ak_i^1 . If the check passes, then it hashes ak_i^1 , and using AA, it calculates the top node of $TREE_i$, namely AK_i^1 . Using AK_i^1 , the verifier calculates $PK_{OTS}^i = KDF(AK_i^1)$, hashes PK_{OTS}^i and verifies $auth_i$ to reach mpk' . The verification passes if $mpk' = mpk$.

5.4 ENTRUST Dynamic Swarm Attestation with Attributes and Verifier Authentication

Swarm attestation schemes aim to provide scalable attestation solutions that verify the trustworthiness of a large-scale network more efficiently than individually attesting devices, as shown in Figure 5.4. This is crucial for complex medical domains like those envisioned in ENTRUST, where the focus is on creating trust-aware medical service-graph chains comprising heterogeneous CMDs with different hardware

Figure 5.4: Swarm Attestation in the context of ENTRUST

capabilities, TCBs, and disparate software configurations. However, the ultimate goal is not merely to reduce communication overhead compared to the naive approach of repeatedly applying single Prover attestation. It also enables attestation intelligence, which determines the sets of devices that need to be attested collectively during runtime. This may depend on the safety-critical nature and time-sensitivity of the functions and services running in such swarms, which in turn may require different types of assurance claims. This, in turn, may affect the timing of attestation tasks based on available resources in a non-intrusive manner, thereby avoiding harm to the overall execution profile of the device. We now propose a swarm attestation scheme that the Entrust low-end devices can adopt:

5.4.1 Setup Phase

Assuming the successful enrollment of a high-end CMD to the medical domain, the Domain Manager can allocate low-end devices as its children. The DM generates $N = 2^n$ challenges, ch_1, \dots, ch_N . The DM sends the challenges to the manufacturer, along with the possible mother high-end device IDs and all possible attributes to be attested.

- One-time attribute keys:** Suppose we define P attributes for the low-end devices known to the external verifiers. Let the attributes a_1, \dots, a_p for $p \in [1, P]$ be the attributes to be certified. For example, the attributes a_1, a_2, a_3 , and a_4 can correspond to the secure boot, Key restriction user policy, authenticated tracer, and certified TCB of the k^{th} PUF, respectively. The manufacturer calculates one-time attribute keys using a KDF that takes the k^{th} PUF response R_i^k corresponding to a challenge ch_i as inputs, together with the golden values of the attributes. For instance, the secure boot attribute key corresponding to the challenge ch_i is $ak_i^{k,1} = \text{KDF}(R_i^k, \text{golden value of } a_1)$. To generalize, the p^{th} attribute key for the k^{th} PUF and a challenge ch_i is denoted by: $ak_i^{k,p} = \text{KDF}(R_i^k, \text{golden value of } a_p)$ for all $p \in [1, P]$, where P denote the total number of attributes.
- Attribute Tree:** To construct the k^{th} Merkle attribute tree TREE_i^k , the manufacturer calculates the hash of the one-time attribute keys $ak_i^{k,1}, ak_i^{k,2}, ak_i^{k,3}$ and $ak_i^{k,4}$ that correspond to the leaf nodes of the tree and calculates the upper nodes to reach to the top node AK_i^k that is the master one-time attribute key of the K^{th} PUF corresponding to the challenge ch_i as in the example in Figure 6.3.

We need each attribute key mapped to a specific domain, with no different attribute keys sharing the same domain. Therefore, given an attribute key-value pair, the verifier should be able to identify which attribute is being attested.

- **Low-end one time public keys:** For each challenge ch_i , the manufacturer creates the k^{th} low-end device's private key R_i^k using a key derivation function (KDF) with knowledge of the k^{th} PUF root key and the root node of the attribute tree $TREE_i^k$, namely AK_i^k . With input R_i^k and AK_i^k , the OTS-KEYGEN algorithm generates the corresponding one-time public key PK_i^k for the k^{th} low-end device.
- **Swarm one time public keys:** The manufacturer then concatenates PK_i^k for $k \in [1, K]$ to obtain the one-time public key of the connected low-end devices in the swarm for a challenge ch_i , i.e., $PK_i = (PK_i^1 || \dots || PK_i^K)$, where K is the total number of low-end devices in the Swarm as in Figure 5.5
- **Authentication key for High-end:** The manufacturer calculates for each possible high-end j , $\gamma_i^{kj} = \text{KDF}(R_i^k | ID_j)$.
- The manufacturer then sends the PK_i corresponding to the challenges ch_i for all $i \in [1, N]$ and γ_i^{kj} to the DM together with individual attribute trees $TREE_i^k$.
- The DM creates the Merkle tree using the following steps:
 - ✓ For each $i \in [1, N]$, the DM calculates $h_i = H(PK_i)$
 - ✓ The hash values h_i are placed as leaves and hashed recursively to form a binary tree as follows: Let $a_{i,j}$ denote the node in the tree with height j , and left-right position i . The hash values $h_i = a_{i,1}$ are the leaf nodes. where $j = 1, \dots, d$, where d denotes the height of the tree.
 - ✓ The DM publishes mpk together with the challenges $\{ch_i\}$ and a proof of construction π_{mpk} of mpk.
 - ✓ The DM sends the Merkle tree together with γ_i^{kj} to each possible mother high-end j in the swarm over a **secure authenticated channel**.
 - ✓ The DM sends $TREE_i^k$ with the corresponding challenges ch_i to the k^{th} low-end device.

5.4.2 Attestation & Report Phase

- The external verifier that wants to attest the Swarm sends a challenge ch_i that has not been used before to the high-end device.
 - The high-end device j , with identity ID_j , retrieves γ_i^{kj} from its records and forwards ch_i with the corresponding γ_i^{kj} to every low-end device child k .
 - The k^{th} PUF embedded in the low-end device k outputs the response R_i^k for the challenge ch_i and checks $\gamma_i^{kj} = \text{KDF}(R_i^k | ID_j)$ is valid.
 - Upon receiving a challenge ch_i and the attribute to be attested (say, secure boot as an example) from an external verifier, PUF internally creates the response R_i^k . Using R_i^k , PUF computes the attribute key corresponding to the secure boot leaf node, i.e., $ak_i^{k,p} = \text{KDF}(R_i^k, \text{current boot value})$
- (In general, for any attribute p to be attested,

$$ak_i^{k,p} = \text{KDF}(R_i^k, \text{current } p^{\text{th}} \text{ attribute value})$$

Consider a Swarm of four low-end devices. $D_1, D_2, D_3,$ and D_4 . Each $PK_{\{i\}} = PK_i^{D1} || PK_i^{D2} || PK_i^{D3} || PK_i^{D4}$ for a Challenge ch_i
 A successful attestation is achieved if every PK_i is well constructed.

Figure 5.5: A swarm authentication with four challenge inputs and four devices

Using the attribute tree $TREE_i^k$, the k^{th} Low-end device calculates the attribute authentication AA path, as shown in Figure 6.3 (For attribute 1, this would be the Key restriction user policy node value and a34).

- The low-end device signs the challenge using the corresponding secret key R_i^k , resulting in a one-time signature σ_i^k .
- Each low-end device sends its $(ak_i^{k,p}, \sigma_i^k)$ to the mother high-end device j that initiated the attestation.
- After receiving the outputs of all its K children low-end devices, the high-end device verifies each σ_i^k under $ak_i^{k,p}$ for $k \in [1, K]$. If any verification fails, the high-end aborts.
- If the check passes, then it hashes $ak_i^{k,p}$, and using AA, it calculates the top node of $TREE_i^k$, namely AK_i^k . Using AK_i^k , the high-end calculates $PK_i^k = KDF(AK_i^k)$.
- The high-end calculates the OTS public key $PK_i' = (PK_i^1 | \dots | PK_i^K)$, then sends $(PK_i', Auth_i)$, where $Auth_i$ is the authentication path of the swarm Merkle tree, to the external verifier.

5.4.3 Verification Phase

- Note that this ch_i is only allowed to be used once, which prevents replay attacks. The verifier, with knowledge of mpk , verifies the authentication path $Auth_i$. If this path leads to the same mpk , the verifier accepts; otherwise, it rejects. The verification steps work as follows:
- The Verifier computes $h_i' = H(PK_i')$.
- Using the authentication path $Auth_i$ computes the root of the Merkle tree mpk' .

- If $mpk = mpk'$, the verifier declares the signature as valid; otherwise, it rejects it.
- Note that the signature is only verified correctly if $PK'_i = PK_i$ that was set by the manufacturer, i.e. each PK_i^k matches the device's PK_i^k set by the device manufacturer in the MUD profile. Upon successful verification, the verifier is convinced that each low-end device satisfies the attested attribute matches the golden value without knowing the exact current attribute value. This provides Attribute Confidentiality.
- If the verification and the revocation check pass, then the verifier outputs 1; otherwise, 0.

A high-level description of the protocol's sequence of actions is described in Figure 5.6.

Figure 5.6: Swarm Attestation Sequence Diagram

5.5 Swarm Attestation Security Properties

Table 5.1 defines the key security and privacy properties associated with ENTRUST’s Swarm Attestation scheme. These properties are crucial for ensuring the integrity, confidentiality, and overall trustworthiness of the IoT devices involved. Section 5.5.1 introduces a comprehensive security model that captures the identified security properties within the Universal Composable (UC) framework. The UC framework is well-regarded for its ability to provide strong security guarantees in a modular way, allowing for the combination of different cryptographic protocols while maintaining security. The identified security properties will be proved through a series of games. Each game will represent a different scenario or challenge that the scheme must withstand, ultimately proving that the ENTRUST Swarm Attestation scheme meets the outlined security specifications.

Swarm Attestations Security Requirement	Description
Swarm.SC.1 - Unforgeability	It is computationally infeasible to produce (attestations) message signature pairs $(M;\sigma)$ that are accepted by the verification algorithm without knowledge of the PUF’s secret identity key. The unforgeability of the proposed swarm attestations protocol is built on the Unforgeability of the WOTS+. This property can be achieved only if the manufacturer is honest.
Swarm.SC.2 - Anonymity	Our swarm attestation protocol supports complete privacy against external Verifiers that might be honest but curious to de-anonymise all devices even if they are in a correct state (no failed attestation). The privacy of the IoT devices is only achieved against external Verifiers. In our proposed SA protocol, IoT Devices generate fully random responses to an identified challenge, resulting in an entirely random PK' , that doesn’t reveal the IoT Devices’ identities. Thus, starting with a swarm signature, an external Verifier cannot tell the identity of the IoT Devices that generated this signature unless it collaborates with the high-end Device.
Swarm.SC.3 - Traceability	Recall that the requirement is that a swarm signature should be traceable to the swarm member who issued it, in case of a failed attestation report. Whenever an IoT Device generates a signature, the parent high-end Device will be able to trace back the identity of the IoT Device, relying on its records that list each IoT Device’s shared authentication key γ^{kj} .
Swarm.SC.4 - Data Integrity and Authenticity Guarantees	The Swarm attestation result should reflect the claimed (system) integrity measurement extracted for the underlying attestation task. This requirement is fulfilled by the offering of Hash Functions to be able to guarantee the integrity of the data, to allow the different data sources to be authenticated, and provide the necessary guarantees to the other entities which are required to perform the different activities foreseen over the ENTRUST infrastructure. In our swarm attestation, the integrity measurement during the attestation is preserved using a collision-resistant one-way hash function H for creating signatures for IoT and high-end devices.
Swarm.SC.5 - User Revocation	Our swarm protocol supports revocation of the IoT Devices by their parent high-end Device. We assume that the high-end Device will have access to a set of IoT revoked keys called the Key Revocation List (KRL). The high-end Device checks that each of its children’s IoT signatures was not produced by any key in KRL . Relying on the trustworthiness of high-end Devices and the accuracy of the updated KRL , high-end Devices would also be able to revoke IoT Devices whose keys are correctly stored in KRL .
Swarm.SC.6 - Attribute Disclosure	A verifier can verify a Swarm Attestation and ensure that the IoT device has the required correct attribute values that are required to be attested, however, the verifier learns nothing about the attribute current attribute values of the device. This property is achieved by the one-way property of the Key Derivation Function (KDF) used by the manufacturer in the setup to calculate the one-time attestation keys.

<p>Swarm.SC.7-SC.8 Correctness & Linkability</p>	<p>It ensures that honestly generated signatures are always valid and that honest users are not sharing the same secret keys responses for the same challenges.</p>
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Table 5.1: High-level Security Analysis of the swarm attestations Scheme

5.5.1 Security Model

We employ the Universal Composability (UC) model, based on which we aim to equate the real-world network topology to an ideal-world model, both of which are indistinguishable to an adversary. This enables us to break down the proposed scheme into simpler building blocks with provable security. Specifically, the security definition of our swarm attestation protocol is given in terms of an ideal functionality F . This is depicted in Figure 5.7, for a swarm of three edges and four IoT devices. However, the UC model can be generalised to any dynamic network topology and swarm size. In UC, an environment E should not be able to distinguish, with a non-negligible probability, between the two worlds:

Figure 5.7: UC security model: the Real and the Ideal world executions are indistinguishable to the environment E .

1. The real world, where each party E_j or D_k (corresponding to the Edge and IoT devices, respectively) executes its assigned part of protocol Π . The network is controlled by an adversary A that communicates with the environment E .
2. The ideal world, in which all parties forward their inputs to a trusted entity, called the ideal functionality F , which internally performs all the required tasks and creates the parties' outputs in the presence of a simulator \S . This essentially translates to the Edge and IoT devices sending their outputs to F , which is then able to perform all operations in a trustworthy manner and provide the compiled output.

We prove the security properties in Table 5.1 of our protocol by demonstrating that an adversary cannot gain any significant advantage when monitoring the operations and interacting tasks that take place in the real world; i.e., been indistinguishable from the case where the protocol internal phases are executed in the ideal world. More specifically, the security of our swarm attestation protocol Π is captured by the fact that every attack A mounted in the real world, \S carries out in the ideal world. Protocol security is implied, since in the ideal world, such attacks cannot be mounted. We have then that the output E retrieved from the execution of Π in the ideal world and \S and the execution of Π with the real-world entities and A are indistinguishably distributed.

Another key point of UC, which reduces the computational complexity of the specified protocol, is the composition theorem. It guarantees composition with arbitrary sets of parties and executed computational tasks. This ensures that UC-security proofs, for any subroutine of F , are also transferred to the security model of the entire protocol Π . In our case, we separate the analysis by the protocol's phases, as well as the internal cryptographic tasks that will be executed, as explained in Section 5.5.2.

5.5.2 Interfaces of Ideal Functionality F

We now explain the interfaces of our proposed Swarm Attestation ideal functionality F in the UC framework based on the functionality originally proposed in [19] with minor modifications to fit our security requirements. The UC framework allows us to focus the analysis on a single protocol instance with a globally unique session identifier sid . F uses session identifiers of the form $sid = (I, sid')$ for some issuer I and a unique string sid' . In the real world, these strings are mapped to the DM's public key, and all parties use the sid to link their stored key material to the particular issuer. We define the JOIN and SIGN sub-session identifiers $jsid$ and $ssid$, respectively, to distinguish several join and sign sessions that might run in parallel.

We define two "macros" to determine whether a secret key key is consistent with the internal functionality records or not. This is checked at several places in the ideal functionality interfaces and also depends on whether key belongs to an honest or corrupt party. The first macro $checkkeyhonest$ is used when the functionality stores a new key that belongs to an honest party, and checks that none of the existing valid signatures are identified as belonging to this party. The second macro $checkkeycorrupt$ is used when storing a new key that belongs to a corrupt party, and checks that the new key does not break the identifiability of signatures, i.e., it checks that there is no other known key^* , unequal to key , such that both keys are identified as the owner of a signature. Both functions output a bit b , where $b = 1$ indicates that the new key is consistent with the stored information, whereas $b = 0$ signals an invalid key.

SETUP

1. On input (SETUP, sid) from issuer I (DM), output (SETUP, sid) to S .
2. On input the real-protocol algorithms (ALG, sid , Sign, Verify, Identify, Kgen) from S ,
 - Check that Verify and Identify are deterministic.
 - Store the algorithms and output (SETUPDONE, sid) to I .

JOIN

1. On input (JOIN, sid , $jsid$, D_k) from IoT device D_k , create a join session record $\langle jsid, D_k, E_j \rangle$, where E_j is the mother device, and output (PROCEEDJOIN, sid , $jsid$, D_k) to I .
2. On input (PROCEEDJOIN, sid , $jsid$, ch_i) from I , output (JOINCOMPLETE, sid , $jsid$, ch_i) to S .
3. For all $k \in [1, K]$ and $i \in [1, L]$, where L denotes the number of challenges to be certified, on input (JOINCOMPLETE, sid , $jsid$, (dsk_i^k, ch_i)) from S .
 - Abort if I or D_k is honest and a record $\langle D_k, *, * \rangle \in IoTmemberslist$ already exists.
 - If D_k is honest, set $dsk_i^k \leftarrow \perp$.
 - Else, verify that the provided dsk_i^k is eligible by checking
 - ✓ $checkkeyhonest(dsk_i^k) = 1$ if D_k is honest, or

- ✓ $\text{checkkeycorrupt}(\text{dsk}_i^k) = 1$ if D_k is corrupt.
- For each attribute p , if D_i has been granted the attribute p , then S output $\langle D_k, (\text{dsk}_i^k, \text{ak}_i^{k,p}, \text{ch}_i) \rangle$, into IoTmemberslist and output $(\text{JOINED}, \text{sid}, \text{jsid}, D_k, E_j, \text{mpk})$ to I , else S output $\langle D_k, (\text{dsk}_i^k, \perp, \text{ch}_i), \text{mpk} \rangle$,

SIGN

1. For all $k \in [1, K]$, where K is the number of children for an IoT mother device E_j . On input $(\text{SIGN}, \text{sid}, \text{ssid}, \text{ch}_i)$ from D_k . If E_j is honest and no entry $\langle D_k, E_j, * \rangle$ in IoTmemberslist , abort. Else, create a sign session record $\langle \text{ssid}, D_k, \text{ch}_i \rangle$ and output $(\text{PROCEEDSIGN}, \text{sid}, \text{ssid}, \text{ch}_i)$ to D_k .
2. On input $(\text{PROCEEDSIGN}, \text{sid}, \text{ssid}, \text{ch}_i)$ for some $i \in [1, L]$ from each D_k where $k \in [1, K]$. Output $(\text{SIGNCOMPLETE}, \text{sid}, \text{ssid}, \text{ch}_i)$ to S .
3. On input $(\text{SIGNCOMPLETE}, \text{sid}, \text{ssid}, \sigma_i^k, \text{ak}_i^{k,p}, \text{ch}_i)$ from S .
 - If the device doesn't have the attribute, then output $(\text{SIGNCOMPLETE}, \text{sid}, \text{ssid}, \sigma_i^k, \perp, \text{ch}_i)$. else,
 - For each $k \in [1, K]$, if D_k is honest, retrieve the corresponding dsk_i^k :
 - ✓ Check $\text{checkkeyhonest}(\text{dsk}_i^k) = 1$ and store $\langle D_k, \text{dsk}_i^k \rangle$ in IoTdomainkeylist
 - ✓ Compute signature as $(\sigma_i^k, \text{AA}) \leftarrow \text{sig}_{\text{IoT}}(\text{dsk}_i^k, \text{ch}_i, \text{ak}_i^{k,p})$ and check $\text{ver}_{\text{IoT}}(\text{dsk}_i^k, \text{ch}_i, \text{ak}_i^{k,p}) = 1$, where sig_{IoT} and ver_{IoT} are taken from the real protocol sign and verify interfaces with the only difference that ver_{IoT} doesn't perform revocation checks.
 - ✓ Check $\text{identify}_{\text{IoT}}(\sigma_i^k, \text{ak}_i^{k,p}, \text{ch}_i, \text{dsk}_i^k) = 1$ and check that there is no $D' \neq D_k$ with key dsk' registered in IoTmemberslist or IoTdomainkeylist with $\text{identify}_{\text{IoT}}(\sigma_i^k, \text{ak}_i^{k,p}, \text{ch}_i, \text{dsk}') = 1$.
 - Store $\langle \sigma_i^k, \text{ak}_i^{k,p}, \text{ch}_i, D_k \rangle$ in IoTsignedlist .
 - Output $(\text{SIGNATURE}, \text{sid}, \text{ssid}, \sigma_i^k, \text{ak}_i^{k,p}, \text{AA})$ to E_j .

VERIFY: On input $(\text{VERIFY}, \text{sid}, \text{ch}_i, \sigma_k^i, \text{IoT KRL})$ from some party V .

- Retrieve all pairs (dsk, D_k) from IoTmemberslist and $\langle D_k, *, \text{dsk}_i^k, \rangle \in \text{IoTdomainkeylist}$ where $\text{identify}_{\text{IoT}}(\sigma_k^i, \text{ch}_i, \text{dsk}_i^k, \text{ak}_i^{k,p}) = 1$. Set $f = 0$ if at least one of the following conditions holds:

CHECK1. More than one key dsk_i^k was found.

CHECK2. If the parent edge E_j is honest and no pair (dsk_i^k, D_k) was found.

CHECK3. There is an honest D_k but no entry $\langle *, \text{ch}_i, D_k \rangle \in \text{IoTsignedlist}$ exists.

CHECK4. There is a $\text{dsk}^* \in \text{IoT KRL}$ where $\text{identify}_{\text{IoT}}(\sigma_k^i, \text{ak}_i^{k,p}, \text{ch}_i, \text{dsk}^*) = 1$ and no pair (dsk_i^k, D_k) for an honest D_k was found.

- If $f \neq 0$, set $f = \text{ver}_{\text{IoT}}(\sigma_k^i, \text{ch}_i)$.
- Add $\langle \sigma_k^i, \text{ak}_i^{k,p}, \text{ch}_i, \text{IoT KRL}, f \rangle$ to $\text{IoTverificationlist}$, output $(\text{VERIFIED}, \text{sid}, f)$ to V .

5.6 Security Proof

5.6.1 High level description of our proof

In order to prove the security of our protocol as defined above, we present a sequence of games to show that there exists no environment E that can distinguish the real world protocol denoted by Π with an adversary A , from the ideal world F with a simulator S .

We start with the real-world protocol execution in Game 1. In the next game, we construct one entity C that runs the real-world protocol for all honest parties. Then we split C into two pieces: an ideal functionality F and a simulator \mathcal{S} that simulates the real-world parties. Initially, we start with an “empty” functionality F . With each game, we gradually change F and update \mathcal{S} accordingly, moving from the real world to the ideal world, and culminating to the full F being realised as part of the ideal world, thus, proving our proposed security model presented in Section 5.5.2. The ultimate goal of our proof is to demonstrate the indistinguishability between Game 1 and Game 14, i.e., between the complete real world and the fully functional ideal world. This is achieved by demonstrating that each game is indistinguishable from the previous one, starting with Game 1 and progressing to Game 15. Each of these games contains additional checks that ensure a desired security requirement, while also proving game-to-game indistinguishability. At the end of the proof, we showcase that our real protocol guarantees the desired security requirements that the ideal world provides.

Proof. **Game 1 (SWARM Real World):** This is the real world protocol.

Game 2 (Transition to the Ideal World): An entity C is introduced. C receives all inputs from the honest parties and simulates the real-world protocol for them. This is equivalent to Game 1, as this change is invisible to E .

Game 3 (Transition to the Ideal World with Different Structure): We now split C into two parts, F and S , where F behaves as an ideal functionality. It receives all the inputs and forwards them to S , which simulates the real world protocol for honest parties and sends the outputs to F . F then forwards these outputs to E . This game is essentially equivalent to Game 2 with a different structure.

Game 4 (F handles the setup): F now behaves differently in the setup interface, as it stores the real-world protocol algorithms. F also performs checks and ensures that the structure of sid , which represents the issuer’s unique session identifier defined in 5.5.2, is correct for an honest I , and aborts if not. When I is honest, \mathcal{S} will start simulating it. Since \mathcal{S} is now running the Issuer, it knows its secret key. In case I is corrupt, S extracts I ’s secret key from π_{ipk} and proceeds to the setup interface on behalf of I . By the simulation soundness of π_{mpk} , this game transition is indistinguishable for the adversary (Game 4 \approx Game 3).

Game 5 (F handles the verification and linking): F now performs the verification and linking checks instead of forwarding them to S . There are no protocol messages, and the outputs are identical to those in the real-world protocol. However, the only difference is that the verification algorithms that F doesn’t perform revocation checks, so knowing KRL for corrupt IoTs, F can perform these checks separately, and the outcomes are equal (Game 5 \approx Game 4).

Game 6 (F handles the join): The join interface of F is now changed. Specifically, F stores the members that joined in its records. If I is honest, then F stores the secret keys dsk_i^k extracted from π_i^k by S for corrupt IoT devices, respectively. Only in the case where the IoT device is already registered in $IoTmemberslist$, F will abort the protocol. However, I and the parent edge device E_j have already tested this case before continuing with the query JOINPROCEED, thus, F will not abort. Knowing E_j and all children dsk_i^k , F will proceed with adding the children IoT devices into $IoTmemberslist$ after checking that the IoT device is not registered before in $IoTmemberslist$. Therefore, F and S can interact to simulate the real-world protocol in all cases. Due to the simulation soundness of π_i^k , Game 6 \approx Game 5.

Game 7 (F further handles the join): If I is honest, then F only allows the devices that joined to sign. An honest edge device will always check whether it joined with an IoT in the real-world protocol, so there is no difference for honest edge devices. Therefore, $\text{Game 7} \approx \text{Game 6}$.

Game 8 (F handles the sign/ SC.2: Anonymity) (Simulating an IoT device without knowing its secret): In this game, F creates anonymous signatures for honest IoT devices by running the algorithms defined in the setup interface. Anonymity of the IoT devices is also achieved against external Verifiers through the use of *fully random pseudonyms* that don't reveal the identities of the IoT devices. Thus, starting with an IoT pseudonym, V cannot tell the identity of the IoT device that generated this pseudonym unless it collaborates with the edge device. It is easy to see that an external environment cannot distinguish between an honest IoT signature from a signature, by the same party, but with a randomly chosen fresh dsk_i^k in every signature ($\text{Game 8} \approx \text{Game 7}$, except for a negligible probability).

Game 9 (SC.3: Traceability): When storing a new dsk_i^k , F checks if $\text{CheckkeyHonest} = 1$ or $\text{CheckkeyCorrupt} = 1$ for both keys. If the device is corrupt, F checks that $\text{CheckkeyCorrupt} = 1$ for the keys dsk_i^k that the simulator extracted. This check prevents the adversary from choosing different keys. There exists only a single dsk_i^k for every valid signature where $\text{identify}_{\text{IoT}}(\sigma_k^i, \text{ch}_i, \text{dsk}_k^i) = 1$ for each IoT device, respectively, thus this check will never fail. For keys of honest devices, F verifies that $\text{CheckkeyHonest} = 1$ whenever it receives or generates a new key. With these checks, we avoid the registration of keys for which matching signatures already exist. Since keys for honest devices are chosen uniformly from an exponentially large group and every signature has exactly one matching key, the chance that a signature under that key already exists is negligible ($\text{Game 9} \approx \text{Game 8}$).

Game 10 (SC.7: Correctness): In this game, F checks that honestly generated signatures are always valid. This is true, since the sign_{IoT} algorithms always produce signatures passing through verification checks. Also, they satisfy $\text{identify}_{\text{IoT}}(\text{dsk}_i^k, \sigma_k^i, \text{ch}_i) = 1$. F ensures, by using its internal records MemberList and DomainKeys , that honest users are not sharing the same secret keys dsk_i^k for each challenge ch_i ; this is reduced with non-negligible probability to breaking the collision resistance problem of the hash function ($\text{Game 10} \approx \text{Game 9}$).

Game 12 (SC.1: Unforgeability): CHECK3 is added to F to prevent anyone from forging signatures by using honest dsk_i^k and their credentials. If the issuer is honest, CHECK2 prevents signing with join credentials that were not issued by the issuer. The unforgeability of our protocol is based on the unforgeability of the WOTS+ [7] and the Merkle signatures [1].

Game 13 (SC.5: Revocation) CHECK4 is added to F . This ensures that honest devices are not being revoked. If an honest device is simulated, when a matching key in the revocation list is found, it must be the secret key of the target instance. This is again equivalent to breaking the one-wayness of the hash functions ($\text{Game 13} \approx \text{Game 12}$).

Game 14 (SC.4-SC.6: Attribute Disclosure): In case the device doesn't have the required attribute p , F will replace the provided $\text{ak}_i^{k,p}$ by \perp that corresponds to any input not equals to $\text{ak}_i^{k,p}$. If the IoT device doesn't have the required correct attribute values that need to be attested, the verifier cannot correctly verify the signature or learn anything about the current attribute value of the device. This property is achieved by the one-way property of the Key Derivation Function (KDF) used by the manufacturer in the setup to calculate the one-time attestation keys ($\text{Game 14} \approx \text{Game 13}$).

Game 15 (SC.8: Linkability): All the remaining checks of the ideal functionality F that are related to link queries are now included. A generated one-time key dsk_i^k only matches one signature and no other signature. Game 15 is indistinguishable from Game 16, and F now includes all the functionalities of F . This concludes the proof.

□

5.7 Complexity Analysis for our Swarm Attestation

In this section, we analyse the time complexity of each phase of our Swarm Attestation protocol. We structure our analysis into two parts: attribute-related complexity and Swarm-related complexity, corresponding to operations involving attribute verification and Swarm-wide coordination, respectively. Finally, we instantiate our scheme with concrete parameters and provide a detailed comparison with existing aggregate signature schemes to highlight the efficiency and scalability of our approach.

5.7.1 Attribute Trees

- Let P be the number of attributes. The complexity for constructing each attribute tree is $O(P)$. This is required to compute the hashes for each leaf node value, and $O(\log P)$ for computing the hashes up the tree to $AK_{\mathcal{I}}^k$. Overall, the complexity of key generation is $O(P)$ for each IoT device. Generating the WOTS+ keys has a complexity of $O(lw)$, where the parameters w and l are defined in Section 5.2.
- Signing: The signer then constructs the signature, which includes the WOTS+ signature and the authentication path (the sequence of hashes from the leaf to the root). Each WOTS+ signature requires a complexity of $O(lw)$. For a swarm of K IoT devices, the complexity is $O(Klw)$. Retrieving each authentication path requires $O(\log P)$ for each device.
- Verification: The verifier receives the signature (WOTS+) and the authentication path. The high-end device verifies K WOTS+ with complexity $O(Klw)$ and calculates the root $AK_{\mathcal{I}}^k$ using the authentication path with complexity $O(K \log P)$.

5.7.2 Swarm Merkle Tree

- Let n be the number of challenges. The complexity of constructing the tree is $O(n)$ to compute the hashes for each leaf node value, and $O(\log n)$ for computing the hashes up the tree to the root. Overall, the complexity of key generation is $O(n)$.
- Signing: The High-end device includes the input leaf public key (calculated by concatenating the IoT public keys) and the authentication path (the sequence of hashes from the leaf to the root). Calculating and concatenating the public keys requires $O(1)$. Retrieving the authentication path requires $O(\log n)$. Thus, the signing complexity is $O(\log n)$.
- Verification: The external verifier hashes the public key and checks it against the root hash using the authentication path. Hashing the input public key requires $O(1)$. Recomputing the hash from the leaf up to the root along the authentication path requires $O(\log n)$ hashes. Therefore, the verification complexity is also $O(\log n)$.

5.7.3 Comparison with other aggregatable schemes

To enable a fair comparison with other aggregatable signature schemes, we evaluate the signature size of our proposed scheme using the following parameters: four attributes, 1024 challenges, and 1000 IoT devices. For the underlying WOTS+ scheme, we use a Winternitz parameter of $w = 16$, resulting in each WOTS+ signature being 16, 480 B. The authentication path for each attribute contributes an additional 64 B (as the height of the attribute Merkle tree is 2), yielding a total signature size of 16, 544 B per device.

For a network of 1000 IoT devices, the cumulative signature size amounts to 16, 544, 000 B (16.544 MB). The Swarm authentication path, corresponding to 1024 challenges, contributes an additional $10 \times 32 = 320$ B —assuming each node is 32 B (256 bits). Hence, the total signature size for our Swarm signature of 1000 devices is approximately 16.5 MB. For our ENTRUST use cases, we usually deal with a smaller number of connected IoT devices. For example, in the Smart Ambulance use case, we have approximately 10 connected IoT devices, resulting in a signature size of around 165 KB.

Since WOTS+ signatures are inherently non-aggregable, the total signature size scales linearly with the number of devices. This is the case of Sphincs+ and Dilithium schemes in Table 5.2. Despite this, our scheme provides strong attribute privacy guarantees and supports heterogeneous attribute attestation, allowing each IoT device to be attested to a different attribute. To the best of our knowledge, this level of privacy and flexibility is not supported by existing Swarm or aggregable signature schemes.

Hash-based and lattice-based cryptographic approaches are among the most promising candidates for securing digital signatures in the post-quantum era. In contrast to traditional public-key cryptography, which is susceptible to quantum attacks, hash-based schemes derive their security from the preimage resistance of hash functions, ensuring resilience against quantum adversaries. Since our scheme is based on a hash-based construction, it inherits post-quantum security guarantees. Therefore, for comparison, we benchmark our approach against lattice-based post-quantum signature schemes, particularly CRYSTALS-Dilithium, which is among the most efficient and standardized options.

Table 5.2: Comparison of Aggregable schemes with 1000 IoT Signatures

Signature	Public Key Size	Aggregated Signature Size	Attribute Privacy	Post-Quantum Secure
BLS [4]	48B	96 B	No	No
MMSAT [13]	4.2 KB	36 KB	No	Yes
PRIVE' [18]	277 B	617 B	Yes	No
[29]	32 B	165 KB	No	Yes
Dilithium [16]	1.9 KB	3.2 MB	No	Yes
Sphincs+ [2]	32 B	7.8 MB	No	Yes
This Work	32 B	16.5 MB	Yes	Yes

Chapter 6

Exploration of Alternative Hardware-based RoTs: A Photonic-PUF Instance in the Context of ENTRUST

6.1 Introduction to Photonic Physical Unclonable Functions (p-PUFs)

The need for robust, hardware-based security primitives has intensified with the proliferation of interconnected devices, particularly within the IoT and embedded computing ecosystems. Traditional cryptographic key storage methods, which rely on non-volatile memory, have shown susceptibility to invasive, side-channel, and software-level attacks, leading to significant vulnerabilities in security-critical applications. In response to these threats, Physical Unclonable Functions (PUFs) have emerged as a promising class of security primitives that exploit intrinsic manufacturing variations to derive unique, instance-specific cryptographic features directly from the physical substrate of a device [39].

Among the diverse PUF modalities, p-PUFs, a subclass of non-silicon PUFs, utilize physical phenomena, such as light scattering through disordered media, to generate complex, unclonable challenge-response behavior, exploiting the rich complexity of light propagation and interference in such media [37]. P-PUFs have drawn growing interest as a non-electronic platform for secure identification, authentication, and cryptographic key generation [46]. They offer advantages like large information capacity and contact-free optical readout, making them attractive for applications such as anti-counterfeiting tags, secure hardware modules, and IoT device authentication [48]. Below an overview of the main types of photonic PUFs is provided along with their operating principles.

6.1.1 Overview of p-PUF Types

Photonic PUFs can be broadly classified into three principal categories based on their underlying operational mechanisms and physical architectures: **(i) interferometric**, which exploit the interference of coherent light within disordered media to generate unique speckle patterns; **(ii) resonant**, which utilize micro- or nano-scale optical resonators exhibiting device-specific spectral signatures; and **(iii) integrated**, which embed structural randomness within photonic circuits to enable scalable, chip-level implementations of PUF functionality. Below, a short description of the main p-PUF classes is provided.

- **Interferometric p-PUFs**: These type of p-PUFs rely on the complex interference of light in random or disordered structures to produce unique optical patterns. A classic example is the **speckle pattern** formed when coherent laser light scatters through a random medium [37]. In [37] authors

utilized a 3D scatterer and laser illumination to generate a unique speckle as a “fingerprint” of the object. Such interferometric PUFs can be implemented with free-space optical diffusers, surface roughness [30], or even single and multimode optical fibers [35], [15]. Their interference-based outputs have been used for one-time authentication codes and tamper-evident labels.

- **Resonant p-PUFs:** These PUFs exploit resonant optical modes in chaotic or disordered photonic structures. Light interacting with a microcavity or waveguide that contains fabrication-induced disorder will excite a complex set of resonance modes, yielding a distinctive spectral or temporal response. For instance, a chaotic silicon micro-ring resonator can imprint a unique transmission spectrum or waveform on an input pulse [26]. This unpredictable yet deterministic response serves as a fingerprint of the cavity, from which thousands of bits of cryptographic key can be extracted. Notably, attempts to fabricate identical resonant PUF structures result in measurably different outputs due to unavoidable nanoscale process variations, demonstrating physical unclonability. Such resonant p-PUFs have been proposed for secure communications (by encoding data in the random spectral key of a device) and for on-chip key storage that is resistant to cloning [46].
- **Integrated p-PUFs:** This category refers to PUF structures fabricated on photonic integrated circuits, leveraging CMOS-compatible processes [50]. They often incorporate intentional disorder (e.g. random phase variations, scattering sites, or a mesh of interferometer waveguides) into on-chip devices. Recent examples include disordered waveguide lattices and Mach–Zehnder interferometer networks [28] that generate unique broadband spectral responses. The appeal of integrated p-PUFs is their scalability and robustness: they can be mass-produced alongside microelectronic circuitry and read out via compact optoelectronic setups. Integrated photonic PUFs are being explored for securing the semiconductor supply chain (for example, as unique on-chip identifiers to prevent IC counterfeiting [48]) and can potentially augment electronic PUFs for higher security in hardware systems. Integration also helps mitigate alignment sensitivities by confining and routing light on-chip, enabling stable challenge-response behavior even under varying external conditions [46].

6.1.2 Advantages of p-PUFs

P-PUFs, encompassing both speckle-based and resonant architectures, offer a range of inherent advantages over traditional electronic PUFs, positioning them as promising candidates for robust authentication, anti-counterfeiting, and cryptographic key generation.

One of the most distinct characteristics of p-PUFs is their ability to generate high entropy responses to a given challenge, originating from the interaction of light with disordered or random optical structures. This interaction generates high-dimensional output patterns (e.g. speckles), where each grain or intensity feature behaves as an independent random variable. This results in **extremely high entropy**, enabling the extraction of long cryptographic keys or large sets of challenge-response pairs. For example, resonant silicon photonic PUFs have been shown to produce reliable binary keys exceeding 17 kilobits from a single microcavity device [26]. Such entropy far exceeds that of many electronic PUFs, providing a stronger security margin. The complexity also translates to resistance against brute-force attacks, since an attacker cannot feasibly search the exponential-sized space of possible optical responses [40].

By design, a PUF should be prohibitively difficult to duplicate, and p-PUFs exemplify this with their sub-microscopic randomness. Even if an adversary had the same fabrication process and materials, the exact stochastic pattern of defects or scatterers in a p-PUF cannot be reproduced [37]. Attempts to create a “copy” (for instance, fabricating an optical diffuser with the same specifications) result in a different speckle signature [35]. Furthermore, environmental perturbations that might normally degrade a device have minimal effect on unclonability, minor changes just alter the output rather than produce a predictable

fraudulent response. This **inherent unclonability** makes photonic PUFs appealing for anti-counterfeiting (e.g. unique optical labels on products or documents that are infeasible to forge).

As previously mentioned, p-PUFs leverage the analog nature of optics. Unlike many electronic PUFs that output a few digital bits and can sometimes be modeled as simple circuits, a p-PUF can produce a richly detailed analog pattern. The underlying physical mapping from challenge to response is typically a complex many-body interference process described by Maxwell’s equations with numerous random variables [35]. **This complexity is one-way**: it is easy to measure the output given the physical system, but extremely hard to infer the system’s internal configuration from the output. In practical terms, this means that even if an attacker obtains many challenge–response examples, mimicking the PUF’s internal structure or predicting potential upcoming responses is very difficult without some simplifying weakness. The continuous intensity values and high dimensionality also make machine-learning or model-building attacks less straightforward (the attacker must fit a very complicated function in a high-dimension space) [38], [34]. In summary, the analog complexity of p-PUFs contributes to their security by amplifying the effort required to analyze or reproduce their behavior.

Figure 6.1: Desired properties for the performance of an ideal PUF [26].

Once fabricated, a p-PUF’s **physical structure is typically stable over time** (assuming the materials are not sensitive to aging or light exposure). The responses are deterministic for given conditions, providing consistency across repeated queries [37]. This time-invariant behavior means the “keys” do not degrade with use and do not need refreshing or error-correction beyond normal tolerance for noise. Robustness can be enhanced by engineering the PUF or the readout to filter out environmental variations (e.g. using single-mode optics or reference normalization to handle illumination changes). As a result, photonic PUFs can be reliably re-used indefinitely for authentication as long as the physical token remains intact.

6.1.3 Challenges and Vulnerabilities of p-PUFs

Despite their considerable potential, p-PUFs, and in particular the interferometric implementations which are the main focal point in the context of ENTRUST, face several technical and security-related challenges that necessitate careful consideration and ongoing research.

One of the primary threats to so-called “strong” PUFs, characterized by their large challenge-response space, is the potential for **modeling attacks**. In the context of p-PUFs, especially those based on optical scattering, the speckle response is often the result of a deterministic linear transformation of the incident optical field. Under coherent illumination, this transformation can be approximated mathematically,

particularly when the physical configuration remains fixed. If attackers can query the PUF extensively (obtaining many speckle images for known challenges), they could attempt to build a mathematical model (or train a deep neural network) to predict responses for new challenges. Under this attack methodology, an adversary gains control of the raw PUF's responses and the corresponding challenges, and exploits these pairs so as to gain information about the transfer function of the system [41]. In the vast majority of optical PUFs, this vulnerability stems from the linearity of the scattering process. A notable example is the work by Rührmair [41], which demonstrated the feasibility (theoretically) of such an attack by training a machine learning model on simulated speckle data, effectively compromising the PUF's unpredictability. These vulnerabilities are amplified in systems with low noise and high repeatability, where the modeling becomes tractable. This challenge has spurred research into hardening p-PUFs: for example, introducing non-linear optical elements, time-varying components, or optical reconfiguration to increase complexity beyond what an attacker can feasibly learn [27], [9], [5]. It has to be noted that currently there are no records in the literature on successful ML attacks on actual speckle-based optical PUFs. Nonetheless, the risk remains that an advanced modeling attack could undermine a speckle PUF's security if it's not properly safeguarded (e.g., by limiting access to challenge-response pairs or adding additional unpredictability in the optical path).

A critical practical limitation of traditional p-PUFs (i.e. speckle imaging-based p-PUF instances) lies in their **sensitivity to optical alignment and environmental stability**. The accurate generation and measurement of the speckle pattern depend on precisely maintaining the relative positioning of optical elements, including the light source, scattering medium, and imaging sensor. Even minor deviations, such as sub-millimeter translations, slight angular misalignments, or fluctuations in temperature, can significantly alter the interference pattern, resulting in inconsistent responses across repeated measurements [46]. While this extreme sensitivity enhances unclonability by amplifying the influence of microscopic structural variations, it also introduces operational fragility. False rejections may occur if legitimate users are unable to reproduce the exact optical conditions under which the PUF was enrolled. Polarization state variations, ambient vibrations, or thermal expansion effects further contribute to measurement instability. Moreover, many systems require high-resolution imaging equipment to capture fine-grained speckle features, increasing the cost and complexity of deployment. These limitations hinder the portability and practical use of optical PUFs in real-world environments [38]. If an adversary is capable of subtly interfering with the alignment, (e.g. through physical perturbation of the setup) they may induce errors or exploit inconsistencies in the response to degrade reliability. In response, integrated photonic PUFs are being explored as a promising solution, wherein the disordered scattering structure and optical path are fabricated monolithically on a single photonic chip [5]. Although this approach dramatically reduces susceptibility to macroscopic misalignments and improves mechanical robustness, the construction of such a p-PUF instance dictates an extremely sophisticated and costly setup.

P-PUFs, like all hardware security primitives, are susceptible to systemic attacks such as **replay and readout spoofing**. In the case of a replay attack, an adversary may attempt to intercept and reproduce a valid challenge-response exchange in order to impersonate a legitimate device or token. Although the high-dimensional, analog nature of speckle patterns renders simple photographic reproduction infeasible, owing to the necessity of preserving the phase coherence of the optical field, more sophisticated attack vectors, such as holographic replay, remain conceivable. Moreover, when the output of the p-PUF is digitized and interfaced with an electronic verification system, the analog-to-digital boundary becomes a potential attack surface. Sensor spoofing, data injection, or interface manipulation could be employed to undermine authentication without physically compromising the optical token. As such, photonic PUF implementations must incorporate complementary security countermeasures, including dynamic challenge randomization, time-constrained response windows, and encrypted optical-to-digital conversion pipelines. These precautions are necessary to ensure that the overall system architecture maintains its security guarantees, even in the presence of a capable adversary with partial access to the authentication protocol.

6.1.4 State-of-the-Art Considerations for Enhancing the Security and Practicality of p-PUF Instances

In response to the challenges associated with p-PUFs and discussed in the previous section, particularly on those associated with speckle-based optical PUFs, the research community is actively investigating novel approaches aimed at improving both the security and deployability of these systems. A non-exhaustive description of the most prominent strategies are presented below

A significant line of inquiry involves the transition from traditional image-based readout techniques to non-imaging detection schemes. Conventional speckle-based p- PUFs rely on high-resolution imaging sensors to capture two-dimensional interference patterns. However, recent studies have demonstrated that this requirement can be circumvented by employing aggregate measurements of the optical response. For example, Wang et al.[49] introduced a single-pixel detection framework wherein the speckle field is not imaged directly; instead, fluctuations in total scattered intensity, measured utilizing a photodiode, are used to derive the PUF’s response characteristics. Despite the absence of spatial resolution, this method achieved authentication performance comparable to conventional imaging systems. Notably, the approach benefits from the ability to operate with speckle features finer than the Nyquist limit of digital sensors, since the analog intensity variations are still sensitive to sub-pixel-scale disorder. Consequently, this technique allows for increased optical complexity while simplifying the hardware footprint. Moreover, by denying the attacker access to full spatial data, non-imaging modalities enhance resistance to reverse engineering. Non-imaging detection and other analog encoding techniques (like interferometric summing of speckle or spectral filtering of the output) are thus promising for creating compact, robust p-PUF modules.

Figure 6.2: The experimental setup utilizing in [49]. A DMD creates challenges by randomly shaping the wavefront pattern of a He-Ne laser beam. After passing through the lens L1, iris and another lens L2, challenges are projected on the surface of the PUF in sequence. The scattered light in the far field of each challenge is detected by a single-pixel photon detector.

Another promising avenue in the advancement of p-PUFs lies in the utilization of multiple orthogonal optical properties to enhance both entropy and resilience against adversarial modeling. Traditional optical PUFs typically operate through a single output modality, such as monochromatic intensity imaging, which inherently limits the entropy per challenge. In contrast, multidimensionally-encoded optical PUFs aim to extract multiple, independently informative outputs from a single physical token, thereby significantly enlarging the effective challenge-response space, by generating unique signatures in multiple wavelengths (colors) of light, in polarization state, and in emission lifetime or phase, all at once. Recently, an all-silicon PUF was demonstrated [48], that combines a disordered silicon metasurface with embedded erbium (Er)-doped quantum dots (QDs), yielding five in-situ optical responses per challenge within one device. These included distinct photoluminescence (PL) peaks and scattering features, together providing an ultrahigh information entropy (up to 2.32 bits per pixel) – far higher than a single-channel optical tag. By

leveraging multiple dimensions (e.g. intensity at different wavelengths, different polarization components, etc.), the output space becomes exponentially larger, drastically reducing the chances of a false match or successful modelling. Multidimensional PUFs also make it harder for an adversary to clone or predict the response, since they would need to replicate several independent physical phenomena simultaneously (for example, both the random scattering and the exact spectral emission characteristics). Current research in this area spans using composite materials (quantum dots [10], fluorescent proteins [32], plasmonic nanoparticles [45], etc.) and nanostructured surfaces [47] to encode optical fingerprints that are highly unique yet still CMOS-fabrication-compatible. The essence of such an approach is to create PUF labels that can be easily read by a multi-modal optical scanner and provide a provably secure, unclonable signature for several applications.

Figure 6.3: The all-silicon multidimensionally-encoded optical PUF encryption features as demonstrated in [48]. **(a)** Illustration of the operational principle of the proposed photonic PUF system. **(a)** Schematic overview of the PUF operation. **(b, c)** Top-view optical microscopy images of the PUF captured at positions 1 and 2, respectively, with overlaid circles highlighting differences in the random micropatterns. **(d)** Photoluminescence (PL) spectra measured at six distinct positions, with PL peaks at 1540 nm magnified fivefold. **(e)** Statistical distribution of the PL emission wavelength from silicon quantum dots (Si QDs). **(f)** Demonstration of spatial variability in PL wavelength using 20 positions per sample; $(\lambda - \lambda_{\text{average}})$ denotes the deviation from the mean. **(g)** PL lifetime measurements at six different positions. **(h)** Spatial variation in PL lifetime characterized over 20 positions; $(\tau - \tau_{\text{average}})$ denotes the deviation from the mean. **(i)** Optical key generation demonstrated using samples with different PL wavelength thresholds. **(j)** Schematic of five distinct security keys extracted from a single PUF. All boxplots represent the interquartile range (IQR), extending from the first to third quartile, with a central line denoting the median, whiskers indicating the minimum and maximum, and hollow squares representing mean values.

Beyond the two directions described above, efforts are underway to make photonic PUFs more robust against environmental variations and even actively tunable. Environmental sensitivity, particularly to alignment, temperature, and mechanical vibration, remains a key limitation of many optical PUF implementations. To address this, integrated photonic structures with embedded reference channels or self-calibrating mechanisms have been proposed to compensate for extrinsic variations and ensure measurement stability [46]. [3]. Parallel efforts are being directed towards the development of reconfigurable photonic PUFs that dynamically alter their internal scattering profiles through external stimuli [44]. Such tunability can be achieved through the use of phase-change materials, microelectromechanical systems (MEMS), or liquid crystal elements. A reconfigurable PUF presents a moving target to potential attackers: even if one configuration is successfully modelled, subsequent configurations remain unpredictable. Furthermore, other research groups have proposed optical PUFs as quantum-secure primitives, where single-photon level manipulation is employed to prevent copying or eavesdropping [28]. While these areas are still nascent, they represent the evolving landscape of photonic PUF technology. Although these concepts remain in the early stages of development, they represent a significant expansion of the p-PUF design space and signal a shift toward more dynamic and resilient security primitives.

6.2 ENTRUST's p-PUF instance

As introduced in [21], the ENTRUST project investigates two distinct PUF-based implementations tailored to different operational requirements: (i) an SRAM-based PUF implementation designed to meet the stringent resource constraints of CMDs (detailed information for ENTRUST's SRAM-PUF instance can be found in [23], [20]), and (ii) a p-PUF instance, which offers enhanced security assurances and is intended for deployment in more centralized healthcare environments. The following subsections, are devoted to the latter. The first and second implementation phases are described in depth, along with experimental setups considered here as well as their main PUF characteristics (i.e. robustness, unpredictability and unclonability).

6.2.1 Speckle Imaging-based Optical (photonic) PUF instance realization

The original p-PUF, as introduced in [37], derives its nomenclature from the intrinsic reliance on the interaction between a coherent light source (serving as the challenge) and a structurally disordered optical medium. The light propagation through such a medium is governed by complex scattering phenomena, rendering the resulting behavior fundamentally unpredictable. In its canonical implementation, a laser beam is directed through an "optical token"—typically, a substrate composed of an epoxy resin embedded with randomly distributed microscopic refractive particles, as illustrated in Figure 6.4

The randomness in particle positioning, sizing, and orientation arises inherently from manufacturing process variations, leading to unique light-scattering behaviors for each token. The emergent light field, when captured at the output, forms a high-resolution optical speckle pattern, a complex arrangement of overlapping bright and dark fringes. This speckle pattern, constituting the PUF response, is influenced both by the intrinsic scattering properties of the medium and by the characteristics of the incident laser beam (e.g., wavelength, spatial coherence, and profile). To derive reproducible digital outputs, the speckle images are typically post-processed through a perceptual hashing technique, producing unique bit strings for each challenge-response pair.

Figure 6.4: A 3D inhomogeneous structure is optically hashed to produce a 2D image, which is subsequently filtered by a multiscale Gabor transform to generate a 1D cryptographic key. A 1 cm³ cube contains approximately 10¹² cubic blocks of 1 μm dimensions, comparable to the optical wavelength, corresponding to roughly a terabit of structural entropy. The captured 320×240 pixel image contains on the order of a megabit of intensity data, which is distilled into a 2400-bit key through Gabor-based dimensionality reduction [37].

6.2.2 First implementation phase: A Spatial Light Modulator at the heart of the ENTRUST’s p-PUF

The initial implementation of the ENTRUST’s p-PUF focused on constructing and evaluating a PUF instance that is based on coherent light scattering from digitally synthesized phase masks. Such a system relies on the deterministic transformation of a phase-modulated coherent wavefront into a complex speckle pattern, establishing a high-dimensional mapping from input challenges to unique optical responses.

Figure 6.5: The experimental setup created to evaluate different p-PUF configurations in the context of ENTRUST project.

The initial experimental setup (Figure 6.5) comprises of a stabilised continuous wave He-Ne laser emitting at 633 nm, a reflective spatial light modulator (SLM), Holoeye PLUTO-2.1 NIR, and a high quantum efficiency, Peltier cooled CMOS camera, Atik Camera ACICS 7.1. The laser beam is expanded to a diameter of 3.5 cm to uniformly illuminate the active region of the SLM. The SLM acts as a digitally recon-

figurable phase diffuser by setting the corresponding mask (i.e. "diffuser mask"), where each challenge is encoded as another spatially varying phase mask over the pixel array (i.e. "challenge mask"). These phase modulations alter the optical path length across the beam profile without affecting amplitude. Upon free-space propagation, the modulated wavefront undergoes interference, resulting in a spatial speckle intensity pattern recorded by the CMOS camera. Each speckle image is thus uniquely determined by the applied "challenge mask" to the corresponding "diffuser mask" and forms the final p-PUF response. In Figure 6.6 a challenge-response pair generated by the aforementioned experimental setup is presented.

Figure 6.6: An indicative example of the challenge generated by the SLM (left) and the corresponding response recorded by the CMOS camera (right).

In speckle-based optical PUF instances, a critical challenge that must be addressed to enable deployment in real-world applications is their inherent susceptibility to external environmental factors, which can significantly affect the operational robustness and consistency of the generated responses. The reproducibility of photonic PUF responses is governed by a combination of optical, mechanical, and electronic stability factors that collectively influence the consistency of the speckle patterns under repeated interrogation.

A primary source of variability stems from mechanical vibrations and misalignments within the optical setup. Even micrometer-scale displacements in the SLM, optical mounts, or imaging sensor can alter the relative phase relationships across the wavefront, thereby disrupting the resulting interference pattern. Ensuring structural rigidity and minimizing vibration transfer through stable optical benches is therefore essential. Ambient temperature fluctuations also pose a challenge by inducing thermal expansion in optical components and shifting the refractive index of the propagation medium, which can lead to slow phase drifts and decorrelation of the speckle field over time. In addition, the coherence and power stability of the laser source play a critical role. Variations in coherence length or intensity distribution can degrade speckle contrast and introduce temporal noise in the recorded response.

The fidelity of the phase modulation applied by the SLM is another significant factor. Non-idealities such as spatial phase inhomogeneities, quantization artifacts, and time-dependent drift in the liquid crystal alignment can lead to unintended modifications in the encoded phase masks. Similarly, the performance of the CMOS imaging sensor influences reproducibility, as pixel-level noise (e.g., shot noise, readout noise) and inconsistent exposure or gain settings may introduce variation in the recorded speckle intensities. To mitigate this, the use of fixed acquisition parameters and camera calibration is necessary. Additionally, the spatial uniformity of the laser beam across the SLM surface is crucial; any non-uniform illumination profile can cause asymmetric phase modulation, thus reducing the determinism of the challenge-response mapping. Finally, the resolution and definition of the digital phase challenges themselves influence reproducibility. High-resolution, well-separated phase masks reduce inter-challenge overlap and improve the likelihood that repeated applications of a given challenge yield near-identical optical responses.

Addressing these factors collectively ensures that the photonic PUF exhibits the necessary repeatability for robust and secure operation.

To that end, extensive experimental efforts were undertaken during the first 18 months of the project to design, implement, and refine the optical PUF setup presented herein. This process involved the systematic evaluation of several optical elements, coherent light sources, and high-resolution CMOS cameras, as well as the investigation of optical path stabilization strategies aimed at minimizing mechanical and thermal perturbations that could compromise response repeatability.

• **Robustness evaluation**

To quantitatively assess the robustness of the p-PUF system under repeated excitation, the Pearson correlation coefficient was utilized, which is a statistical measure of linear similarity between two variables. In the context of speckle-based PUFs, it is used to evaluate the similarity between two speckle images $I_1(x, y)$ and $I_2(x, y)$ generated in response to the same optical challenge at different time intervals.

The Pearson correlation coefficient r is defined as:

$$r = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (I_1(i) - \bar{I}_1)(I_2(i) - \bar{I}_2)}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N (I_1(i) - \bar{I}_1)^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N (I_2(i) - \bar{I}_2)^2}} \tag{6.1}$$

where N is the total number of pixels, and \bar{I}_1, \bar{I}_2 are the mean intensity values of images I_1 and I_2 , respectively. A value of $r = 1$ indicates perfect positive correlation (identical patterns), $r = 0$ indicates no correlation, and $r = -1$ denotes perfect negative correlation.

In the aforementioned experimental setup, the same phase challenge mask was applied to a constant diffuser mask over a 24-hour period, and speckle responses were captured at regular intervals. The Pearson correlation coefficient was computed pairwise between speckle images acquired at different times. The observed values, as shown in Figure 6.7, consistently remained above 0.975, with minimal variation over time. These results confirm that the p-PUF produces stable and reproducible responses under ambient environmental fluctuations, thus demonstrating high robustness, a critical property for real-world deployment of optical PUFs.

Figure 6.7: Pearson correlation coefficient computed between repeated speckle responses generated under a fixed optical challenge over a 24-hour period.

- **Key Extraction utilizing Random Binary Matrix perceptual hashing technique**

In general, the experimental evaluation of a speckle-based p-PUF entails the use of an imaging device, resulting in an unprocessed image for each run. Therefore, it was necessary to identify the most suitable perceptual hashing technique for the PUF's purpose. By definition, perceptual hashing is a method used to create compact digital fingerprints of visual content, such as images, such that perceptually similar inputs generate similar hash values, while perceptually different inputs generate distinctly different hashes. A perceptual hash extracts key visual features (such as low-frequency textures, spatial gradients, or symmetry) from an image and condenses them into a binary string. There are several image hashing algorithms in the literature, but for the p-PUF class considered here Random Binary Method (RBM) [8], is the most prominent [43], [35].

Essentially, RBM is a compressive sensing technique which, by exploiting the sparsity of a signal, enables its recovery with a sampling rate lower than that dictated by the Shannon–Nyquist theorem. This is achieved by multiplying the signal with a random table Θ , namely the *sensing matrix*, whose entries are usually selected from an identical and independent distribution (i.i.d.), such as Gaussian, sub-Gaussian, or Bernoulli [8]. The method can be summarized through the following relation:

$$\tilde{y} = \text{sign}(\Theta y) \quad (6.2)$$

where y is the standardized PUF response converted to a one-dimensional array of size $N = N_1 \times N_2$, \tilde{y} is its corresponding resultant hashed bit-string of length $M \leq N$, and $\text{sign}(\cdot)$ denotes the quantization function of the procedure. In practice, the sensing matrix used was defined as $\Theta = S \cdot F \cdot U$. The matrix U represents a diagonal random table of dimensions $N \times N$, containing only the values ± 1 with $\Pr[U_{ii} = 1] = \Pr[U_{ii} = -1] = 0.5$ (Rademacher distribution). The matrix F is the discrete Fourier transform matrix of size $N \times N$. Finally, S symbolizes a sampling matrix containing M entries randomly chosen from a uniform distribution over $(0, N)$; these indices are used to extract the corresponding $(FU) \cdot y$ elements, which constitute the hashed binary sequence \tilde{y} . The result of the above procedure is converted to binary by thresholding the real part of each extracted element using the mean of all sampled values. This alternative algorithm, as proposed in [43], has been shown to exhibit similar behavior to conventional techniques employing full Gaussian or sub-Gaussian distributions, while offering faster hash extraction.

To evaluate the robustness of the p-PUF at key-level utilizing RBM hashing technique described above, a statistical analysis of intra-device response stability was performed across multiple key lengths. The metric employed was the fractional Hamming Distance (HD) between repeated responses generated under similar conditions.

As depicted in Figure 6.8, for a key length of 2048 bits, the distribution of HD values exhibited a mean (μ) of 3.7% and a standard deviation (σ) of 1.6%. Similarly, the 1024-bit keys demonstrated a mean HD of 3.6% with a standard deviation of 1.5%, while the 512-bit keys achieved improved stability with $\mu = 2.6\%$ and $\sigma = 1.4\%$. Notably, the 256-bit keys exhibited slightly higher variability, with $\mu = 4.1\%$ and $\sigma = 2.3\%$, which is still within acceptable bounds for practical cryptographic applications. The observed behavior, where longer keys (e.g., 512, 1024, 2048 bits) exhibit lower intra-device HD and thus enhanced robustness compared to shorter keys (e.g., 256 bits), can be attributed to several interrelated factors. First, longer keys benefit from a *statistical averaging effect*. By aggregating a larger number of binary decisions across the full spatial structure of the speckle pattern, local noise fluctuations are averaged out, reducing their relative impact on the overall bitstream. In contrast, shorter keys contain fewer bits, so each bit contributes more significantly to the overall HD, making the key more sensitive to minor instabilities.

Furthermore, longer keys inherently possess *higher entropy and redundancy*, which increases their resilience to random perturbations. The expanded bit length provides a buffer against localized errors,

Fractional HD

Figure 6.8: Statistical distribution of fractional intra-device Hamming Distance (HD) values for key lengths of 2048, 1024, 512, and 256 bits, respectively. The low HD values (mean ranging from 2.6% to 4.1%) demonstrate the robustness and reproducibility of the p-PUF system considered here, under similar operating conditions.

enabling more consistent key regeneration. Shorter keys, lacking this redundancy, are more prone to instability. Also, from an optical sampling perspective, longer keys result in a *denser and more spatially distributed sampling* of the speckle field. This allows the RBM method to extract a more global and robust signature, whereas shorter keys may emphasize localized features that are more susceptible to optical path variations, such as slight shifts in alignment or illumination. Lastly, in terms of projection geometry, longer keys imply a greater number of projections M in the sensing matrix $\Theta = S \cdot F \cdot U$. This higher dimensionality improves robustness due to the *concentration of measure phenomenon*, whereby decision boundaries in high-dimensional projection spaces become more stable under noise. Shorter keys, with fewer projections, are more likely to exhibit threshold-crossing errors due to minor signal perturbations.

• **Unpredictability evaluation**

Upon the assessment of the p-PUF’s instance robustness the next step was to evaluate its unpredictability, i.e. the conditional probability of generating an identical output by applying two different challenges on the same PUF. To do so, 200 challenge masks were applied to a constant diffuser mask and the corresponding responses were analysed in terms of fractional HD. The results of the unpredictability study are presented in Figure 6.9 for different key lengths, as extracted utilizing RBM hashing technique. The results demonstrate that, across all key lengths considered here, the distribution of HD values closely follows a binomial-like curve centered around the ideal theoretical value of 0.5, which denotes maximum unpredictability.

Specifically, for key lengths of 2048, 1024, 512, and 256 bits, the mean HD (μ) consistently converged to 0.498, while the standard deviation (σ) increased modestly with decreasing key size: $\sigma = 0.016, 0.019, 0.025,$ and $0.033,$ respectively. This trend is expected, as shorter keys contain fewer independent bits and thus exhibit slightly higher statistical variance. Nevertheless, the narrow concentration of the distributions around 0.5 confirms that the PUF responses are highly uncorrelated across challenges, satisfying the unpredictability property essential for secure key generation.

Figure 6.9: Statistical distribution of inter-response (inter-challenge) fractional HD for key lengths of 2048 (a), 1024 (b), 512 (c), and 256 (d) bits. All distributions are tightly centered around the ideal mean $\mu = 0.498$, indicating strong unpredictability and statistical independence between keys derived from different challenges.

• **Unclonability evaluation**

The unclonability of the specific p-PUF system was quantitatively evaluated by analyzing the inter-device Hamming Distance (HD) across responses derived from 75 random diffuser masks subjected to an identical challenge mask. In a secure and unclonable system, these HD values should ideally follow a uniform distribution centered around 0.5, indicating complete statistical independence between the responses of different p-PUF instances.

The experimental results, shown in Figure 6.10 for key lengths of 2048, 1024, 512, and 256 bits, confirm this behavior. The mean inter-device HD values remained consistently centered around $\mu = 0.498-0.499$, while the standard deviation σ increased slightly with decreasing key length: $\sigma = 0.015$ for 2048 bits, 0.019 for 1024 bits, 0.025 for 512 bits, and 0.033 for 256 bits. This variance trend reflects the reduced entropy of shorter bitstrings but remains within the expected bounds for high-entropy PUF outputs.

These results substantiate the strong unclonability property of the system: distinct PUF instances, despite being structurally similar and identically challenged, produce responses that are effectively indistinguishable from random bitstrings. This is a critical security property, ensuring resistance against duplication or modeling attacks.

Figure 6.10: Distribution of inter-device (unclonability) fractinal HD for key lengths of 2048 (a), 1024 (b), 512 (c), and 256 (d) bits. The histograms, generated using RBM over responses from distinct diffuser masks under identical challenge conditions, show tightly centered distributions around $\mu \approx 0.499$ with increasing standard deviation σ for shorter keys. The results confirm the strong unclonability property of the PUF system, with negligible statistical correlation between responses from different devices.

6.2.3 Second implementation phase: Increasing the complexity of the ENTRUST’s p-PUF photonic core

Building upon the insights gained during the initial phase, the second implementation phase of the ENTRUST’s p-PUF aimed to further augment the system’s optical complexity and security characteristics. To achieve this, the original setup, comprising mainly a digitally reconfigurable SLM and a coherent light source, was retained, while a commercially available sandblasted glass was introduced into the optical path 40cm away from the CMOS. This new configuration, combining digital and physical scattering components, was designed to amplify the inherent randomness of the speckle generation process, thereby increasing entropy and enhancing resistance to potential modeling attacks, since now an adversary has to compute not only the transfer function of the SLM’s diffuser mask but also the corresponding of the actual diffuser. Since the results obtained from the first phase were encouraging considering the main features that a PUF should possess, the motivation for this extension stemmed from the desire to evaluate

the impact of added physical disorder on key PUF performance metrics, including robustness, unpredictability, and unclonability, considering that the main challenge of adding such a scattering medium is its mechanical stability as well as its temperature-dependent refractive index which can potentially affect several operational aspects of the system, mainly the robustness characteristics. In the following text, the experimental results obtained from this extended setup are presented and analyzed.

Figure 6.11: An indicative speckle pattern captured from the extended experimental setup when a challenge mask and a diffuser mask generated by the SLM are applied in a sandblasted glass.

• **Robustness evaluation with Physical Diffuser**

To evaluate the impact of added physical complexity on the PUF’s stability, the intra-device characteristics (i.e. robustness) were reassessed in terms of Pearson correlation coefficient and fractional HD using the same key extraction methodology described above. All measurements were conducted under identical illumination conditions and with the same SLM challenge configurations as previously employed for 24-hours continuous operation, thereby allowing a direct comparison between the two p-PUF instances, whereas the fractional HD distributions for key lengths of 2048, 1024, 512, and 256 bits were analyzed. The results of the robustness study are depicted in Figure 6.12 and Figure 6.13.

Figure 6.12: Pearson correlation coefficient of the new p-PUF instance computed between repeated speckle responses generated under a fixed optical challenge over a 24-hour period.

Figure 6.12 illustrates the Pearson correlation coefficient over time for the modified setup with the additional diffuser glass. The results indicate a slight degradation in reproducibility compared to the previous p-PUF instance ((Figure 6.8)), but are considered more than acceptable for a system of that complexity, composed of two scattering media.

Figure 6.13: Statistical distribution of fractional intra-device HD values for key lengths of 2048, 1024, 512, and 256 bits, respectively.

The key-level robustness, measured through intra-device HD distributions for various key lengths (Figure 6.13), reveals such a modest reduction in stability. Intra-device HD distributions for keys of length 2048, 1024, 512, and 256 bits were compared between the two configurations (Table 6.1). The added diffuser resulted in slightly higher HD values, indicating a marginal degradation in bit-level reproducibility. However, all values remained below the typical 10–15% threshold used in fuzzy extractor designs.

Key Length (bits)	Mean HD (SLM-only) [%]	Mean HD (SLM+Diffuser) [%]	Δ HD [%]
2048	3.7	4.6	+0.9
1024	3.6	5.0	+1.4
512	2.6	4.9	+2.3
256	4.1	4.7	+0.6

Table 6.1: Comparison of intra-device HD values between the SLM-only setup and the SLM plus diffuser configuration.

Based on the aforementioned results, we can conclude that the addition of the physical diffuser successfully increased the entropy and optical path complexity of the p-PUF system with out compromising

its robustness. Although a moderate reduction in repeatability and bit-level stability was observed, the robustness remained within acceptable cryptographic limits. This trade-off is acceptable given the significant gain in resistance to modeling and cloning, making the modified configuration more suitable for high-security applications.

• **Unpredictability evaluation with Physical Diffuser**

This experimental phase focused on assessing the inter-challenge unpredictability of the p-PUF under an augmented optical configuration that incorporates a physical diffuser in addition to the phase-only SLM. The unpredictability property, which reflects the system’s ability to generate decorrelated responses under varying challenge inputs, was evaluated through the statistical analysis of inter- fractional HD values. Ideally, a uniformly random behavior would yield an inter-HD centered around 0.5, indicating minimal correlation among distinct challenge-response pairs.

The obtained results (Figure 6.14) across all tested key lengths—2048, 1024, 512, and 256 bits—demonstrated that the mean inter-HD values for the new setup remained tightly concentrated around this ideal reference, exhibiting marginal deviations in the range of 0.494–0.495. In comparison to the former configuration where the HDs extracted was in the range of 0.498-0.494, these values still indicate strong unpredictability.

Figure 6.14: Distribution of inter-HD values across different key lengths for the SLM plus Diffuser setup, showing robust unpredictability and convergence toward the ideal value of 0.5.

• **Uclonality evaluation with Physical Diffuser**

To assess the unclonability of the new p-PUF instance with the physical diffuser, a dedicated study was conducted using 20 distinct diffuser configurations (i.e. diffuser clones), each representing a physically unique instantiation of the PUF system. For each configuration, binary keys were extracted under identical challenge conditions, and the inter-fractional HD was computed to quantify the dissimilarity across devices (Figure 6.15).

Figure 6.15: Distribution of inter-fractional HDs derived from 20 physically distinct diffuser-based photonic PUF instances. Each plot corresponds to a different key length (2048, 1024, 512, and 256 bits). The results confirm excellent unclonability, with all mean inter-HD values approximating the ideal value of 0.5.

The experimental results demonstrated that the mean inter-HD values remained very close to the ideal value of 0.5, with observed averages of 0.498 for 2048- and 1024-bit keys, 0.500 for 512-bit keys, and 0.499 for 256-bit keys. This convergence toward the theoretical maximum of randomness underscores the high inter-device entropy of the photonic PUF, thereby validating its strong unclonability properties.

These findings indicate that even though the same optical setup was used across all experiments, the introduction of distinct diffuser plates yields highly uncorrelated speckle patterns, ensuring that no two devices produce the same binary output under identical input conditions. Such statistical behavior is fundamental for secure hardware fingerprinting, non-replicable key generation, and robust device authentication in real-world quantum-resistant infrastructures.

By comparing these findings with the SLM-only configuration, it is evident that in both cases the expected ideal HD mean for two uncorrelated keys remains close to 0.5, indicating maximum entropy and unpredictability. The addition of the diffuser did not degrade unclonability. On the contrary, it slightly improved the randomness for certain key lengths, as evidenced by a more ideal centering around the theoretical value (e.g., $\mu = 0.500$ for 512-bit keys). However, in order to make more concrete statements regarding

the system's unclonability, a broader evaluation involving a larger number of distinct diffusers should be conducted.

6.3 Results Summary and Future Research Activities

The experimental investigation of the speckle-based p-PUF progressed through two phases, each introducing increasing optical complexity to assess response stability, unpredictability, and unclonability.

In **Phase 1**, a baseline setup utilizing a phase-only SLM was established. Speckle responses were generated under varied challenges and converted into binary keys using RBM. Robustness analysis indicated consistent intra-HD values across key sizes, with mean values ranging between 2.6% and 4.1%. Unpredictability and unclonability evaluations confirmed the statistical randomness and uniqueness of responses, with inter-HD values clustering tightly around 0.498–0.499. Importantly, intra- and inter-HD distributions remained **well separated**, affirming the extremely low false acceptance and false rejection rates.

In **Phase 2**, the optical setup was augmented with the insertion of a physical diffuser, aiming to increase the scattering complexity of the optical path. Despite the fact that robustness slightly decreased compared to the SLM-only configuration, as indicated by higher intra-HD values across all key lengths, it retained in acceptable levels for cryptographic applications. Unpredictability also exhibited a minor deterioration, with average inter-HD values marginally reduced, suggesting an increased correlation among responses to different challenges. Moreover, unclonability was not compromised, as measurements across 20 physically distinct diffuser instances yielded inter-HD values consistently centered around the ideal 0.5. These results confirm that while the added optical complexity introduced slight performance trade-offs, the uniqueness and physical non-replicability of the PUF responses were retained.

Future Research Directions

To further advance the robustness and security guarantees of the proposed photonic PUF architecture, several avenues of investigation are identified:

- **Scaling Unclonability Evaluation:** Expand the population of photonic instances (e.g., distinct diffuser plates) beyond the current cohort of 20, to better assess statistical distribution properties and identify potential edge-case vulnerabilities.
- **Environmental Characterization:** Examine the sensitivity of the system to environmental disturbances such as temperature fluctuations, mechanical vibrations, and optical alignment perturbations, to quantify operational boundaries and tolerances.
- **Explore other image hashing techniques:** Evaluate alternative image hashing and key extraction algorithms beyond RBM and SVD, including deep perceptual hashing, wavelet-based descriptors, or learned compact representations, to improve the trade-off between entropy extraction, robustness, and computational efficiency.
- **Longitudinal Stability Studies:** Evaluate the temporal consistency of PUF responses over extended periods and under varying storage and usage conditions to assess long-term operational reliability.
- **Resistance to Machine Learning-Based Attacks:** Perform adversarial modeling evaluations to test for structural or statistical regularities in the PUF responses that may be exploited by supervised learning models trained on known challenge-response pairs.

Chapter 7

Conclusions

This deliverable, **D4.3**, has presented the final release of the **ENTRUST Runtime Assurance and Certification Framework**, representing the culmination of the design, implementation, and security analysis efforts of **Work Package 4**. This concluding chapter provides a comprehensive overview of the key achievements detailed in Chapters 2 through 6, which collectively establish a complete and integrated solution for the secure lifecycle management of **Connected Medical Devices (CMDs)** within a **zero-trust architecture**.

As outlined in Chapters 2 and 3, the ENTRUST architecture and its core **Trusted Computing Base (TCB)** have been finalized to support a diverse range of CMDs. A central contribution of this work is the realization of a practical **dual-credential model**, where **manufacturer-issued Verifiable Credentials** support secure device onboarding, while **domain-issued Conformity Certificates (CCs)** enable dynamic, fine-grained runtime trust assessment. The extensive benchmarking results presented for TCB components—including their integration with hardware-based trust anchors like **PUFs on wearable CMDs**—demonstrate their operational feasibility, confirming that robust security can be achieved without imposing prohibitive overhead on resource-constrained platforms.

The security of the framework's cryptographic underpinnings, detailed in Chapters 4 and 5, has been substantiated through rigorous **security proofs**. Chapter 4 provided a comprehensive security proof for the core cryptographic schemes, including the **Attribute-Based Signcryption (ABSC)** protocols and the **privacy-preserving Attribute-Based Credentials (p-ABCs)** used for Conformity Certificate management. These proofs formally demonstrate essential properties such as **unforgeability**, **confidentiality (IND-CPA)**, **attribute privacy**, and **key binding**. Complementing this, Chapter 5 introduced the finalized **Agile Swarm Attestation** protocol, a scalable solution for managing the collective trustworthiness of low-end device clusters. The security proof for this scheme, conducted within the **Universal Composability (UC) model**, confirms its resilience in complex, multi-party environments.

Beyond the core implementation, Chapter 6 documented the project's forward-looking research into **alternative hardware Roots-of-Trust**. The detailed exploration of **photonic PUFs (p-PUFs)** and the experimental results from a two-phase implementation confirmed their significant potential. The findings highlighted their **high entropy** and **strong unclonability** characteristics, which offer enhanced resistance to physical duplication and modeling attacks, positioning p-PUFs as a promising technology for future high-security applications.

In summary, the ENTRUST Runtime Assurance and Certification Framework, as finalized across the preceding chapters, provides a comprehensive, cryptographically sound, and scalable architecture for ensuring **end-to-end trust** in the CMD lifecycle. By delivering a full suite of security mechanisms backed by extensive security proofs and performance analysis, ENTRUST has laid a definitive foundation for the development and adoption of **trustworthy and resilient medical infrastructures**.

Appendix A

Glossary

(Medical) Domain Refers to the entirety of the infrastructure of the medical organization where a Connected Medical Device (CMD) is deployed, including the backend infrastructure (servers), medical devices operating within the organization, and interconnectivity between all aforementioned entities.

ATL The Actual Trust Level (ATL) reflects the result of an evaluation of a trust proposition, for a specific CMD, as defined in a trust model managed by the ENTRUST Trust Assessment Framework (TAF). It quantifies the extent to which a certain node or data can be considered trustworthy based on the available evidence.

Attestation Agent The component of the CMD which is responsible for the execution of the attestation logic of an attestation enabler, as well as communicating with external entities in order to share attestation-related information.

Authentication The process which aims to verify the authenticity of a device, prior to its Onboarding and Enrolment into the (Medical) Domain. This process is performed by the Authentication Server of the Manufacturing domain through the Domain Manager, using the Root ID Key of the device.

Authentication Server The Authentication Server is responsible for authenticating the device using its Root ID Key, in order to enable its enrolment and onboarding into the (Medical) Domain.

CMD A medical device that has been deployed, enrolled, and onboarded into a (Medical) Domain. Note that this term cannot be used during the Manufacturing (Design) Phase of the ENTRUST action workflow, since this phase considers the device in isolation, and can only be applied during the Pre-deployment (Domain-specific) Phase and the Runtime Phase of the ENTRUST action workflow.

Conformity Certificate A certificate which is created after a successful attestation process on a device and is stored on the ledger, so that an external entity is able to audit the correctness of the attested set of attributes of the device. The Conformity Certificate utilizes Privacy Attribute-Based Credentials (PABCs) in order to share those attributes in a privacy-preserving manner.

Device Tracer The capabilities of the device (e.g., eBPFs) to collect types of trust evidence or attestation evidence specified by the Trust Policy of the device in order to prove the correctness of the required trust attributes of the device.

Device-level eMUD Defines the foundational security requirements of a device, outlining the necessary operational characteristics to mitigate threats and vulnerabilities, considering the device in isolation (i.e., before it is deployed to the actual medical domain).

Domain Manager The Domain Manager is a centralized server deployed at the infrastructure level of a (Medical) Domain, responsible for the Authentication, Enrolment, and Onboarding of medical devices into the domain. It also acts as an orchestrator for the operation of all ENTRUST components between the medical domain, as well as the mediator between the device, the Blockchain infrastructure, and the MUD Server.

Domain-level eMUD Extends the Device-level extended Manufacturer Usage Description (eMUD) in order to include device characteristics, threats, and vulnerabilities that considering its positioning within the medical domain, and specifies security enablers for mitigating domain-level threats and vulnerabilities.

Enrolment Entails the issuance of the set of Verifiable Credentials (VCs) of a device through the Privacy Certification Authority (CA), after it has been successfully authenticated.

Formal Verification The Formal Verification component is the component of the ENTRUST framework which is responsible for checking whether the design of the device satisfies the security requirements identified for the particular device, by specifying and using models of the critical security protocols and schemes of ENTRUST and checking whether the security properties hold for the specific model.

Key Restriction Usage Policy A local attestation policy dictating that a specific cryptographic key cannot be used by a device, unless it is known to be in a correct and trustworthy state, based on the characteristics contained in the Policy Hash of the device.

Manufacturing (Design) Phase The Manufacturing phase of the ENTRUST framework includes all actions taken from the construction of the actual device until it leaves the manufacturing domain and is deployed to the medical domain where it will be enrolled and onboarded. This phase includes the identification of threats and vulnerabilities by the Manufacturer and the Threat Modeling (TM) component, the Formal Verification of the source code and binaries on the device, the emulation of identified threats using the of the device, and an initial Risk Assessment (RA) of the device in isolation (i.e., before it is actually deployed to the medical domain).

Merkle Tree A Merkle tree is a data structure used in cryptography that efficiently verifies the integrity and consistency of data. It consists of leaves that represent data blocks and non-leaf nodes that are cryptographic hashes of their child nodes, culminating in a single root hash that securely represents the entire data..

MUD Server The MUD Server is responsible for the storage of the Device-level eMUD and the Domain-level extended Manufacturer Usage Description (eMUD) of the CMDs. They can be retrieved based on the MUD URL provided by the Manufacturer and contained within the device, so that the specified security controls can be applied by the device.

Onboarding Entails the integration of a medical device into the (Medical) Domain, after its successful Authentication and Enrolment. In this context, the device needs to provide a Verifiable Presentation (VP) to the Domain Manager containing the set of attributes that the device needs to verifiably prove ownership of in order to be enrolled into the domain.

OP-TEE OP-TEE (Open Portable Trusted Execution Environment) is an open-source project that provides a secure, isolated execution environment for running trusted applications on modern Arm-based systems. It ensures confidentiality and integrity of sensitive data and operations by leveraging hardware security features..

Policy Hash Values that can be used in order to verify the operational correctness of the device based on specific characteristics of the device (e.g., secure boot output, type of Secure Element, Trusted Computing Base (TCB) specification).

Pre-deployment (Domain-specific) Phase The Pre-deployment (Domain-specific) phase of the ENTRUST framework includes the actions taken from the moment the device is deployed from the Manufacturer to the medical domain, until it begins its actual operation in the context of the domain. It includes two core phases: (i) The device authentication, enrolment, and onboarding, and (ii) the re-evaluation of the recalculation of the Required Trust Level (RTL) of the device based on domain-specific threats and vulnerabilities identified by the System Administrator, the Threat Modeling, the , and the Formal Verification component.

Privacy CA The entity responsible for the issuance of the Verifiable Credentials (VCs) of the CMD containing the device attributes or characteristics based on which Trust Assessment is performed, after it has been successfully authenticated through the Authentication Server.

Protection Profile The Protection Profile of the device is the part of the Device-level eMUD or Domain-level eMUD which contains the identified threats and vulnerabilities for the device, as well as the mitigation measures which can be employed for their mitigation during runtime.

PUF A physical unclonable function (PUF), also known as a physically-unclonable function (which represents a slightly less secure measure), is a unique physical object that cannot be replicated through physical means using the same technology. Given a specific input and set of conditions (challenge), it generates a distinct "digital fingerprint" (response) that serves as a unique identifier..

Remote Attestation A secure mechanism where a Verifier entity aims to verify the correctness of one or more attributes of a Prover device (e.g., configuration integrity or control flow). This is typically performed by the Verifier issuing an attestation challenge to the Prover, who needs to collect the appropriate data as attestation evidence (using its Device Tracer) and construct the appropriate response in order to prove the correctness of the specified attributes.

Risk Assessment The Risk Assessment component of ENTRUST is responsible for performing risk quantification on the device based on all the identified threats and vulnerabilities, both at the manufacturing domain considering the device in isolation, and at the medical domain considering the interdependencies of the device with other entities of the service graph chain. It is also responsible for the calculation of the RTL of the device based on the identified threats and vulnerabilities, as well as its recalculation in case new threats or zero-day exploits are detected during runtime.

RoT The (Hardware) Root of Trust (RoT) is the minimal set of security guarantees usually provided by the hardware that is sufficient to guarantee the security of a larger TCB.

RTL The RTL reflects the amount of trustworthiness a device considers required in order to characterize it as trusted, based on the identified threats and vulnerabilities for the particular type of device.

Runtime Phase The Runtime phase includes all actions in order to ensure the trustworthiness of the CMD during runtime. This entails the execution of security controls, such as Remote Attestation (RA) schemes and the runtime calculation of the Actual Trust Level (ATL) of the CMD. In case $ATL < RTL$, the device is determined to be in an untrustworthy state and additional mitigation measures may need to be applied, such as the deployment of a Secure Software Update.

Secure Software Update This process refers to the secure deployment of a software or firmware patch through the of the device, in case a vulnerability has been detected and needs to be addressed.

Software Verification The Software Verification component is responsible for checking the safety of software applications running on the medical device, as well as libraries running on the device, using Indices of Compromise from multiple intelligence sources based on the identified threat landscape.

System Administrator The person or entity who has in-depth knowledge of the (Medical) Domain and its specific requirements, is responsible for providing information on domain-specific threats and vulnerabilities to the Risk Assessment component, and is able to re-assess the risks identified by the ENTRUST component and the mitigation measures required in order to address them.

TAF A software framework which, given a trust model for a specific function running inside a CMD, is able to evaluate trust sources for trustworthiness evidence, as well as evaluate propositions within the trust model to obtain their ATLS. An RTL can also be evaluated and trust decisions can be taken and communicated to the application.

TCB The Trusted Computing Base (TCB) of a computer system is the set of all hardware, firmware, and/or software components that are critical to its security, in the sense that bugs or vulnerabilities occurring inside the TCB might jeopardize the security properties of the entire system. By contrast, parts of a computer system that lie outside the TCB must not be able to misbehave in a way that would leak any more privileges than are granted to them in accordance to the system's security policy.

Threat Intelligence Database A common database which contains the threats and vulnerabilities identified for a medical device by the ENTRUST framework, and can be accessed by other device manufacturers as threat intelligence knowledge towards increasing the security posture of devices operating within the medical domain.

Threat Modeling The Threat Modeling component is responsible for identifying known threats and vulnerabilities for a specific type of device based on existing threat intelligence databases, and aggregating them into an attack vector using an .

Trust Policy A smart contract deployed to the private ledger, which specifies the RTL of the device, as well as the types of trust evidence that needs to be collected in order to verify the correctness of the trust attributes of the device.

Bibliography

- [1] Georg Becker. Merkle signature schemes, merkle trees and their cryptanalysis. Ruhr-University Bochum, Tech. Rep, 12:19, 2008.
- [2] Daniel J Bernstein, Christoph Dobraunig, Maria Eichlseder, Scott Fluhrer, Stefan-Lukas Gazdag, Andreas Hülsing, Panos Kampanakis, Stefan Kölbl, Tanja Lange, Martin M Lauridsen, et al. Sphincs, 2017.
- [3] Farhan Bin Tarik, Azadeh Famili, Yingjie Lao, and Judson D Ryckman. Robust optical physical unclonable function using disordered photonic integrated circuits. Nanophotonics, 9(9):2817–2828, 2020.
- [4] Dan Boneh, Craig Gentry, Ben Lynn, and Hovav Shacham. Aggregate and verifiably encrypted signatures from bilinear maps. In International conference on the theory and applications of cryptographic techniques, pages 416–432. Springer, 2003.
- [5] Bryan T Bosworth, Iskandar A Atakhodjaev, Michael R Kossey, Brian C Grubel, Daniel S Vresilovic, Jasper R Stroud, Neil MacFarlane, Jesús Villalba, Najim Dehak, A Brinton Cooper, et al. Unclonable photonic keys hardened against machine learning attacks. APL Photonics, 5(1), 2020.
- [6] Ernie Brickell, Jan Camenisch, and Liqun Chen. Direct anonymous attestation. In Proceedings of the 11th ACM conference on Computer and communications security, pages 132–145, 2004.
- [7] Johannes Buchmann, Erik Dahmen, Sarah Ereth, Andreas Hülsing, and Markus Rückert. On the security of the winternitz one-time signature scheme. International Journal of Applied Cryptography, 3(1):84–96, 2013.
- [8] Emmanuel J Candès and Michael B Wakin. An introduction to compressive sampling. IEEE signal processing magazine, 25(2):21–30, 2008.
- [9] Hui Cao and Yaniv Eliezer. Harnessing disorder for photonic device applications. Applied Physics Reviews, 9(1), 2022.
- [10] Feiliang Chen, Qian Li, Mo Li, Feng Huang, Hui Zhang, Jianbin Kang, and Pidong Wang. Unclonable fluorescence behaviors of perovskite quantum dots/chaotic metasurfaces hybrid nanostructures for versatile security primitive. Chemical Engineering Journal, 411:128350, 2021.
- [11] Liqun Chen, Nada El Kasseem, Anja Lehmann, and Vadim Lyubashevsky. A framework for efficient lattice-based daa. In Proceedings of the 1st ACM Workshop on Workshop on Cyber-Security Arms Race, pages 23–34, 2019.
- [12] Liqun Chen, Ming-Feng Lee, and Bogdan Warinschi. Security of the enhanced TCG privacy-CA solution. In Trustworthy Global Computing: 6th International Symposium, TGC 2011, Aachen, Germany, June 9-10, 2011. Revised Selected Papers 6, pages 121–141. Springer, 2012.

- [13] Yarkin Doröz, Jeffrey Hoffstein, Joseph H Silverman, and Berk Sunar. Mmsat: a scheme for multi-message multiuser signature aggregation. [Cryptology ePrint Archive](#), 2020.
- [14] Manu Drijvers, Sergey Gorbunov, Gregory Neven, and Hoeteck Wee. Pixel: Multi-signatures for consensus. In [USENIX Security Symposium \(USENIX Security\)](#), pages 2093–2110, 2020.
- [15] Yang Du, Sasi Jothibas, Yiyang Zhuang, Chen Zhu, and Jie Huang. Unclonable optical fiber identification based on rayleigh backscattering signatures. [Journal of Lightwave Technology](#), 35(21):4634–4640, 2017.
- [16] Léo Ducas, Eike Kiltz, Tancrede Lepoint, Vadim Lyubashevsky, Peter Schwabe, Gregor Seiler, and Damien Stehlé. Crystals-dilithium: A lattice-based digital signature scheme. [IACR Transactions on Cryptographic Hardware and Embedded Systems](#), pages 238–268, 2018.
- [17] Nada El Kassem, Liqun Chen, Rachid El Bansarkhani, Ali El Kaafarani, Jan Camenisch, Patrick Hough, Paulo Martins, and Leonel Sousa. More efficient, provably-secure direct anonymous attestation from lattices. [Future Generation Computer Systems](#), 99:425–458, 2019.
- [18] Nada El Kassem, Wouter Hellekens, Ioannis Siachos, Edlira Dushku, Stefanos Vasileiadis, Dimitrios S Karas, Liqun Chen, Constantinos Patsakis, and Thanassis Giannetsos. Privé: Towards privacy-preserving swarm attestation. In [22nd International Conference on Security and Cryptography](#), pages 247–262, 2025.
- [19] Nada El Kassem, Wouter Hellekens, Ioannis Siachos, Edlira Dushku, Stefanos Vasileiadis, Dimitrios S. Karas, Liqun Chen, Constantinos Patsakis, and Thanassis Giannetsos. PrivÉ : Towards privacy-preserving swarm attestation. In [Proceedings of the 22nd International Conference on Security and Cryptography](#), pages 247–262, 2025.
- [20] ENTRUST. Runtime assurance certification framework first release. Deliverable D4.2, The ENTRUST Consortium.
- [21] ENTRUST. D2.1 entrust reference architecture - initial release. Deliverable D2.1, The ENTRUST Consortium, 12 2024.
- [22] ENTRUST. D3.2 risk assessment and collective threat intelligence framework - initial release. Deliverable D3.2, The ENTRUST Consortium, 18 2024.
- [23] ENTRUST. D4.1 conceptual architecture of entrust customizable tc attestation models specifications. Deliverable D4.1, The ENTRUST Consortium, 15 2024.
- [24] ENTRUST. D6.1 integrated framework (first release) and use case analysis. Technical Report D6.1, The ENTRUST Consortium, 21 2024.
- [25] Jesús García-Rodríguez, Stephan Krenn, Jorge Bernal Bernabe, and Antonio Skarmeta. Beyond selective disclosure: Extending distributed p-ABC implementations by commit-and-prove techniques. [Computer Networks](#), 248:110498, June 2024.
- [26] Brian C. Grubel, Bryan T. Bosworth, Michael R. Kossey, Hongcheng Sun, A. Brinton Cooper, Mark A. Foster, and Amy C. Foster. Silicon photonic physical unclonable function. [Optics Express](#), 25(11):12710–12721, 2017.
- [27] Ruijie Hui, Feiliang Chen, Mo Li, and Jian Zhang. Non-linear optical scattering puf: enhancing security against modeling attacks for authentication systems. [Optics Express](#), 31(24):40646–40657, 2023.

- [28] H Shelton Jacinto, A Matthew Smith, and Nader I Rafla. Utilizing a fully optical and reconfigurable puf as a quantum authentication mechanism. OSA Continuum, 4(2):739–747, 2021.
- [29] Irakliy Khaburzaniya, Konstantinos Chalkias, Kevin Lewi, and Harjasleen Malvai. Aggregating and thresholdizing hash-based signatures using starks. In Proceedings of the 2022 ACM on Asia Conference on Computer and Communications Security, pages 393–407, 2022.
- [30] Min Seok Kim, Gil Ju Lee, Jung Woo Leem, Seunggho Choi, Young L Kim, and Young Min Song. Revisiting silk: a lens-free optical physical unclonable function. Nature Communications, 13(1):247, 2022.
- [31] Benjamin Larsen, Nada El Kassem, Thanassis Giannetsos, Ioannis Krontiris, Stefanos Vasileiadis, and Liqun Chen. Achieving higher level of assurance in privacy preserving identity wallets. In 2023 IEEE 22nd International Conference on Trust, Security and Privacy in Computing and Communications (TrustCom), pages 1049–1059. IEEE, 2023.
- [32] Jung Woo Leem, Min Seok Kim, Seung Ho Choi, Seong-Ryul Kim, Seong-Wan Kim, Young Min Song, Robert J Young, and Young L Kim. Edible unclonable functions. Nature communications, 11(1):328, 2020.
- [33] T. Looker, V. Kalos, A. Whitehead, and M. Lodder. The bbs signature scheme, 2023.
- [34] Mohammad Amin Mahdian, Ebadollah Taheri, Kaveh Rahbardar Mojaver, and Mahdi Nikdast. Hardware assurance with silicon photonic physical unclonable functions. Scientific Reports, 14(1):25591, 2024.
- [35] Charis Mesaritakis, Marialena Akriotou, Alexandros Kapsalis, Evangelos Grivas, Charidimos Chaintoutis, Thomas Nikas, and Dimitris Syvridis. Physical unclonable function based on a multi-mode optical waveguide. Scientific Reports, 8(1):9653, 2018.
- [36] David Nowak. A framework for game-based security proofs. In Information and Communications Security: 9th International Conference, ICICS 2007, Zhengzhou, China, December 12-15, 2007. Proceedings 9, pages 319–333. Springer, 2007.
- [37] Ravi Pappu, Benjamin Recht, Jason Taylor, and Neil Gershenfeld. Physical one-way functions. Science, 297(5589):2026–2030, 2002.
- [38] Fabio Pavanello, Ian O'Connor, Ulrich Rührmair, Amy C Foster, and Dimitris Syvridis. Recent advances in photonic physical unclonable functions. In 2021 IEEE European Test Symposium (ETS), pages 1–10. IEEE, 2021.
- [39] Fabio Pavanello, Ian O'Connor, Ulrich Rührmair, Amy C. Foster, and Dimitris Syvridis. Recent advances in photonic physical unclonable functions. In 2021 IEEE European Test Symposium (ETS), pages 1–10, 2021.
- [40] MAES Roel. Physically unclonable functions: Constructions, properties and applications. Katholieke Universiteit Leuven, Belgium, pages 148–160, 2012.
- [41] Ulrich Rührmair, Christian Hilgers, Sebastian Urban, Agnes Weiershäuser, Elias Dinter, Brigitte Forster, and Christian Jirauschek. Revisiting optical physical unclonable functions. IACR Cryptol. ePrint Arch., 2013:215, 2013.

- [42] Raphael Schermann, Rainer Urian, Ronald Toegl, Holger Bock, and Christian Steger. Enabling anonymous authenticated encryption with a novel anonymous authenticated credential key agreement (AACKA). In 2022 IEEE International Conference on Trust, Security and Privacy in Computing and Communications (TrustCom), pages 646–655. IEEE, 2022.
- [43] Saloomeh Shariati, François-Xavier Standaert, Laurent Jacques, and Benoit Macq. Analysis and experimental evaluation of image-based pufs. Journal of Cryptographic Engineering, 2:189–206, 2012.
- [44] Amos Matthew Smith and H Shelton Jacinto. Reconfigurable integrated optical interferometer network-based physically unclonable function. Journal of Lightwave Technology, 38(17):4599–4606, 2020.
- [45] Joshua D Smith, Md Alimoor Reza, Nathanael L Smith, Jianxin Gu, Maha Ibrar, David J Crandall, and Sara E Skrabalak. Plasmonic anticounterfeit tags with high encoding capacity rapidly authenticated with deep machine learning. ACS nano, 15(2):2901–2910, 2021.
- [46] Farhan Bin Tarik, Azadeh Famili, Yingjie Lao, and Judson D Ryckman. Scalable and cmos compatible silicon photonic physical unclonable functions for supply chain assurance. Scientific Reports, 12(1):15653, 2022.
- [47] Jingyang Wang, Qiang Zhang, Runzhi Chen, Jing Li, Jinhua Wang, Guyue Hu, Mingyue Cui, Xin Jiang, Bin Song, and Yao He. Triple-layer unclonable anti-counterfeiting enabled by huge-encoding capacity algorithm and artificial intelligence authentication. Nano Today, 41:101324, 2021.
- [48] Kun Wang, Jianwei Shi, Wenxuan Lai, Qiang He, Jun Xu, Zhenyi Ni, Xinfeng Liu, Xiaodong Pi, and Deren Yang. All-silicon multidimensionally-encoded optical physical unclonable functions for integrated circuit anti-counterfeiting. Nature Communications, 15:3203, 2024.
- [49] Pidong Wang, Feiliang Chen, Dong Li, Song Sun, Feng Huang, Taiping Zhang, Qian Li, Kun Chen, Yongbiao Wan, Xiao Leng, and Yao Yao. Authentication of optical physical unclonable functions based on single-pixel detection. Micromachines, 12(4):432, 2021.
- [50] Chao Xiang, Steven M Bowers, Alexis Bjorlin, Robert Blum, and John E Bowers. Perspective on the future of silicon photonics and electronics. Applied Physics Letters, 118(22), 2021.
- [51] Kang Yang, Liqun Chen, Zhenfeng Zhang, Christopher JP Newton, Bo Yang, and Li Xi. Direct anonymous attestation with optimal tpm signing efficiency. IEEE transactions on information forensics and security, 16:2260–2275, 2021.

